

Evolution of Halley-type Comets and Meteoroid Streams

A thesis submitted for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Physics

by

Aswin Sekhar, B.Sc., M.Sc., M.Phil.

Armagh Observatory
United Kingdom

&

School of Mathematics and Physics
The Queen's University of Belfast
United Kingdom

Apr 2014

Declaration

This thesis was submitted for evaluation and accepted after examination in accordance with the requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Physics of the Queen's University of Belfast, United Kingdom. I certify that the contents of this thesis is solely my own work, other than where I have clearly indicated so, and has not been presented for the award of any other degree, title or fellowship elsewhere.

External Examiner:

Dr Jérémie Vaubaillon
Institut de Mécanique Céleste et de Calcul des Éphémérides
Paris Observatory, France

Internal Examiner:

Dr Apostolos Christou
Armagh Observatory, United Kingdom

Principal Supervisor:

Dr David Asher
Armagh Observatory, United Kingdom

Ph.D Candidate:

Aswin Sekhar

Student Number: 29056314

Armagh Observatory and Queen's University of Belfast

'I do not know what I may appear to the world, but to myself I seem to have been only like a boy playing on the sea-shore, and diverting myself in now and then finding a smoother pebble or a prettier shell than ordinary, whilst the great ocean of truth lay all undiscovered before me.' - **Sir Isaac Newton**

In memory of my ancestors,
Rao Bahadur Dr P K Warriar and Vaidyaratnam P S Varier, who were
role models to our family in terms of excellence, ethics and etiquette

Acknowledgements

I wish to mention my special gratitude to:

1. David for his scientifically rigorous + socially composed discussions (academic as well as non-academic). Words remain futile to express how much I have learnt from this thorough gentleman in the last three years.
2. Mark for his time and patience during my sensical as well as nonsensical rants about various topics in astrophysics. I have always been amazed at his proficiency in diverse areas (unlike the super specialists these days!) of astronomy.
3. Tolis for his brainy as well as super witty remarks about research+other things in life. Good mathematician + fine comedian is a unique personality for sure :) Thanks for his time and suggestions to improve the thesis.
4. Jeremie for lots of helpful comments to improve my thesis. It has always been a pleasure to discuss science with him during many conferences.
5. Gavin for being my supportive and helpful second supervisor. Thanks very much.
6. Mihalis for his comments and guidance during QUB differentiation process.
7. Jorick for sparing his valuable time for being the independent chairman during the long four hour grilling :)
8. Gerry for the role of an excellent Observatory-QUB interface.
9. Simon for always actively involving during the talks and discussion meetings I led during the last 3 years. It has helped me to improve my grasp on fundamental principles.
10. Stefano for some interesting insights into asteroidal geometry and orbits.
11. John Butler for the interesting conversations about cinema, politics, culture, travelling, music, science, books, nature, theatre etc. The list simply goes on. Recently I noticed that there is none in NI who does not know him :) Special thanks for allowing me to host many parties at his place.
12. James for interesting conversations on many legends in electromagnetism.
13. John McFarland for helping me in finding many papers and books. He is one of the quietest and calmest people I have ever met in my life. Time to replace His Holiness the Dalai Lama :)
14. Aileen for numerous visa support letters and prompt help in all paperwork. Her high efficiency is known to all.
15. Shane for assisting in everything concerning logistics. He has always been extra quick to help me.
16. Martin for installing various packages on the workstation and quickly resolving whenever I had any computing problem.

-
17. Alison for the swift and efficient processing of all my travel claims.
 18. Justyna for helping to keep our offices neat and tidy.
 19. Terry for interesting discussions about various things related to astronomy and public outreach.
 20. Miruna for being such a generous and kind host on numerous occasions. It is a well known fact in student circles that none can beat her in cooking and hospitality skills.
 21. Gotz and Ding for all the jovial conversations inside and outside the observatory.
 22. Alexey for letting me into that special list with whom he does not mind talking to :)
 23. Maria for her super kind comments and wishes after viva.
 24. quick witted Geert for motivating me to join the International Meteor Organization and the International Meteor Conference. Almost time for him to receive an OBE for his spontaneous jokes :)
 25. ever cheerful Toby for all his sincere help before and after my arrival in Armagh. I wonder whether there is anyone as kind and organised as him when it comes to helping others.
 26. Tom for the funny debates on cricket. I gather he is a celebrity in CA these days :)
 27. Naslim for being such a special and helpful friend.
 28. Shenghua for being my saviour in sharing meteor logging work. He was declared the official work genie of the observatory :)
 29. Joachim for all the fun and frolic at his house parties, pubs, cinema, theatre, concerts, road trips, ASGI etc .
 30. Kamalam for all the help and support during my admission+visa formalities and while settling here.
 31. Zhenghua for excellent games of badminton. Time for him to represent the Chinese team :)
 32. Xianfei for lovely chinese food during parties.
 33. Blagovest for being such an understanding and good hearted housemate. All residents at 85 RWS have always made chaos in the solar system a reality :)
 34. Tugca & Onur for being generous hosts for many movie and BBQ evenings. It was simply awesome to discuss about various movies and books with you.
 35. Adam for the lovely road trips and a memorable ASGI at Birr Castle. Its been real fun to discuss a lot of particle physics.
 36. Chris & Helen for putting up with my numerous whimsical conversations on science, arts and society when some of us were delightfully high :) One of the perfect couples I have ever met in my life.
 37. Aaron for being a wonderful office mate. This poor chap must have been bored with my archaic and utopian ideas by now :)
 38. Libby for being another jolly good office mate. Always a delight to converse with ever cheerful people like her.
 39. Ruxy for interesting debates on religion.
 40. Venu & Alex for their friendship.
 41. Juie, Will and Yanina for their lovely thoughtful gift after my viva. A personalised bottle in my name from Bushmills distillery is a rare honour :)
 42. Emma-Jane for organising the interesting workshops on some key government policies. Good to be apprised of latest rules.
 43. my summer student Ben for tolerating my rants about the great Halley as well as

comet Halley for one whole month :). Poor chap! Hope he remembers me when he becomes a great physicist in future.

44. International Student Support Office (especially Elaine) at QUB for all their timely help and advice regarding various paperwork concerning FCO, UKBA and Home Office.

45. Planetarium staff for always being kind to waive my ticket fees without me requesting at all.

46. Numerous interesting visitors like Colin, Eamon, Tony, Aurelie, Jonathan, Takuya, Dicle, Rebecca, James, Clara, Aurelien, Amy etc for fun evenings.

47. Incredibly large list (\sim several 10^2) of my friends and family members who sent me kind messages after the successful thesis defence. I was overwhelmed to put it mildly!

48. All the conference/meeting organisers and various embassies during 2010-2014 for all the travel, fun and learning.

Thanks^{n!} to all my previous supervisors Dr S B Gudennavar (during M.Phil), Prof G I Menon (during IAS summer project), Dr R L Hota (during M.Sc), Dr K C Ajithprasad (during B.Sc).

Sadly nothing can be done in today's world without money. I express my special thanks to the Department of Culture, Arts & Leisure of Northern Ireland for the generous funding to pursue my research work.

Only a pleasant childhood can lead to a happy life thereafter. As always I express my love and respect for my dad, mom, my beloved grandparents and some selected relatives who have been real angels to me whenever I was in happiness or sorrow.

Last but not the least, these are the two fine minds who inspired me into science: **Krishna Warriar** (an epitome of brilliance and innocence) and **Sashi Warriar** (an incarnation of knowledge and wit). Life would not have been this way for me without both of you. **Hence this thesis is fondly dedicated to my beloved Babumaman and Sashi uncle.**

Aswin Sekhar
Space-time coordinates - (Armagh, 2014 Apr 28)

Abstract

The overall objective of the thesis is to understand the long term orbital dynamics of comets and meteoroid streams. The initial idea focused mainly on detailed analysis of Jovian resonances in Orionids and Leonids. Special emphasis was given to study their influence in causing meteor outbursts and storms on Earth. The theoretical simulations matched with observational records to a very good degree. This work led to the curious question as to whether any resonance mechanism could be driven due to Saturn's gravity. Subsequent analysis showed that Saturn's influences can also become vital when the order of resonance (concerning Saturn) is smaller than that in the adjacent Jovian resonances. Compact resonant structures (due to Saturn's effects) were identified in both Orionid and Leonid streams during present times. All these calculations were done solely using a Newtonian model. This raised more questions as to whether Einstein's general relativistic effects could have any substantial role during long term (of the order of thousand years) meteor shower forecasts. Analytical and numerical analysis showed that general relativistic effects could lead to significant errors (in long term forecasts) in some particular combinations (or different epochs) of Keplerian orbital elements in certain low perihelion distance (below 0.15 AU) and low semi-major axis (below 1.5 AU) meteoroid streams. Because some low perihelion distance meteoroid streams are associated with sungrazing comets, this led to the next question regarding the reason for the absence of meteor showers from this class of comets. A detailed study using Lagrange's planetary equations showed that most sungrazers cannot make the nodes of meteoroid particles Earth intersecting at low ejection velocities (of order 10 m/s). This can be used as a convincing argument to establish the absence of spectacular meteor showers on Earth from the frequently observed sungrazers so far.

Contents

Declaration	i
Acknowledgements	i
Abstract	iv
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xvi
Publications	xvii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Mean Motion Resonances	1
1.1.1 Geometry of Resonance	1
1.1.2 D’Alembert Rules	5
1.1.3 Comparison with Simple Pendulum	7
1.1.4 Examples of Resonances in Solar System	8
1.2 The Great Inequality	10
1.2.1 Evolution of Relevant Literature	10
1.3 Newtonian and Einsteinian Models of Gravitation	12
1.3.1 Newton’s Theory	12
1.3.2 Post-Newtonian/Einstein’s Theory	16

1.4	Lagrange's Planetary Equations	19
1.4.1	Basic Technique	19
1.4.2	Resolving the Velocity Components	22
2	Jovian Resonances	31
2.1	Overview	31
2.1.1	1P/Halley and Orionids	32
2.1.2	55P/Tempel-Tuttle and Leonids	38
2.2	Resonant Motion	41
2.2.1	Comet 1P/Halley	43
2.2.2	Comet 55P/Tempel-Tuttle	44
2.3	Resonant Structures	45
2.3.1	Orionid Stream	48
2.3.1.1	Orbital Element Maps	48
2.3.1.2	Specific Calculations	52
2.3.2	Leonid Stream	58
2.3.2.1	Orbital Element Maps	58
2.3.2.2	Specific Calculations	60
2.4	Orbital Evolution in the Past	62
2.4.1	1P/Halley	63
2.4.2	55P/Tempel-Tuttle	64
2.5	Summary and Discussion	65
3	Saturnian Resonances	78
3.1	Overview	78
3.2	Separation of Jovian and Saturnian Resonances	83
3.3	Geometry of Resonant Zones	86
3.3.1	Orionids	86

3.3.2	Leonids	88
3.4	Ecliptic Plane Crossings and Orbital Distribution	90
3.4.1	Orionids	90
3.4.2	Leonids	91
3.5	Earth Intersection Possibilities	93
3.6	Summary and Discussion	93
4	General Relativistic Effects	103
4.1	Overview	103
4.2	Drift in argument of pericentre due to GR and its subsequent effect on nodal distances	107
4.3	Conditions for maximum relativistic precession in pericentre	110
4.3.1	Analytical treatment	110
4.3.2	Numerical treatment	112
4.4	Values of argument of pericentre for maximum change in nodal distances	114
4.4.1	Numerical treatment	114
4.4.2	Analytical treatment	115
4.5	Summary and Discussion	117
5	Sungrazers	123
5.1	Overview	123
5.2	Effect of ejection velocity on meteoroids' nodal distances	127
5.2.1	Conditions to favour meteor phenomena on Earth	127
5.2.2	Separating the effects due to three components of ejection velocity	129
5.3	C/2012 S1 (ISON) and C/1680 V1 (Newton's comet)	132
5.4	Marsden family versus other sungrazing families	137
5.5	Nodal Dispersion in 1P/Halley and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle	142
5.6	Summary and Discussion	144

6 Conclusion and Future Work	155
6.1 Conclusion	155
6.2 Future Work	158
6.2.1 Extension of Jovian Resonances Work	158
6.2.2 Extension of Saturnian Resonances Work	159
6.2.3 Extension of General Relativistic Precession Work	159
6.2.4 Extension of Sungrazing Orbits Work	160
6.2.5 Kozai Resonance and Meteoroid Stream Dynamics	160
6.2.6 Ancient Meteor Records	161
Bibliography	163
Appendices	171
A Useful Stuff	172
A.1 Notations	172
A.2 Acronyms	174
A.3 Physical Constants	175

List of Tables

1.1	Notations and conventions used for different resonances discussed in chapters 2 and 3. Here J and S stands for Jovian and Saturnian resonances respectively.	5
2.1	Data of resonant dust trails which caused/can cause various Orionid outbursts (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014b)	55
2.2	Data of dust trails which caused Leonid outbursts.	62
3.1	Order of resonances discussed in this work and applying combinatorics to calculate resonant arguments permitted by D'Alembert rules (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2013). T is the approximate number of successive years for the Earth to encounter a single Leonid/Orionid resonant zone. P is the interval until the next series of successive encounters. In previous work (Sekhar & Asher 2014b) on Orionids, $T \sim 5-6$ yr & $P \sim 71$ yr for 1:6 Jovian, and $T \sim 1-2$ yr & $P \sim 77$ yr for 2:13 Jovian.	85
4.1	$\Delta\omega$ and Δr due to general relativistic effects for different parent bodies and meteoroid streams in 1000 years. Ascending nodes for Orionids and Halley. Descending nodes for Geminids, Phaethon, Leonids and Tempel-Tuttle (taken from Sekhar 2013).	108
4.2	$\Delta\omega$ and Δr for different low q (≤ 0.15 AU) and low a (≤ 1.5 AU) meteoroid streams (taken from the list of established meteor showers in IAU-MDC) due to general relativistic precession in 1000 years (taken from Sekhar 2013).	109

5.1	Orbital elements taken from JPL Horizons, IAU Minor Planet Center, and computed nodal distances, for a few well known sungrazers (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).	133
5.2	Maximum nodal displacement of meteoroids due to individual components of ejection velocity (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).	134
5.3	Distribution of sungrazing families from Catalogue of Cometary Orbits 2008 (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).	138
5.4	Orbital elements (from JPL Horizons) and computed nodal distances during present times for Halley and Tempel-Tuttle	143

List of Figures

1.1	Schematic of low $e(\sim 0.1)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 1:6 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 1:3 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.	25
1.2	Schematic of high $e(\sim 0.96)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 1:6 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 1:3 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.	25
1.3	Schematic of low $e(\sim 0.1)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 4:11 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 8:9 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.	26
1.4	Schematic of high $e(\sim 0.9)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 4:11 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 8:9 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.	26
1.5	Relative positions leading to stable configuration for interior high $e \sim 0.9$ resonance (2:1 Jovian). Conjunctions occur at pericentre here. If P_J is Jovian orbital period. (a) $t=0$, (b) $t=(1/4)P_J$, (c) $t=(1/2)P_J$, (d) $t=(3/4)P_J$, (e) $t=P_J$. Here Jupiter's orbit is in green and 2:1 resonant orbit in red.	27
1.6	Relative positions leading to unstable configuration for interior high $e \sim 0.9$ resonance (2:1 Jovian). Conjunctions occur at apocentre here. If P_J is Jovian orbital period. (a) $t=0$, (b) $t=(1/4)P_J$, (c) $t=(1/2)P_J$, (d) $t=(3/4)P_J$, (e) $t=P_J$. Here Jupiter's orbit is in green and 2:1 resonant orbit in red.	28

1.7	Schematic for the system where mass m_1 orbits around central mass M and gets perturbed by mass m_2 . Respective position vectors and X, Y, Z directions are shown.	29
1.8	Schematic showing the radial S (red), transverse T (blue) and normal W (black) components of ejection velocities at two different positions in the orbits around the sun. Normal component is outward from the plane of paper.	30
2.1	Evolution of 1:6 resonant argument of 1P/Halley over 6000 years from 2404 B.C.	68
2.2	Evolution of 2:13 resonant argument of 1P/Halley over 6000 years from 2404 B.C.	68
2.3	Evolution of 5:14 resonant argument of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle over 6000 years from 1366 A.D.	69
2.4	Evolution of 4:11 resonant argument of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle over 6000 years from 1366 A.D.	69
2.5	(a, M) space for 1:6 resonance in Orionids showing regions where particles undergo resonant librations, as a function of initial semi-major axis and mean anomaly at the initial epoch JD 1208880.5.	70
2.6	(a, M) space for 2:13 resonance in Orionids; initial epoch JD 1633920.5	70
2.7	Ascending Nodal Distance in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.	71
2.8	Solar Longitude of Node in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910.	71
2.9	Difference in Nodal Passage Times in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910. The difference is computed by subtracting the time of particle's arrival at the node and the time of observed outburst.	72
2.10	Ascending Nodal Distance in 2007 vs Initial Orbital Period of Meteoroids in -910. For comparison, comet Halley's $r_a \sim 1.8$ AU in the 1986 return. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.	72
2.11	(a, M) space for 5:14 resonance in Leonids; initial epoch JD 2220280.5	73
2.12	(a, M) space for 4:11 resonance in Leonids; initial epoch JD 2220280.5	73

2.13	Descending Nodal Distance in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.	74
2.14	Solar Longitude of Node in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366.	74
2.15	Difference in Nodal Passage Times in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366. The difference is computed by subtracting the time of particle's arrival at the node and the time of observed outburst. . . .	75
2.16	Descending Nodal Distance in 1998 vs Initial Orbital Period of Meteoroids in 1366. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.	75
2.17	Evolution of 1P/Halley's semi-major axis in an integration going back in time from 240 B.C.; close encounter with Jupiter at 0.05 AU leads to sudden change in orbit at about 12 kyr in past.	76
2.18	Heliocentric distance of descending node of 1P/Halley in an integration going back in time from 240 B.C. (same integration as figure 2.17). . . .	76
2.19	Evolution of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle's semi-major axis in an integration going back in time from 1366 A.D.; close encounter with Jupiter at 0.3 AU leads to change in orbit at about 3.5 kyr in past.	77
2.20	Heliocentric distance of ascending node of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle in an integration going back in time from 1366 A.D. (same integration as figure 2.19).	77
3.1	(a) Libration of 1:3 (Saturnian) resonant argument for an Orionid test particle, confirming presence of 1:3 MMR with Saturn. (b) Circulation of 2:15 (Jovian) resonant argument for the same particle, confirming absence of 2:15 MMR with Jupiter.	95
3.2	(a) Libration of 8:9 (Saturnian) resonant argument for a Leonid test particle, confirming presence of 8:9 MMR with Saturn. Circulation of (b) 16:45 (Jovian) and (c) 5:14 (Jovian) resonant arguments for the same particle confirm absence of 16:45 and 5:14 MMR with Jupiter.	96
3.3	three resonant zones (integrated for 4 kyr) for 1:3 Saturnian MMR in Orionids as a function of a and M at initial epoch JD 1208900.18109; 1404 B.C. Oct 15 return	97

3.4	three resonant zones (integrated for 4 kyr) for 1:3 Saturnian MMR in Orionids as a function of a and M at initial epoch JD 2446470.5.; 1986 Feb 9 return	97
3.5	nine zones (integrated for 1 kyr) for 8:9 Saturnian MMR in Leonids as a function of (a,M) at initial epoch JD 2220280.1685; 1366 Oct 19 return	98
3.6	nine zones (integrated for 1 kyr) for 8:9 Saturnian MMR in Leonids as a function of (a,M) at initial epoch JD 2451040.5; 1998 Aug 14 return .	98
3.7	Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 450 A.D.; particles ejected in 1404 B.C. return . . .	99
3.8	Distribution of heliocentric distances, for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 450 A.D.; particles ejected in 1404 B.C. return	99
3.9	Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 750 A.D.; particles ejected in 1266 B.C. return . . .	100
3.10	Distribution of heliocentric distances, for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 750 A.D.; particles ejected in 1266 B.C. return	100
3.11	Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 2000 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1366 A.D. return time frame.	101
3.12	Distribution of heliocentric distances for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 2000 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1366 A.D. return time frame. . .	101
3.13	Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 1998 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1333 A.D. return time frame.	102
3.14	Distribution of heliocentric distances for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 1998 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1333 A.D. return time frame. . .	102
4.1	Extreme values of $F(a,q)$ plotted for different values in a for Northern Daytime ω Cetids like ($q=0.108$ AU) orbit. The region to the left of $a = 0.108$ AU (separated by vertical dotted line) shows the unreal part. To the right of that region is the feasible and stable part of the function.	119

4.2	Extreme values of $F(a, q)$ plotted for different values in q for Northern Daytime ω Cetids like ($a=0.967$ AU) orbit. The region to the right of $q = 0.967$ AU (separated by vertical dotted line on the right) is the unreal part. The region to the left of that separation is real (except when q is smaller than the radius of the sun shown by the vertical dotted line on the left). The region between two dotted lines corresponds to feasible part in the solar system.	119
4.3	Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Daytime Arietids for different values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=4.0 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr	120
4.4	Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Northern Daytime ω Cetids for various values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr	120
4.5	Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Geminids for all values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=2.3 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr	121
4.6	Change in heliocentric distance of ascending node in Orionids for various values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=1.2 \times 10^{-4}$ degrees/kyr	121
4.7	Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Leonids for all possible values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=1.7 \times 10^{-4}$ degrees/kyr	122
5.1	Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for an ISON like ($q \sim 0.012$ AU, $e \sim 1$) orbit . .	146
5.2	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For C/2012 S1 ISON when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	147
5.3	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For Marsden family comets when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	148
5.4	Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for a Halley like ($q \sim 0.58$ AU, $e \sim 0.968$) orbit	149
5.5	Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for a Tempel-Tuttle like ($q \sim 0.98$ AU, $e \sim 0.906$) orbit	150

5.6	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on ascending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 1P/Halley when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	151
5.7	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 1P/Halley when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	152
5.8	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on ascending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 55P/Tempel-Tuttle when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	153
5.9	Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 55P/Tempel-Tuttle when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1}	154

Publications

A list of publications and talks resulting from the work presented in this thesis is given below:

Refereed Publications

1. Sekhar A. & Asher D. J. 2014, *Resonant Behavior of Comet Halley and the Orionid Stream*, Meteoritics and Planetary Science, 49, 52.
2. Sekhar A. & Asher D. J. 2014, *Meteor Showers on Earth from Sungrazing Comets*, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters, 437, L71 .
3. Sekhar A. 2013, *General Relativistic Precession in Meteoroid Orbits*, WGN, Journal of the International Meteor Organization, 41, 179.
4. Sekhar A. & Asher D. J. 2013, *Saturnian Mean Motion Resonances in Meteoroid Streams*, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters, 433, L84.

Non-refereed Publications

1. Sekhar A. 2014, *Effects of General Relativity on Meteoroid Orbits*, In: Proceedings of the International Meteor Conference, Poznan, Poland, 22-25 Aug 2013, Eds. Gyssens M., Roggemans P., International Meteor Organization, in press.
2. Sekhar A. 2012, *Evolution of Comet Halley and the Orionid Stream*, In: Proceedings of the International Meteor Conference, Sibiu, Romania, 15-18 Sep 2011, Eds. Gyssens M., Roggemans P., International Meteor Organization, 33-37.

Talks at Conferences

1. Saturnian Mean Motion Resonances in Meteoroid Streams
Meteoroids 2013, Poznan, Poland
2. General Relativistic Effects on Meteoroid Orbits
International Meteor Conference 2013, Poznan, Poland
3. Resonant Behaviour of Comet Halley and the Orionid Stream
European Planetary Science Congress 2012, Madrid, Spain
4. Resonant Behaviour of Comet Halley and the Orionid Stream
Asteroids, Comets, Meteors 2012, Niigata, Japan
5. Long Term Evolution of Halley's Comet and the Orionid Stream
Astronomy Science Group of Ireland Meeting 2012, Birr, Ireland
6. Long Term Evolution of Comet Halley and the Orionid Stream
National Astronomy Meeting 2012, Manchester, England

Chapter 1

Introduction

The main aim is to give a brief background to the theoretical concepts and equations used in the next four chapters. The four subsections in this chapter are directly relevant (on a one-to-one basis) to the next four chapters (concerning our original work). But the four subsections presented here are primarily taken and understood from works of various authors who have contributed to these fields in the past. This chapter is essentially just a review and concise commentary of previous seminal works.

1.1 Mean Motion Resonances

1.1.1 Geometry of Resonance

Understanding the science behind mean motion resonances is an important aspect in solar system dynamics. Almost the whole of chapters 2 and 3 concerns various aspects of resonances and hence it is of particular interest in the context of this thesis. In simple terms, two or more bodies are said to be locked in mean motion resonance if their orbital periods (between themselves) are connected by integer ratios.

Consider the case of two bodies orbiting a central mass. In this case, assume that the

object on the interior orbit has negligible mass compared to other body. Consider that the massive body is moving on a circular orbit in the same plane. Both bodies exhibit resonance such that conjunctions always occur at the same longitudes. If conjunctions always occur either at pericentre or apocentre, then the tangential force experienced by the massless body immediately before conjunction is equal and opposite to the tangential force experienced just after conjunction. Thus the net tangential force is zero.

It is known that angular momentum can change only under the influence of tangential forces. If conjunctions occur exactly at pericentre or apocentre, then there is no change in angular momentum. This symmetry does not hold good if conjunctions occur at any other point on the orbit. In a real case, the conjunctions never occur exactly at pericentre or apocentre. Hence there will always be a small change in semi-major axis. But these effects are periodic and hence the semi-major axis would undergo libration in a symmetric manner.

In the case of interior resonance which is discussed above, frequent conjunctions at pericentre are more favourable (because it can avoid close encounters) for a stable configuration provided they are not associated with conjunction at apocentre. For exterior resonances in which the negligible mass body is on an external eccentric orbit, frequent conjunctions at apocentre are more favourable for a stable configuration provided they are not associated with conjunction at pericentre. Here stable configuration means that the less massive body avoids close encounters with the more massive body. This is the key feature which drives the resonance mechanism efficiently.

There are two kinds of resonances, namely eccentricity type and inclination type resonances. The one we have extensively used in our work is the former type. A very good review is given by Peale (1976).

Peale (1976) discusses the geometry and phenomenon of eccentricity type resonance in detail. Stability in the context of high and low eccentricity orbits in an exterior resonance mechanism is discussed. This is of prime importance because all the resonances

discussed in chapters 2 and 3 are of high eccentricity type. A main characteristic of this resonance is the secular change of eccentricity.

Consider a system of two masses such that $m \gg m'$ in coplanar orbits about a central mass. The inner orbit (Jupiter or Saturn in the cases of chapters 2 and 3) is assumed to be circular. Perturbations from m' which is in a very eccentric orbit (comet or meteoroid particle) are neglected. Such a schematic is shown in Figures 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4. These figures are made to visualise the orbital geometry of resonances in a clear way. The angular orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero in order to map the orbital diagram easily to a 2D picture.

Figure 1.1 and 1.3 shows the case for a low eccentricity ($e \sim 0.1$) model whereas figures 1.2 and 1.4 show the high eccentricity ($e \geq 0.9$) examples.

In figures 1.1 and 1.2, Jupiter's orbit, Saturn's orbit, 1:6 Jovian resonant particle's orbit and 1:3 Saturnian resonant particle's orbit are shown in green, brown, blue and red colours respectively.

In figures 1.3 and 1.4, Jupiter's orbit, Saturn's orbit, 4:11 Jovian resonant particle's orbit and 8:9 Saturnian resonant particle's orbit are shown in green, brown, blue and red colours respectively. These specific resonances are chosen because they are discussed in detail in chapters 2 and 3 (in the context of Orionid and Leonid meteoroid streams).

If the conjunctions occur at exactly pericentre or apocentre, the effects of tangential forces are nullified. Repetitive conjunctions at any other point upset this symmetry. But the conjunctions can librate stably around apocentre and miss close encounters.

In chapters 2 and 3, all the comets and meteoroid streams concerned had high eccentricity. Hence we have not simulated a low e model so far. The diagrams mentioned above are mainly to show the contrast between high e and low e orbits.

As one can see above, the relative positions and the nature of conjunctions are vital in driving or destroying the resonance mechanisms. For a visualisation of these

processes, section 8.2 in Murray & Dermott (1999) gives two excellent (and simple) examples. Figures 1.5 and 1.6 is an example similar to those. As discussed before, frequent conjunctions at pericentre can drive the resonance mechanism effectively in the case of interior resonances.

In both figures 1.5 and 1.6, Jupiter has twice the orbital period of the asteroid. Here the pattern of relative positions is divided into four equal intervals as shown in the figure. For every single orbit of Jupiter, the asteroid undergoes two orbits. In both figures, Jupiter's orbit and the resonant particle's orbit are shown in green and red respectively.

In figure 1.5, at $t=0$, asteroid and Jupiter are at conjunction. At this time, the asteroid is at its pericentre. When the asteroid reaches apocentre, Jupiter is far from apocentre. When Jupiter reaches the longitude of the asteroid's apocentre ($t=P_J/2$), the asteroid has reached back to its pericentre. A significant close encounter only happens when both bodies are at apocentre. Thus it avoids close encounters in this case. At the end of one revolution of Jupiter, the asteroid and Jupiter come back to the initial configuration (i.e. conjunction happening at pericentre). These configurations keep repeating and the asteroid is locked into resonance because of these periodic effects. As mentioned above, in a real case small libration in semi-major axis leads to deviation from the pattern in figure 1.5.

In figure 1.6, at $t=0$, asteroid and Jupiter are at conjunction. But in this case the asteroid is initially at apocentre. After half orbit of Jupiter ($t=P_J/2$), asteroid reaches its pericentre. Then Jupiter is at the opposite side from the asteroid. After the next $1/4$ of a Jovian orbit ($t=3P_J/4$), the asteroid is at its pericentre and Jupiter is far away. But at the next time step, the conjunction occurs at apocentre. This leads to a significant close encounter between asteroid and Jupiter. This will disrupt the whole mechanism and the system will become unstable. Thus the resonance mechanism is not preserved when conjunctions occur at apocentre in the case of this interior resonance.

Although figures 1.5 and 1.6 portray only a very simple case, the underlying logic is

Table 1.1: Notations and conventions used for different resonances discussed in chapters 2 and 3. Here J and S stands for Jovian and Saturnian resonances respectively.

MMR	Order	Nominal Resonance Location
$p:(p+q)$	q	a_n (AU)
1:6 J	5	17.17
2:13 J	11	18.11
5:14 J	9	10.33
4:11 J	7	10.22
1:3 S	2	19.84
8:9 S	1	10.32

the same for any complicated ratios in the context of mean motion resonances. Using exactly the same logic of tracing relative positions of both bodies at various points in the orbit, one could explain the stable and unstable starting points for 1:6 J, 2:13 J, 5:14 J, 4:11 J, 1:3 S and 8:9 S exterior resonances discussed in chapters 2 and 3. J and S stand for Jovian and Saturnian resonances respectively. The numerical results pertaining to these specific resonances are discussed in chapters 2 and 3 later.

1.1.2 *D'Alembert Rules*

The perturbed body is in exact resonance if the time variation of a particular resonant argument is exactly zero. Resonant argument could be visualised as a measure of displacement of the body from the line of ideal conjunctions. One could define the nominal resonance location for an exterior resonance a_n of the $p:(p+q)$ resonance such that q is always positive and signifies the order of the resonance. Repeated conjunctions occur for every p orbits of the exterior particle. a_n and a are the semi-major axis of the exterior and interior body respectively such that $a_n > a$. Here the exterior body is considered massless (or as a test particle).

The work in chapters 2 and 3 deals with only exterior resonances and hence we do not talk about different scenarios of interior resonances here. Throughout those chapters the convention mentioned above is used (look at Table 1.1).

Resonant bodies should satisfy the expression:

$$a_n = \left(\frac{p+q}{p}\right)^{2/3} a \quad (1.1)$$

This provides only an approximate location of the resonance because in real cases there are contributions from the variation in longitude due to orbital precession.

The D'Alembert rules (D'Alembert 1750) is a standard technique in celestial mechanics to differentiate between resonant and non-resonant orbits (page 323, Murray & Dermott 1999). Mathematically the D'Alembert rules is given by equation 1.2. Equations 1.3 and 1.4 should be satisfied for equation 1.2 to be valid.

In the case of the $p:(p+q)$ mean motion resonance

$$\sigma = p\lambda_x - (p+q)\lambda_y + k_1\varpi_x + k_2\varpi_y + k_3\Omega_x + k_4\Omega_y \quad (1.2)$$

where q is the order of resonance, σ and λ denote resonant argument and mean longitude respectively. Subscripts x and y stand for the exterior and interior body respectively. Ω and ϖ are longitude of ascending node and longitude of pericentre respectively.

$$k_1 + k_2 + k_3 + k_4 = q \quad (1.3)$$

$$k_3 + k_4 = 0, 2, 4, \dots \quad (1.4)$$

In simple terms, the resonant argument measures the actual displacement of the body from the ideal conjunction point. If the resonant argument librates, it indicates that the body is in resonance. If the resonant argument circulates, it means that the body is non-resonant. It is a very simple and effective way of distinguishing between resonant and non-resonant behaviour.

From the definition of the D'Alembert rules, it is evident that there can be different

legitimate combinations (shown in Table 3.1 in chapter 3) for the expression of resonant argument depending on the values of p and q .

For any orbit mean longitude is given by:

$$\lambda = \varpi + M \quad (1.5)$$

For prograde orbits:

$$\varpi = \Omega + \omega \quad (1.6)$$

where ω is the argument of pericentre.

For retrograde orbits in the context of resonance, the change in the definition of longitude of pericentre ϖ (Saha & Tremaine 1993; Whipple & Shelus 1993) should be incorporated while computing the resonant arguments:

$$\varpi = \Omega - \omega \quad (1.7)$$

1.1.3 Comparison with Simple Pendulum

Resonances mentioned above can also be compared with the motion of a simple pendulum. The second time derivative of the resonant argument corresponds to a simple pendulum equation. It can be argued that both odd and even order resonances can be compared to the simple pendulum motion.

By drawing parallels with the pendulum model, it is possible to arrive at three different cases, namely: unbounded motion (when resonant argument circulates), bounded motion (when resonant argument librates) and motion on the separatrix depending on the energy of the system. Unbounded motion corresponds to full 360 degree motion of the pendulum bob around the point of suspension. Bounded motion implies forward

and backward motion about the point of suspension. Motion on the separatrix leads to the suspension of bob in the vertical upward position. Hence the comparisons with a simple pendulum help to visualise the nature of the resonant particle with more clarity.

A simple pendulum model and libration widths with derivation is discussed in pages 334-337, Murray & Dermott (1999) in detail. The whole mathematical formalism is beyond the scope of this chapter because only numerical integrations were done to simulate the orbits of our interest in subsequent chapters.

1.1.4 Examples of Resonances in Solar System

In the solar system, there is a large number of approximate commensurabilities in mean motion between various pairs of bodies. They exist in all types of bodies like planets, natural satellites, asteroids, comets, Kuiper Belt Objects, Trans Neptunian objects and meteoroid streams.

In some cases spin-orbit coupling is observed. The obvious example of a spin-orbit resonance is the Moon. It has an orbital period that is equal to the rotational period. This leads to Moon keeping the same face towards the Earth. Most of the major natural satellite orbits exhibit 1:1 synchronous spin-orbit resonance. However in the case of Mercury 3:2 spin-orbit resonance is observed.

The orbits of Jupiter and Saturn are such that they are close to 5:2 resonance (discussed in section 1.2) between orbital periods. The planets Neptune and Pluto are in 3:2 orbit-orbit resonance so that they avoid close approaches during conjunctions.

A very interesting case of triple commensurability lies between the Galilean moons Io, Europa and Ganymede which are in 1:2:4 ratio of orbital periods respectively. This is called Laplace resonance. The Laplace resonant configuration is in such a way that three satellites can never have conjunctions simultaneously.

The Saturnian system shows many interesting resonant configurations. Satellites

Mimas and Tethys are in a 4:2 resonance. Enceladus and Dione are in a 2:1 resonance. Titan and Hyperion are in a 4:3 resonance. Janus and Epimetheus move on horseshoe orbits and periodically change their positions owing to their 1:1 resonance.

In the Uranian system, small satellites Rosalind and Cordelia are close to 5:3 resonance. However there are no resonances in the major satellites of Uranus.

The Neptune system does not show conventional resonances in the case of satellites. But Pluto and Charon are in a synchronous spin state and the system is tidally despun. This resulted in planet and satellite keeping the same face towards each other.

The asteroid belt is a treasure trove of resonance mechanisms. Explaining the gaps in the asteroid belt was a very challenging problem in solar system dynamics for a long time. With a sample of less than 100 asteroids, Kirkwood (1860) was the first person to notice gaps corresponding to different resonances. The cleared regions are mainly 4:1, 3:1, 5:2 and 2:1 Jovian resonances. The Kirkwood gaps are not fully empty. There are a small number of resonant asteroids librating in that space. Furthermore dense concentrations of asteroids are seen at the 3:2 and 1:1 resonance locations. This shows that such orbits are highly stable against Jovian disturbances. There is an interesting recent example of an asteroid getting trapped in 1:1 resonance with Earth on a horseshoe orbit (Christou & Asher 2011).

Comets and meteoroid stream structures falling into resonances is a common phenomenon and it is indeed the primary focus of this thesis. This is discussed at length in chapters 2 and 3.

1.2 The Great Inequality

1.2.1 Evolution of Relevant Literature

The great inequality is a near resonance phenomenon due to the commensurability close to 2:5 between the mean motions of Jupiter and Saturn, in virtue of which the line of conjunctions slowly advances. This leads to the case where the planets return to their original configuration after about 929 years.

I consulted various works for tracking the chronology and development of this very interesting celestial mechanics problem. Most of those works are ancient. It is not easy to get the original prints and some of them are written in different languages and ready made translations are unable to find. But I found reviews of this problem by Lovett (1895) and Musen (1971). I have followed their works step by step to get a picture about the development of ideas in this branch of celestial mechanics. The analytical derivation and numerical values could be found clearly in Lovett (1895) and Musen (1971).

Thus this subsection is my concise understanding of Lovett's and Musen's literature review. The credit goes to them.

The concept of 'Great Inequality' was first noted by Kepler (1625) on comparing the observations of Brahe and Ptolemy. He found that the observed places of Jupiter and Saturn could not be reconciled with known values of their mean motions. The errors in the position of both the planets were found to increase gradually in the same direction.

Halley (1676) postulated that these irregularities were due to the mutual attraction of Jupiter and Saturn. He determined the magnitude of the inequality and found that in 2000 years, acceleration (measured by the discrepancy in degrees) of Jupiter was 3 degrees 49 minutes and the retardation of Saturn was 9 degrees 16 minutes. He calculated the errors using two secular equations, increasing as the square of the time. One was additive to the mean motion of Jupiter and other was subtractive from the

mean motion of Saturn.

By using orbital elements at different epochs, Flamsteed (1685) found that Jupiter was steadily accelerating and Saturn was subsequently retarding. Euler and Lagrange tried to understand this anomalous behaviour which appeared to be inconsistent with Newtonian law of gravitation. In their analysis they neglected terms of perturbations involving cubes and higher powers of eccentricity.

Laplace (1785) found that if one assumes acceleration of Jupiter and retardation of Saturn in the amounts observed, one could explain the difference using terms affected by small divisor in the second power when the critical argument is taken. Later on calculations confirmed this hypothesis. This led to the investigation of the wider problem of long period inequalities arising from the theory of universal gravitation.

The argument $5n_S t - 2n_J t + k_1$ remains the gist of the whole calculation where k_1 is a constant. n_S and n_J stands for mean motions of Saturn and Jupiter respectively. The principal coefficient of the great inequality which affects the mean longitude of Jupiter was determined by various scientists like Delambre, Burckhardt, Laplace, Bouvard, Hansen, Schubert, Pontecoulant, LeVerrier, Hill etc in later years.

The critical argument $5n_S t - 2n_J t$ in the trigonometric expansion of the disturbing function has a periodicity of about 900 years. Such periodic effects in higher approximations produce a substantial effect on the secular disturbing function. The secular perturbations are the source of long period effects with time scales ranging from 5.7×10^4 to 2.0×10^6 years. These perturbations are responsible for the behaviour of the elements of the main planets over millions of years. Mean motion anomalies determine the secular change of longitudes of pericentre and nodes. The amplitudes determine the extent of oscillations in eccentricity and inclination. Such effects are highly important to understand the dynamics of planets as well as other bodies in the solar system.

Later the geometer G. W. Hill proposed that inequalities be expressed in a form which does not involve t in the coefficients. The rigorous analytical derivation is not

shown because it is beyond the scope of my present study. It is a subject of elaborate book length volumes itself.

Modern computing tools help to calculate higher order terms to be included in the secular disturbing function and in the perturbations. Anolik, Krasinsky & Pius (1969) developed the trigonometrical theory of direct secular perturbations including the terms of the fourth order with respect to the eccentricities and inclinations.

Hill (1890) tried to derive these perturbations from the LeVerrier (1872) work of differential analysis for the eccentricities and inclinations. Brouwer & van Woerkom (1950) and Sharaf & Budnikova (1977) incorporated Hill's work to the secular disturbing function in their linear theories of perturbations in major planets.

This section only acts as a brief literature review (taken from Lovett 1895) of this age-old celestial mechanics problem. The application and nuances of the great inequality for the purpose of chapter 3 do not require extensive analytical calculations. Hence such aspects are not discussed here.

1.3 Newtonian and Einsteinian Models of Gravitation

1.3.1 *Newton's Theory*

One of the most significant and ancient theories concerning the understanding of nature was the ideas related to gravitation. One of the oldest interesting experiments pertaining to this was Galileo's test of falling bodies from the leaning tower of Pisa. He concluded that all bodies, irrespective of their mass, reached the ground at the same time if they fall from the same height. This was an important observation and analysis at that time.

Later Kepler (1609, 1619) derived his three laws of planetary motion using empirical data from the observations of Brahe. He deduced that:

1. All planets move in elliptical orbits with the sun at one of the foci.
2. Areal velocity of an orbiting body is a constant i.e. planets sweep out equal areas in equal intervals of time.
3. The square of the orbital period is directly proportional to the cube of the semi-major axis of the orbit.

One cannot define these laws more elegantly and unambiguously than these original translations (from Kepler's works). These three laws were not mathematically derived. It was purely an empirical result from the existing observations.

Later Newton (1687) came up with his classic work on the theory of gravitation. He proved that a simple inverse square law of force gives rise to all motion in the solar system. Newton proposed that the magnitude of force F between any two masses m_1 and m_2 separated by distance r is given by:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2} \quad (1.8)$$

In the legendary work *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*, Newton postulated three laws of motion:

1. Bodies remain in a state of rest or uniform motion in a straight line unless acted upon by an external unbalanced force. This led to the concept of inertia.
2. The rate of change of momentum is the applied force on a body.
3. For every action, there is equal and opposite reaction.

These are almost same as his own words because of their clarity and simplicity.

The two body problem is the simplest integrable problem in solar system dynamics. It deals with the interaction of two point masses moving under a mutual gravitational field described by Newton's laws. In the real solar system, most bodies can be approx-

imated by two body motion (except in cases like 1:1 resonance) consisting of a less massive body moving around a more massive central body. The effects of other bodies can be treated as perturbations to the two body system.

Newton showed that only two types of central force could explain the observed elliptical motion of planets. The first was a linear force directed towards the centre of the ellipse. The second was an inverse square force directed towards one focus of the ellipse. But it was found that only the second kind of force can explain the empirical laws of Kepler.

Here I repeat the well known straightforward derivation using simple notation (along the lines done by various authors since the time of Newton). Consider the motion of two masses m_1 and m_2 with position vectors \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 referred to an origin O fixed in inertial space. The vector $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1$ denotes the relative position of the mass m_2 with respect to m_1 .

The gravitational forces and accelerations can be written (using equation 1.8) as:

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = +G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^3} \mathbf{r} = m_1 \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_1}{dt^2} \quad (1.9)$$

and

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = -G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^3} \mathbf{r} = m_2 \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_2}{dt^2} \quad (1.10)$$

where G is the universal gravitational constant. This is a direct consequence of the nature of the force shown in equation 1.8.

These equations can be rewritten as (because the forces are known to be equal and opposite):

$$m_1 \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_1}{dt^2} + m_2 \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_2}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

which can be integrated once to give:

$$m_1 \frac{d\mathbf{r}_1}{dt} + m_2 \frac{d\mathbf{r}_2}{dt} = \mathbf{A} \quad (1.12)$$

and another integration gives:

$$m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2 = \mathbf{A}t + \mathbf{B} \quad (1.13)$$

where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are constant vectors. These are directly a consequence of using simple calculus.

If

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (1.14)$$

denotes the position vector of the centre of mass of the system (using vector calculus), then the equations can be written as:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{R}}{dt} = \frac{\mathbf{A}}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (1.15)$$

and

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{\mathbf{A}t + \mathbf{B}}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (1.16)$$

This implies that either the centre of mass is stationary or it is moving with a constant velocity in a straight line with respect to the origin O . This is a very general equation and not restricted to just inverse square law forces.

Now considering the motion of m_2 with respect to m_1 in the centre of mass frame,

the simplified equation for relative motion (using straightforward substitutions) can be written as:

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}}{dt^2} + \mu \frac{\mathbf{r}}{r^3} = 0 \quad (1.17)$$

where $\mu = G(m_1 + m_2)$.

This is a very well known approach replicated by various authors for arriving at the basic equations. In this case, I have referred to chapter 2 in Murray & Dermott (1999) whenever I was in doubt. Except some changes in notation used, there is no change in the underlying technique.

Trying to tackle the three body problem is a huge subject area in itself. It has fascinated and frustrated many leading scientists over many centuries. I am not attempting to take up that task either; because there is no simple analytical approach to solve the problem.

The orbital simulations done by me in this thesis only required an efficient numerical integrator. No analytical calculations regarding n -body problem were done from my side. Hence I do not present any fundamental n -body algebra here.

1.3.2 *Post-Newtonian/Einstein's Theory*

In this subsection only a very rudimentary background is provided. Detailed derivation and analysis can be verified in page 194, Weinberg (1972). As a non-specialist in general theory, I have not derived any equation myself. However the final equation is important in our work and is used for calculations of our interest in chapter 4 later.

As per basic general theory formulation, here one can consider a system of particles bound together by their mutual gravitational field. Let M_\odot , r and v be typical values of the masses, separations and velocities of these particles. It is familiar from Newtonian

mechanics that the typical kinetic energy $(1/2)Mv^2$ will be roughly of the same order as the typical potential energy (GM_\odot/r) . Using this principle,

$$v^2 \sim \frac{GM_\odot}{r} \quad (1.18)$$

the post-Newtonian approximation may be described as a method for obtaining the motions to one higher power of the small parameters (GM_\odot/r) and v^2 than given by Newtonian mechanics. Expansion parameter v^2 is used here.

The system of equations of motion of the particles can be expressed as:

$$\frac{d^2x^\mu}{dt^2} + \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu \frac{dx^\nu}{dt} \frac{dx^\lambda}{dt} \quad (1.19)$$

where the usual Einstein's summation notation in tensor calculus is followed. This is a transformation equation for a system of particles in Einstein's theory. The exact equation mentioned above uses the notation from page 212 in Weinberg (1972). Γ , x and t are connection tensor, spatial coordinate and time respectively. λ , ν and μ are indices for transformations as per Einstein's tensor notation.

From the simple transformations and field equations, it is a very arduous and non-trivial task to reach the general relativistic precession derivation I am interested in. I concede that I have not derived this myself or even attempted to learn the intricacies involved in such a challenging derivation in GR from first principles.

One could look up page 194-197 in Weinberg (1972) to get some basic idea although it is not straightforward at all for any non-specialist in GR.

As per Weinberg's derivation it is shown that:

$$\Delta\omega = \left(\frac{6\pi GM_\odot}{L}\right)\left(\frac{2 - \beta + 2\gamma}{3}\right) \quad (1.20)$$

in radians per revolution where L is the semi-latus rectum (commonly used in celestial mechanics) of the elliptical orbit given by:

$$L = a(1 - e^2) \quad (1.21)$$

and according to Einstein's field equations $\beta = \gamma = 1$ (Weinberg 1972). This is again a commonly used concept in general theory.

After simplifying this equation 1.20, the precession in argument of pericentre is given by:

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{6\pi GM_{\odot}}{a(1 - e^2)} \quad (1.22)$$

in radians per revolution.

The positive sign means that precession is always in the direction of the motion of the orbiting body. In practice this precession is cumulative. Hence N orbits would simply mean N times the precession per orbit. This is a very key point which we make use of in chapter 4. The small effect accumulates effectively over long time scales.

Calculation using this equation predicts a precession of 43.03 arc second per century for the planet Mercury. The observations analysed by Clemence (1943) found that the actual value is in excellent agreement with the prediction of general relativity. This was one of the best confirmations of general theory by virtue of its high accuracy.

The other aspects of general theory are not discussed here solely because chapter 4 deals only with the relativistic precession in argument of pericentre in solar system orbits. Other smaller and more complicated effects like Lense-Thirring effects (Iorio 2005) are not included in our work.

1.4 Lagrange's Planetary Equations

These constitute a set of equations computing the small changes in various Keplerian elements due to the perturbations from another body. The fundamental derivation (Lagrange 1811) was first done by Lagrange and hence named in his honour.

1.4.1 Basic Technique

If we consider the case of a body p_1 of mass m_1 , moving around the sun of mass M_\odot and being perturbed by a second body p_2 of mass m_2 , then the equation of motion of body p_1 is:

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}_1}{dt^2} + G(M_\odot + m_1)\frac{\mathbf{r}_1}{r_1^3} = Gm_2\left(\frac{\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1}{\rho^3} - \frac{\mathbf{r}_2}{r_2^3}\right) \quad (1.23)$$

where \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 are the heliocentric radius vectors of bodies p_1 and p_2 respectively.

A simple schematic is shown in figure 1.7.

Here

$$\rho = [(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1)]^{1/2} \quad (1.24)$$

The corresponding equation of motion of body p_2 is:

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}_2}{dt^2} + G(M_\odot + m_2)\frac{\mathbf{r}_2}{r_2^3} = Gm_1\left(\frac{\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2}{\rho^3} - \frac{\mathbf{r}_1}{r_1^3}\right) \quad (1.25)$$

If the right hand sides of equations 1.23 and 1.25 are set to zero as a first approximation, the resulting two body problems can be solved by traditional methods which give the Keplerian elliptical undisturbed orbits.

The basic logic and methodology of arriving at Lagrange's equations is like this. The first step is to find the effect of perturbations from the other body (or from another

physical cause) on the undisturbed orbit. Hence the disturbing function R is introduced for such a purpose. R is basically quantifying the effect of perturbation on the initial orbit.

The second step is to relate this to six different Keplerian elements using the variational technique in classical mechanics. The effect of disturbing function on different Keplerian orbital elements (denoted by α_i where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$) is arrived at. Furthermore those effects are resolved into three different spatial directions. x, y, z denote the three cartesian directions from the origin of coordinate system.

Writing the whole system of equations in terms of the disturbing function R (which is part of standard orbital mechanics) can be done as follows:

$$\sum_{j=1}^6 \frac{\partial(\frac{dx}{dt})}{\partial\alpha_j} \frac{d\alpha_j}{dt} = \frac{\partial R}{\partial x} \quad (1.26)$$

Similar equations can be found for other directions y and z as well.

This is a standard transformation in classical mechanics using the variational technique on a general function in different coordinates which is not just restricted to gravitation. It has various applications in statistical mechanics, nuclear physics, quantum dynamics etc as well.

The six equations are transformed to obtain six first order differential equations giving the rates of change of orbital elements. Detailed algebra is shown in pages 208-211, Roy (2005) and is not explicitly shown here because I have not made any contribution to the whole process myself.

The fundamental equations are (see appendix for notations):

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{2}{na} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \chi} \quad (1.27)$$

$$\frac{de}{dt} = \frac{1}{na^2e} [(1-e^2) \frac{\partial R}{\partial \chi} - \sqrt{(1-e^2)} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \omega}] \quad (1.28)$$

$$\frac{di}{dt} = \frac{1}{na^2\sqrt{(1-e^2)}} [\cot i \frac{\partial R}{\partial \omega} - \operatorname{cosec}(i) \frac{\partial R}{\partial \Omega}] \quad (1.29)$$

$$\frac{d\chi}{dt} = \frac{-(1-e^2)}{na^2e} \frac{\partial R}{\partial e} - \frac{2}{na} \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial a} \right) \quad (1.30)$$

$$\frac{d\omega}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{(1-e^2)}}{na^2e} \frac{\partial R}{\partial e} - \frac{\cot i}{na^2\sqrt{(1-e^2)}} \frac{\partial R}{\partial i} \quad (1.31)$$

$$\frac{d\Omega}{dt} = \frac{1}{na^2\sqrt{(1-e^2)} \sin i} \frac{\partial R}{\partial i} \quad (1.32)$$

where

$$n^2 a^3 = G(M_\odot + m_1) \quad (1.33)$$

and

$$\chi = -n\tau \quad (1.34)$$

The equations 1.27-1.32 are taken from page 211, Roy (2005).

Although these equations were derived by Lagrange for perturbations from another planet, they hold good even when R is due to other causes.

Obviously the analytical form of R will depend on the actual nature of the force at work.

1.4.2 Resolving the Velocity Components

The planetary equations (initially obtained by Lagrange) mentioned above contain the partial derivatives of the disturbing function R with respect to elements. For our calculations in chapter 5, these equations are not usable directly.

Furthermore, this disturbing function can be expanded into a series where it can be expressed in powers of orbital elements. This uses Gauss's method. We follow Roy's derivation to understand this. Thus it leads to differential equations for different orbital elements in terms of mutually perpendicular components of the disturbing acceleration.

The three components are S , T and W (notation used in Roy 2005) where:

S is the radial component directed outwards along the body's heliocentric radius vector from the body.

T is the transverse component in the orbital plane, at right angles to S so that it makes an angle less than 90 degrees with the velocity vector.

W is the normal component, perpendicular to the orbital plane and positive towards the north side of the orbital plane.

These three directions are shown in figure 1.8. for two different positions in orbits around the sun.

The equations can be written as:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{2}{n\sqrt{1-e^2}} \left(Se \sin f + \frac{a(1-e^2)T}{r} \right) \quad (1.35)$$

$$\frac{de}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2}}{na} (S \sin f + T(\cos E + \cos f)) \quad (1.36)$$

$$\frac{di}{dt} = \frac{Wr \cos(\omega + f)}{na^2 \sqrt{1 - e^2} \sin i} \quad (1.37)$$

$$\frac{d\varpi}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{nae} [-S \cos f + T(1 + \frac{r}{a(1 - e^2)}) \sin f] + 2 \frac{d\Omega}{dt} \sin^2(\frac{i}{2}) \quad (1.38)$$

$$\frac{d\Omega}{dt} = \frac{Wr \sin(\omega + f)}{(na^2 \sqrt{1 - e^2} \sin i)} \quad (1.39)$$

Equations 1.35-1.39 are taken from 221, page Roy (2005).

The definition (which is standard in celestial mechanics)

$$\varpi \equiv \Omega + \omega \quad (1.40)$$

implies

$$\frac{d\varpi}{dt} = \frac{d\Omega}{dt} + \frac{d\omega}{dt} \quad (1.41)$$

so that, from 1.38, 1.39 and 1.41 we get:

$$\frac{d\omega}{dt} = [-\cos f \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{nae}] S + [\sin f (1 + \frac{r}{a(1 - e^2)}) \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{nae}] T + [(2 \sin^2(\frac{i}{2}) - 1) (\frac{r \sin(\omega + f)}{na^2 \sqrt{1 - e^2} \sin i})] W \quad (1.42)$$

Equation (1.42) can be shown to be equivalent to the expression on page 57, Murray & Dermott (1999) which is:

$$\frac{d\omega}{dt} = e^{-1} \sqrt{a\mu^{-1}(1 - e^2)} [-S \cos f + T \sin f (\frac{2 + e \cos f}{1 + e \cos f})] - (\frac{d\Omega}{dt}) \cos i \quad (1.43)$$

(where $\mu = GM_{\odot}$), which confirms that our substitutions from the fundamental equa-

tions given by Roy (2005) yield the right result.

Chapter 5 which deals with sungrazing orbits uses these equations for the nodal dispersion analysis. The change in nodal distances due to individual components of velocities in three different directions is discussed in detail there.

Figure 1.1: Schematic of low e (~ 0.1) exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 1:6 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 1:3 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.

Figure 1.2: Schematic of high e (~ 0.96) exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 1:6 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 1:3 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.

Figure 1.3: Schematic of low $e(\sim 0.1)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 4:11 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 8:9 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.

Figure 1.4: Schematic of high $e(\sim 0.9)$ exterior resonances. Orbits of Jupiter (green), Saturn (brown), 4:11 Jovian resonant meteoroid (blue) and 8:9 Saturnian resonant meteoroid (red) are shown. Orbital elements i , ω and Ω are kept zero to show the diagram clearly on 2D space.

Figure 1.5: Relative positions leading to stable configuration for interior high $e \sim 0.9$ resonance (2:1 Jovian). Conjunctions occur at pericentre here. If P_J is Jovian orbital period. (a) $t=0$, (b) $t=(1/4)P_J$, (c) $t=(1/2)P_J$, (d) $t=(3/4)P_J$, (e) $t=P_J$. Here Jupiter's orbit is in green and 2:1 resonant orbit in red.

Figure 1.6: Relative positions leading to unstable configuration for interior high $e \sim 0.9$ resonance (2:1 Jovian). Conjunctions occur at apocentre here. If P_J is Jovian orbital period. (a) $t=0$, (b) $t=(1/4)P_J$, (c) $t=(1/2)P_J$, (d) $t=(3/4)P_J$, (e) $t=P_J$. Here Jupiter's orbit is in green and 2:1 resonant orbit in red.

Figure 1.7: Schematic for the system where mass m_1 orbits around central mass M and gets perturbed by mass m_2 . Respective position vectors and X, Y, Z directions are shown.

Figure 1.8: Schematic showing the radial S (red), transverse T (blue) and normal W (black) components of ejection velocities at two different positions in the orbits around the sun. Normal component is outward from the plane of paper.

Chapter 2

Jovian Resonances

2.1 Overview

Jovian resonances are known to have played an important role in the long term orbital evolution of many active meteoroid streams (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999; Ryabova 2003; Wiegert & Brown 2005; Vaubaillon, Lamy & Jorda 2006; Christou, Vaubaillon & Withers 2008; Soja et al. 2011).

Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko (1999) showed that the Leonid outburst observed in 1998 was due to resonant dust trails ejected from Tempel-Tuttle during its 1333 return. The particles which encountered Earth in 1998 causing enhanced phenomena were in 5:14 Jovian resonance. Detailed analysis of solar longitude, nodal distances and nodal crossing times are presented.

Ryabova (2003) gives an elaborate model for Orionids and Eta Aquariids. The main attempt is to simulate the formation and evolution of the stream. A complicated fine structure of the Orionids and Eta Aquariids stream in terms of layers is studied. The possible role of Jovian resonances in the stream evolution is mentioned.

Wiegert & Brown (2005) study the orbit of the Quadrantids meteoroid stream in detail. Until recently the parent body was not identified for this stream. The sharp

peak of the shower is explained by meteoroid ejections from the body 2003 EH₁ around 1800 A.D. Interesting points related to Kozai circulation and near 2:1 interior Jovian resonance is presented.

Vaubailon, Lamy & Jorda (2006) explore the mechanisms which can lead to the creation of orphan meteoroid streams. They have been widely observed but never been linked to any specific parent body. In parallel, various interesting aspects related to the 2:1 Jovian resonance in the Quadrantids and the 5:14 Jovian resonance in the Leonids are mentioned.

Christou, Vaubailon & Withers (2008) discusses the geometry and dynamics of the Orionid and Eta Aquariid meteoroid stream intersecting Earth, Venus and Mars. The role of Jovian resonances in the Orionids and Eta Aquariids is explored. This work gives a good overview of various feasible possibilities of meteor showers on these three planets at either node. It was found that the descending node from Halley at Mars can show clumpy structures. An interesting 1:7 Jovian resonance can lead to very strong meteor outbursts with ZHR of about a thousand once per century.

Soja et al. (2011) presents a semi-analytical and numerical model for resonances in the Taurid stream. The 7:2 resonant substructures are compared with observations. Furthermore important parameters related to resonances like libration widths and survival times are calculated in detail.

2.1.1 1P/Halley and Orionids

Various ancient civilizations have done meticulous studies in making a detailed observational record (Yeomans & Kiang 1981) of comet 1P/Halley for almost every perihelion passage right from 240 B.C. There are no credible observations relating to this comet before 240 B.C. The oldest credible record comes from the Chinese observations.

Yeomans & Kiang (1981) presents a detailed orbital determination of Halley from

its 1910 return to 1404 B.C. Perturbations from all planets and the different ranges in non-gravitational forces were used for accuracy. Most of the ancient observational records are from Chinese civilisations. Theoretical simulations were correlated with all the ancient observations to a very good degree. The main assumption is that the comet's non-gravitational forces remain unchanged from one apparition to the next one. This is one of the most excellent and reliable works on the past orbit of Halley.

Furthermore, comet Halley has reliably determined (Yeomans & Kiang 1981) perihelion passage times (the first calculations were done by Halley 1705 using Newton 1687) and orbital elements back till 1404 B.C., beyond which the uncertainty in the orbit starts to increase because of a significant close encounter with Earth at a distance of about 0.04 AU. Any orbital data beyond this point will be just probabilistic in nature.

Newton's (1687) work gave rise to most of the present day classical mechanics we know today. It was an elaborate treatise on various aspects of laws of motion, equations of motion, the theory of gravitation and advanced celestial mechanics. A detailed review of his work is beyond the scope and length of this chapter. But the key aspect is that further works related to solar system orbits always used Newton's theory as the primary tool for understanding gravitation and motion of celestial bodies.

Halley (1705) presented the first prediction of the return of a comet in the future by using past observations of the same comet. This required tedious calculations of planetary perturbations in the most rigorous sense. Although Halley did not live to see the comet's return, it was later found that the real observation matched with Halley's prediction very well. Thus that comet was named 'Halley' in honour of his great insight and brilliance. It was the first and only comet to be named after a theoretician. These days almost all comets are named in honour of their discoverers.

Historical confirmations of the annual nature of the Orionid meteor shower date back to as early as Edward Herrick's observations in 1839 (Lindblad & Porubcan 1999) and Alexander Herschel's radiant determination (Denning 1899) in 1864. These were significant landmarks in the history of this shower.

Denning (1899) discusses the meteors coming from the Orion constellation. It was found that some of them were unusually bright. Some efforts were made to collect meteoritic dust after the event. Balloon experiments were planned and performed. It was not successful at that time.

Lindblad & Porubcan (1999) analyses 60 photographic and 17 video orbits of Orionids from the data in IAU-MDC. They are compared with Halley's orbit. The aim is to understand the stream structure and radiant motion. Herrick's ancient observations in 1839 are mentioned. This is probably the oldest observation which identifies the Orionids as an annual shower.

Many ancient records of meteors seen in October from the Chinese, Japanese and Korean civilisations (Imoto & Hasegawa 1958; Zhuang 1977) could also correspond to the Orionid shower.

Imoto & Hasegawa (1958) present a very interesting list of ancient meteor observations from Japanese, Korean and Chinese civilisations. The evolution of solar longitudes of various known showers are compared as well. Many probable candidates for meteor outbursts and storms are presented for Lyrids, Eta Aquariids, Orionids, Leonids and Perseids. Detailed diary descriptions of these observations are given as well.

Zhuang (1977) presents valuable ancient Chinese observations of different meteor showers. The annual nature and periodicity of various meteoroid streams are discussed along with the equivalent date for the equinox of 1900.

Nevertheless the association of the stream with comet Halley and explaining the differences of the Orionid shower compared to the Eta Aquariids (which have the same parent body) has been a very challenging and gruelling task (McIntosh & Hajduk 1983; McIntosh & Jones 1988) which interested many theoreticians for decades.

McIntosh & Hajduk (1983) gives a shell model of the Orionid and Eta Aquariid meteoroid stream. This model predicts the structural features like activity variations, shifts in peak activity and density profiles. Here the shell model is seen to be a narrow

strip which subtends an angle of 25 degrees at the semi-major axis. The effects due to the Kozai mechanism are discussed as well.

McIntosh & Jones (1988) verifies the previously proposed strip or ribbon model of the Orionid and Eta Aquariid stream. Numerical integration of 500 test particles is done. Perturbations from major planets are taken into account. Radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson effects are incorporated into the model. It is seen that the cross section of stream expands in a few thousand years.

Coincidentally it is widely believed that Sir Edmond Halley was the first (by 1688) to suggest that meteors were of cosmic origin (Williams 2011). This was indeed a significant step in the early modern scientific era. Williams (2011) gives a very interesting review of various important ideas and advances of meteor science from a historical point of view.

It is widely accepted that comets like Halley might lose approximately 0.5% of their mass during every perihelion passage (Whipple 1951; Kresak 1987) which would in turn predict Halley's physical lifetime to be a couple of hundred revolutions or ~ 15 kyr. Of course this is never an accurate age and in real nature it would depend a lot on composition, structure and geometry of the nucleus. Whipple (1951) is a classic work which concentrates on different aspects related to the comet-meteoroid orbit connection. A highly relevant calculation related to a comet's physical lifetime is presented in detail. Thorough analysis using some reasonable assumptions shows that on an average comets like Halley or Tempel-Tuttle are expected to last about 200 revolutions. Both of them belong to the category of Halley-type comets (Carusi et al. 1986).

Kresak (1987) discusses the comet ageing problem. It was found that lifetimes of short period comets contain dormant phases during which they remain almost inactive. Such cases were identified for several short period comets by the absence of observations for a long period.

Carusi et al. (1986) presents a new kind of definition for Halley-type comets. Earlier

Jupiter family comets were defined with orbital periods less than 20 years. Halley types were the comets with periods from 20 to 200 years. In Carusi's work, the boundary is dynamically defined by a conserved quantity called the Tisserand parameter with respect to Jupiter (T_J) i.e. T_J is often conserved better than a , e and i . This is a very logical way of looking at the whole problem because Jupiter is basically responsible for these orbits for the way they are as of now. Comets having $T_J < 2$ are considered as Halley types and the comets with $2 < T_J < 3$ are classified under Jupiter family. Most asteroids have $T_J > 3$. However this is not a hard and fast rule. There are exceptions at both ends.

The dynamical lifetime (time scale to remain on any kind of Halley type comet orbit i.e. orbital period from 20 to 200 years) of 1P/Halley is estimated to be of the order of 100,000 years (Hughes 1985; Hajduk 1986; Steel 1987; Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1996). This can be determined with much more certainty (compared to physical lifetimes) because of the reasonably well known orbits of planets in the solar system.

Hughes (1985) presents the problem of transitions between a long period comet to a short period comet. The subsequent evolution of short period comets to meteoroid streams is also discussed. The distributions of semi-major axes, inclinations and perihelion distances of short period comets and meteoroid streams are used for that study.

Hajduk (1986) studies the flux of particles ejected from comet Halley in the mass range of 10^{-9} kg to 10^{-1} kg. This is compared with the flux of dust particles in the mass range from 10^{-20} kg to 10^{-8} kg as measured by space probes. Total mass and effective diameter are estimated.

Steel (1987) makes use of Opik's theory to calculate the stability of Halley under close encounters with planets. The chances for ejection from the solar system due to close approach is estimated for about 1 million apparitions. He argues that a dynamical loss is quite unlikely in this case i.e. the comet is unlikely to have been ejected after one million orbits.

Bailey & Emel'yanenko (1996) showed that Halley exhibits Kozai resonance (Kozai 1979) during its long term evolution. This would essentially mean an exchange between eccentricity and inclination so that the Z component of angular momentum is a conserved quantity.

From the above points related to physical and dynamical lifetimes, it is reasonable to believe (see also Section 2.4.1. below) that Halley has been on an orbit similar to its present one (with perihelion distance $q \leq 1$ AU), and populating the Orionid stream, for couple of tens of kyr.

It is interesting to note that the zenithal hourly rates (ZHR) of Orionids are variable from year to year (Miskotte 1993; Rendtel & Betlem 1993; Rendtel 2007; Trigo-Rodriguez et al. 2007; Arlt et al. 2008; Kero et al. 2011; IMO database). This fact makes this shower particularly interesting in the context of visual observations.

Miskotte (1993) presents the observations of the Orionids for the period of 1993 Oct 16-19. It is seen that Orionids displayed unusually high activity in the night of 1993 Oct 17-18. A relatively large number of bright meteors were observed.

Rendtel & Betlem (1993) discusses the unusually high Orionid activity on 1993 Oct 18. This event was documented very well all across Europe. The peak was observed between 204.7-204.9 degrees in solar longitude. Detailed calculations of ZHR and population index are presented from various observations.

Rendtel (2007) is a work which correlates the theoretical modelling of Orionids with real observations in the year 2006. It was found that 1:6 Jovian resonant Orionid particles were the cause of this strong meteor outburst. Detailed calculations of the ejected epochs and their time of approaching the Earth's orbit are discussed. The simulation agrees with the real observations to a good degree.

Trigo-Rodriguez et al. (2007) presents the observations of 2006 Orionid observations using Spanish Meteor Network data. Heliocentric orbits were obtained for three meteors from two stations during the outburst. The resonant orbits were compared with the

observed meteors. One must be careful to make conclusions from here because of the small sample size.

Arlt et al. (2008) gives the details of observations of the 2007 Orionid outburst. This was one of the strongest Orionid activities observed in recent times. The ZHR was about 80 at solar longitude of 208.45 degrees. The population index was about 2.1-2.2 during the peak of activity. Usually the typical ZHR for Orionids in most years is about 20.

Kero et al. (2011) does an extensive study on Orionid observations in 2009 using radar observations from Japan. Clearly an enhanced activity was seen compared to usual rates. They find that observations are in good agreement with ejection times around the 1266 B.C. return which was identified in our previous theoretical work (Sekhar & Asher 2014b) on the 2006-2010 outburst.

2.1.2 55P/Tempel-Tuttle and Leonids

The annual Leonid meteor shower is one of the best known meteor showers for the spectacular visual display of meteors with some exceptional storms (Brown 1999) where visual meteor rates greater than 1000 per hour were recorded. Observations extend back more than a thousand years to 899 A.D. (Herschel 1866; Katasev & Kulikova 1972; Yeomans 1981; Yeomans, Yau & Weissman 1996). Most of these occurrences happened within a few years of the perihelion passage of the parent comet. The most recent perihelion passage of the comet on 1998 Feb 28 led to enhanced interest by the meteor science community.

Herschel (1866) discusses the appearance of large number of meteors on fixed nights throughout the year. He notes that frequency of meteors changes with time. He was able to correlate certain parts of sky with similar meteors (in terms of orbit) circulating around the sun. This was a remarkable radiant determination at that time. The periodicity of the November meteor shower (present day Leonids) is noted. Observations in

England 33 years earlier were compared. The latest observations at Royal Observatory, Greenwich were well documented at that time. A prediction for 1866 Nov 13 is done as well.

Katasev & Kulikova (1972) uses Monte-Carlo simulations to model the formation process of different meteoroid streams like Draconids, Perseids, Leonids and Taurids. It was found that meteoroid ejection velocities with respect to parent bodies do not exceed 100 m/s. The typical ages of the streams were found using the same method.

Yeomans (1981) analyses the distribution of dust ejected from Tempel-Tuttle by associated Leonid meteor shower data from the 902-1969 period. It was found that radiation pressure and planetary perturbations, rather than ejection processes, dictate the dynamical evolution of Leonids.

Yeomans, Yau & Weissman (1996) computes the orbit of Tempel-Tuttle using the observations from 1699, 1865-1866 and 1965. The comet's orbit was integrated back in time for 2 millennia and an ephemeris was calculated for each perihelion return. Predictions for forthcoming enhanced meteor displays in 1996-1999 are provided.

Brown (1999) gives the historical observations of Leonids from 1799 to 1997. Intensity and times of peak activity are established for 32 Leonid cases during this long time period of observations. It is seen that the strongest observational flux profile obeys a Gaussian distribution. Later works found that a Laplacian profile is more suitable to fit the data. The dust distributions are derived for this comet and predictions are made for 1999-2000 showers.

Many previous works (Brown & Jones 1996; Wu & Williams 1996; Yeomans, Yau & Weissman 1996; Arlt, Molau & Currie 1998; Jenniskens 2006) did extensive calculations predicting a strong outburst in 1998. Astronomers were rather surprised by the strong peak in fireballs more than half a day earlier than expected. There was a dominance of very bright meteors due to the large size of particles (in the range of a few cm). This high activity level lasted for half a day which in turn indicated a narrow concentrated

sub-structure in the stream. This induced interest among theoreticians at that time.

Brown & Jones (1996) do a detailed simulation for evolution of Leonid meteoroid stream using 3 million particles. Ejections at 5 perihelion passages were modelled. Radiation pressure and planetary perturbations were incorporated in the model. Using all the available observations, time of ejections relating to various observed phenomena are constrained. Using this method, predictions are made for future peak activities in the latter years of the 1990s.

Jenniskens (2006) presents results for all the known meteor showers and their parent bodies at that time. Different resonance mechanisms active in various observed streams are also mentioned briefly. Detailed meteor outbursts and storm forecasts are presented in this work. This book acts as a very good reference to look into the details of all the major showers observed so far.

Wu & Williams (1996) obtain the orbits of Tempel-Tuttle for the 1899 and 1932 returns using the observations of 1865 and 1965. This model agrees quite well with the observations of 1899, 1932 and 1966 meteor shower. The same model is used to extrapolate and predict that the showers of 1998 and 1999 would be similar to those of 1899 and 1932. But the level of the 1966 storm cannot be calibrated with this theoretical modelling.

Arlt, Molau & Currie (1998) presents the activity profile and peak activity times for the 1998 Leonid outburst. Previous observations are compared to constrain and improve the existing model of the Leonid stream.

There are accurate observational records of comet 55P/Tempel-Tuttle starting from 1366 A.D. The other observed perihelion returns are 1699, 1866, 1965 and 1998 (Marsden & Williams 2008). The aspect pertaining to the significant differences in physical and dynamical lifetimes explained in the previous sub-section holds good for this comet as well.

2.2 Resonant Motion

As discussed in chapter 1, for any $p:(p+q)$ mean motion resonance

$$\sigma = p\lambda_j - (p + q)\lambda_c + k_1\varpi_c + k_2\varpi_j + k_3\Omega_c + k_4\Omega_j \quad (2.1)$$

where q is the order of resonance, σ and λ denote resonant argument and mean longitude respectively, and subscripts c and j stand for the comet and Jupiter. ϖ is the longitude of pericentre.

Equation 2.1 should satisfy both these conditions:

$$k_1 + k_2 + k_3 + k_4 = q \quad (2.2)$$

$$k_3 + k_4 = 0, 2, 4, \dots \quad (2.3)$$

For a retrograde orbit, the definition of the longitude of pericentre is:

$$\varpi = \Omega - \omega \quad (2.4)$$

where Ω and ω are longitude of ascending node and argument of pericentre respectively.

Saha & Tremaine (1993) studies the long term motion of four retrograde satellites of the Saturnian system. A 2 million year integration is performed on these orbits. In the context of resonances in two of these retrograde satellites, the modified definition of longitude of pericentre discussed above is used.

Whipple & Shelus (1993) presents the numerical integrations for Jupiter's satellite Pasiphae for 50,000 years. Both forward and backward integration is done. It was found that this moon exhibits secular resonance with Jupiter. The key reason for using the modified definition of longitude of pericentre for retrograde orbits is discussed in

detail. In a simplistic way of visualising this, one could see that the pericentre in real space is closer to $\Omega - \omega$. The orbits we consider in chapter 2 and 3 are similar to this example. Thus, this modified definition is employed throughout our work while dealing with resonances.

All the orbit integrations in this chapter and elsewhere in the thesis were done using the MERCURY package (Chambers 1999) incorporating the RADAU algorithm (Everhart 1985), and including the sun and eight planets, whose orbital elements were taken from JPL Horizons (Giorgini et al. 1996). Elements for Halley's comet non-gravitational parameters were taken from Yeomans & Kiang (1981).

Chambers (1999) gives the details regarding the numerical integration package MERCURY. The whole program is written in FORTRAN 77. It has a user friendly format for input and outputs. Orbital data of test particles and massive bodies are fed into a Small.in and Big.in file respectively. The parameters for integrations are given in a 'Param.in' file. Output format is specified in an 'Element.in' file. Different algorithms can be selected depending on the precise accuracy level required and purpose of integration. Apart from the final orbits in respective body files, close encounters can be studied separately in this package.

Everhart (1985) presents the theoretical aspects concerning the well known RADAU algorithm used in numerical integration packages.

Giorgini et al. (1996) is the formal reference for the JPL Horizons ephemeris system which is one of the sources for any solar system orbit. Most of the initial conditions used for numerical simulations and analysis presented in later chapters use this system for obtaining initial orbits.

2.2.1 Comet 1P/Halley

Over the time frame during which 1P/Halley's orbit is reliably known, i.e. since 1404 B.C., our calculations show that the comet was resonant in the past: it was trapped in the 1:6 and 2:13 MMR with Jupiter from 1404 B.C. to 690 B.C. and 240 B.C. to 1700 A.D. respectively.

Integrations were repeated for different values of non-gravitational parameters (Marsden et al. 1973; Marsden & Williams 2008) to ensure that this resonant pattern is not sensitive to small changes in non-gravitational forces.

Marsden et al. (1973) is a work concerning the study of the effects of non-gravitational forces on cometary orbits. The individual changes in transverse, radial and normal components due to outgassing phenomena are presented in detail. The effects of small changes in such accelerations affecting the orbit on long term is a key aspect in solar system dynamics. Many cometary orbits are simulated and the best fit to observations is found by making changes in non-gravitational force parameters.

Marsden & Williams (2008) is the most reliable and well documented cometary catalogue made so far. It has accurate orbital data for periodic comets, sungrazers and non-periodic ones as well. The exact references to original observations or theoretical works to most of these data is presented alongside the elements.

Fig. 2.1 shows the 1:6 resonant argument librating from 1404 B.C. to about 690 B.C., and Fig. 2.2 shows the 2:13 resonant argument librating from 240 B.C. to 1700 A.D.

In order to confirm the librating versus circulating behaviour of the resonant argument during the time frames mentioned above, various combinations of terms to define the resonant argument (Murray & Dermott 1999, Sections 6.7 and 8.2) according to the D'Alembert rules were verified (see section 1.1). This is a crucial test to convincingly argue for the resonance phenomena.

For the 1:6 MMR ($q=5$) there are 28 combinations and each of them was checked, verifying libration for the interval 1404 to 690 B.C. shown in Fig. 2.1. For the 2:13 MMR ($q=11$) there are 182 combinations of which 50 were checked, all of them verifying the result of Fig. 2.2. In Figures 2.1 and 2.2, σ is plotted for the combinations shown in Equation 2.5 (for 1:6 Jovian resonance) and 2.6 (for 2:13 Jovian resonance) respectively.

$$\sigma = \lambda_j - 6\lambda_c + 5\varpi_c + 0\varpi_j + 0\Omega_c + 0\Omega_j \quad (2.5)$$

$$\sigma = 2\lambda_j - 13\lambda_c + 5\varpi_c + 4\varpi_j + 1\Omega_c + 1\Omega_j \quad (2.6)$$

When the comet itself is resonant, it is more likely for the ejected meteoroid particles to be trapped in resonance which in turn would enhance the chances for meteor outbursts in future years. That is an important motivation for looking into the resonant behaviour of the parent body.

2.2.2 Comet 55P/Tempel-Tuttle

Tempel-Tuttle's orbit is retrograde like that of Halley's. Hence the same definition shown in equation 2.4 is applied here. 1366 A.D. is the oldest available accurately observed perihelion return of this comet. The orbital elements were retrieved from JPL Horizons.

The comet's orbit was integrated from 1366 A.D. forward 6,000 years. Fig 2.3 shows that the comet undergoes 5:14 libration ($a_n=10.33$ AU) for about 1,500 years. Fig 2.4 shows that the comet is trapped in the 4:11 resonance ($a_n=10.22$ AU) for about 1,000 years during a later part of its evolution. Both these resonant patterns are not sensitive to changes in non-gravitational parameters. This was confirmed by using different combinations of feasible non-gravitational forces from Marsden & Williams (2008) and

repeating the integrations. Hence one could say that capture into the 4:11 resonance is a common phenomenon in the orbital evolution of Tempel-Tuttle although specific time frames (in the future) cannot be that precise because of random perturbations.

Like in the case of Halley, D'Alembert rules were applied to confirm the librating behaviour.

In Figures 2.3 and 2.4, σ is plotted for the combinations shown in Equation 2.7 (for 5:14 Jovian resonance) and 2.8 (for 4:11 Jovian resonance) respectively.

$$\sigma = 5\lambda_j - 14\lambda_c + 4\varpi_c + 3\varpi_j + 1\Omega_c + 1\Omega_j \quad (2.7)$$

$$\sigma = 4\lambda_j - 11\lambda_c + 3\varpi_c + 2\varpi_j + 1\Omega_c + 1\Omega_j \quad (2.8)$$

As discussed in the previous section on Halley, resonant motion of the comet itself would enhance the probability of more meteoroid particles being trapped in the same resonance. This is particularly of interest because of its influence on future meteor outbursts and storms. That is the primary motivation of looking into the past and future of the parent body.

2.3 Resonant Structures

Here we quote $a = a_n$ as the 'nominal resonance location' (see section 1.1.2) (Murray & Dermott 1999, Section 8.4), which is the value of semi-major axis corresponding to a resonant orbital period assuming the most simple case where $(d\varpi/dt)$ (which quantifies orbital precession) is zero, i.e. as implied by Kepler's third law (Kepler 1609, 1619).

In reality $(d\varpi/dt)$ is never exactly zero, e.g. with the 1:6 resonance (resonant argument as per Equation 2.5):

$$\sigma = \lambda_j - 6\lambda_c + 5\varpi_c \quad (2.9)$$

then

$$\lambda_j - 6(\varpi_c + M_c) + 5\varpi_c = \sigma \quad (2.10)$$

where M denotes the mean anomaly.

Simplifying the expression we get

$$\lambda_j - \varpi_c - 6M_c = \sigma \quad (2.11)$$

If we assume, as a time average, for resonant libration:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

Differentiating Equation 2.11 on both sides with respect to time and using Equation 2.12,

$$\frac{d\lambda_j}{dt} - \frac{d\varpi_c}{dt} - 6\left(\frac{dM_c}{dt}\right) = 0 \quad (2.13)$$

From our numerical integrations we find that $(d\varpi_c/dt)$ is always positive for these resonant particles. If $(d\varpi_c/dt)$ is positive, then we require the rate of change of mean anomaly to be smaller compared to the ‘nominal’ case, which in turn means an increase in the value of semi-major axis.

$$a_{\text{ORI}} = a_n + \Delta a \quad (2.14)$$

Subscript ORI stands for Orionid particle.

A similar analysis can be shown for the Leonids case as well:

$$\sigma = 5\lambda_j - 14\lambda_c + 9\varpi_c \quad (2.15)$$

then

$$5\lambda_j - 14(\varpi_c + M_c) + 9\varpi_c = \sigma \quad (2.16)$$

Simplifying the expression we get

$$5\lambda_j - 5\varpi_c - 14M_c = \sigma \quad (2.17)$$

If we assume, as a time average, for resonant libration:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = 0 \quad (2.18)$$

Differentiating Equation 2.17 on both sides with respect to time and using Equation 2.18,

$$5\frac{d\lambda_j}{dt} - 5\frac{d\varpi_c}{dt} - 14\left(\frac{dM_c}{dt}\right) = 0 \quad (2.19)$$

From our numerical integrations we find that $(d\varpi_c/dt)$ is always positive for these resonant particles. If $(d\varpi_c/dt)$ is positive, then we require the rate of change of mean anomaly to be smaller compared to the ‘nominal’ case, which in turn means an increase in the value of semi-major axis.

$$a_{\text{LEO}} = a_n + \Delta a \quad (2.20)$$

Subscript LEO stands for Leonid particle.

Such an analysis is important to understand the magnitude of disparity between the theoretical (simplified case here) nominal resonance location and the centre of resonant zones from the numerical integrations. Typically in our integrations we see an increase in the value of semi-major axis of the resonant centres by about 1-2 percent.

A much more comprehensive and general description about this subject and its application to meteoroid streams can be found in Emel'yanenko (2001).

Emel'yanenko (2001) calculates the theoretical nominal resonant locations and libration widths for Lyrids, Perseids, Orionids, Eta Aquariids, Leonids, Ursids, Quadrantids and Geminids. This work is very interesting because it gives a comparison of these parameters for different order of resonances. The conditions for stability of such resonances are discussed analytically.

2.3.1 Orionid Stream

2.3.1.1 Orbital Element Maps

One of the main aims of this work is to correlate particular resonant zones to past and present meteor outbursts.

Figures 2.5 and 2.6 show the general schematic of the geometry of resonant zones in the case of 1:6 ($a_n=17.17$ AU) and 2:13 ($a_n=18.11$ AU) resonances respectively.

Integrations were done by taking 7200 particles, varying the initial a_n from 16.5 to 17.9 in steps of 0.014 AU for 1:6 MMR and from 17.6 AU to 18.6 AU in steps of 0.01 AU for 2:13 MMR, and initial M from 0 to 360 degrees in steps of 5 degrees, keeping all other orbital elements (namely e , i , ω and Ω) constant. The values here were chosen such that they would encompass the entire range of resonant zones and at the same time, sufficient number of particles would remain resonant after thousands of years so that one could see a true picture of fine sub-structures over long time scales.

The starting epochs for Fig 2.5 and Fig 2.6 are 1P/Halley's perihelion return times in 1404 B.C. and 240 B.C. respectively. All the particles were integrated for 2,000 years using the RADAU algorithm with accuracy parameter as 10^{-12} . Output data were generated for every 10 years (this step size helps to separate libration and circulation regimes with better resolution).

Resonant particles were identified by employing a simple technique which looks at the overall range of the resonant arguments (for various combinations allowed by D'Alembert rules, see sections 1.1 and 2.2) of all particles during the whole integration time to check when there is no circulation. Checks on ten thousands of representative particles covering many different libration amplitudes confirm that those particles filtered by this algorithm will have librating resonant arguments.

Figures 2.5 and 2.6 give a general picture of these resonances: we can visualize 6 or 13 resonant zones spaced in mean anomaly along the whole orbit, each zone consisting of individual librating particles (cf. Emel'yanenko 1988). These zones, or clouds of resonant particles, are preserved for as long as substantial numbers of particles continue to librate. Further test integrations over a longer time frame showed that for some particular ejection epochs the 1:6 MMR is exceptionally effective in retaining the compact dust trail structures for as long as 50,000 years.

Emel'yanenko (1988) calculates the parameters for the main resonant zones near the orbits of some meteor swarms. A few good examples of possible features of resonances in the observed showers are given. The general idea of the variation of spatial density across the stream is also discussed at some length.

However particles disperse in mean anomaly much faster (in a few thousands of years) in the case of the 2:13 resonance and do not show such high stability. Typically the rule of thumb is that the higher the order of resonance (denoted by q , see equation 2.1), the lower the strength (i.e. its ability to retain particles for multiple revolutions) of the resonance.

A necessary condition for a resonant meteor outburst is that the Earth should encounter one of these clusters of resonant particles, i.e. when the Earth misses these clusters, there is no enhancement (which is the case in most years) in meteor activity, at least due to the MMR mechanism.

Of course there are various other factors like nodal distance, solar longitude, date and time of intersection of the meteoroid with Earth, geocentric velocity etc. which play a key role in confirming the occurrence and characteristics of a meteor outburst or storm (see Section 2.3.1.2). It is possible in reality firstly that many resonant zones would only be partially filled (unlike the uniform pattern shown in Figures 2.5 and 2.6), and secondly that within a given resonant zone there is significant fine structure which could lead to enhanced meteor phenomena if Earth happens to pass exactly through the densest parts.

Similar plots to Figures 2.5 and 2.6 reveal mean anomaly distributions of resonant particles in the long term (a few millennia). The cluster of particles in a single 1:6 resonant zone occupies a much longer part of the orbit (covering 5-6 years) than the equivalent for a 2:13 resonant zone (only 1-2 years). This means that for the 1:6 MMR there can be 5-6 consecutive years of enhanced meteor activity (depending on the exact parts of the resonant stream's fine structure encountered by the Earth), compared to just 1-2 years of outburst possibilities due to the 2:13 Jovian resonance.

The 1:6 resonance is also more effective in trapping considerably larger numbers of particles compared to 2:13. The maximum ZHR in 2007 was about 80 (Arlt et al. 2008) whereas in 1993 it was about 35 (Rendtel & Betlem 1993); cf. normal rates of 20.

Rendtel (2008) presents a review of all the important Orionid observations from 1944-2007. All the visual meteor data during this period were transformed into the standard format of the visual data base at IMO. This data clearly showed that there was an Orionid outburst in 1936 which was similar to 2006 Orionid outburst. Theoretical simulations given later in this chapter can be correlated with both these observations because they were caused by 1:6 Jovian resonant dust trails.

When the comet is resonant, it would remain in a single resonant zone and populate that particular zone. When the comet goes out of resonance, it would keep traversing between zones and thereby populate different resonant zones gradually, implying that meteor outbursts could come from different zones.

Our calculations show that the outbursts during 1436-1440, 1933-1938 and 2006-2010 (Section 2.3.1.2) are from the same 1:6 resonant zone, specifically the same one in which the comet librated from 1404 B.C. to 690 B.C. Also a future meteor outburst in 2070 would occur due to the particles in the same 2:13 resonant zone which caused increased meteor activity in 1916 and 1993. Halley presumably released many meteoroids into the 2:13 resonant zone in which it librated from 240 B.C. to 1700 A.D. but most of these meteoroids do not have the precession rate required for producing Earth-intersecting orbits at the present time. Comparison with resonant zones are an effective way to match observations with theoretical simulations.

The numbers of particles trapped in other resonances close to this range of semi-major axis (16.5 AU to 19 AU) were also checked. For example the percentage of particles in 1:7 ($a_n=19.03$ AU), 3:17 ($a_n=16.53$ AU), 3:19 ($a_n=17.80$ AU) and 3:20 ($a_n=18.42$ AU) resonances with Jupiter are very low compared to the 1:6 ($a_n=17.17$ AU) and 2:13 ($a_n=18.11$ AU).

It should be pointed out that if particle ejection were centred around the resonant value of 1:7 MMR, then there would be substantial amounts of resonant particles which can cause outbursts, but in reality the comet is never near this resonant semi-major axis in the time frames which we consider in this work. Also the ratio of particles trapped in the Saturnian resonances of 2:5 ($a_n=17.56$ AU), 3:8 ($a_n=18.34$ AU), 5:12 ($a_n=17.09$ AU), 5:13 ($a_n=18.03$ AU), 7:17 ($a_n=17.23$ AU), 7:18 ($a_n=17.90$ AU) and 8:19 ($a_n=16.97$ AU) are extremely small owing to the overpowering effect of Jupiter's gravity. But the 1:3 Saturnian resonance was later found to be very strong and active in Orionids (see chapter 3).

Hence significant measurable enhancements in meteor activity can be ruled out

from these obscure Jovian and Saturnian resonances. Even if such resonant particles encounter Earth it will be almost impossible to distinguish them because of the lack of any sizeable increase in ZHR in any year. Hence it should be understood that just the mere fact of having some resonant particles intersecting Earth does not mean an increase from normal meteor rates. It depends on how effective that resonance mechanism is in trapping very large numbers of ejected particles and subsequently avoiding close encounters with other planets.

2.3.1.2 Specific Calculations

Past observations (Millman 1936, Imoto & Hasegawa 1958, Rendtel & Betlem 1993, Dubietis 2003, Rendtel 2007, Trigo-Rodriguez et al. 2007, Arlt et al. 2008, Spurny & Shrbeny 2008, Kero et al. 2011) of Orionids have shown enhanced meteor activity in some particular years. Previous works (Rendtel 2007; Sato & Watanabe 2007) have highlighted the significance of 1:6 MMR in explaining the outburst in 2006. According to Sato & Watanabe (2007), the meteor outburst in 2006 was caused by 1:6 resonant particles ejected from the comet in -1265 (1266 B.C.), -1197 (1198 B.C.) and -910 (911 B.C.). All these ejection years can be directly linked to the time frame in which the comet itself was 1:6 resonant (Section 2.2.1). Hence more meteoroids became trapped in this resonance during this time frame compared to other years when the comet was not resonant.

Millman (1936) finds that there was a high number of bright Orionids in the year 1936. Some of them had very long trajectories in the atmosphere. Some comparisons with observations in previous years is presented.

Dubietis (2003) calculates typical population index and activity profiles for Orionids from the observations in the visual meteor database. He finds that ZHRs are normally in the range of 15-20 for Orionids and 40-80 for Eta Aquariids. This work looks into the stream structure and geometry. It was found that a filamentary structure can explain the features and a 12 year periodicity (due to possible MMRs with Jupiter) can be seen

in different parts of the stream.

Sato & Watanabe (2007) presents calculations concerning the observed Orionid outburst in 2006. They find that 1:6 Jovian resonant particles ejected about 3000 years in the past can explain the observed enhanced activity seen in 2006. Furthermore they predicted that similar levels of outbursts would be observed for 3-4 years after 2006. Our calculations agree with this work to a good degree.

Spurny & Shrbeny (2008) report exceptionally high fireball activity in Orionids in 2006. They find that it was higher than the total number of such bright fireballs recorded during about five decades of continuous operation of the Czech part of European fireball network. It is proposed that filaments of larger meteoroids were trapped in 1:5 Jovian resonance.

In order to investigate the orbital evolution, ejection epochs were set between 1404 B.C. and 1986 A.D. All the ejections were done by keeping the perihelion distance and other elements as constant and by varying the semi-major axis and eccentricity. In this simple model, ejection was done at perihelion ($M=0$) in the tangential direction. Ejection velocities were set in the range -50 to +50 m/s, i.e. both behind and ahead of the comet, meaning that over all epochs collectively the initial orbital periods range from 60 to 88 years, encompassing all possible 1:6 and 2:13 resonant particles, positive ejection velocity corresponding to larger periods.

Radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson effects were not incorporated in these calculations. Because they span a range of orbital periods, test particles ejected tangentially at perihelion and moving only under gravitational perturbations are able, over the time frames we consider here, to represent the motion of all meteoroids released over the comet's perihelion arc with different velocities and subject to different amounts of radiation pressure (Kondrat'eva & Reznikov 1985; Asher & Emel'yanenko 2002).

Kondrat'eva & Reznikov (1985) simulate Leonid showers in 1833, 1966 and 2001 using the parent body's orbital elements. This work presents a way of calculating the

effects of radiation pressure on velocity dispersion. The increase in semi-major axis and orbital period due to solar radiation pressure is modelled.

In order to confirm the correlation between theory and observations, it is vital to match the time (second half of October) when the Orionid meteoroids reach their ascending node, solar longitude λ_{\odot} (approx. 204-210 degrees) at the node and heliocentric distance of ascending node (by analyzing the difference Δr between heliocentric distances of Earth and ascending node of meteoroid; Earth diameter is about 0.0001 AU). These essential parameters from our simulations (Table 2.1) can be matched with real observations (listed in past meteor records).

Each entry in Table 2.1 is a carefully chosen meteoroid which has the average value (in initial semi-major axis) out of many candidate particles covering the small range of orbital periods that favours an outburst in the given year. For example, Figures 2.7, 2.8 and 2.9 are plots of heliocentric distance of ascending node, solar longitude and difference in time of nodal crossing of the particles from the time of observed outburst (all three parameters computed at 2007 Oct 22) versus initial semi-major axis of meteoroids (ejected at the -910 return). Heliocentric distance of Earth on 2007 Oct 22 was 0.995 AU. These results show that the conditions for an outburst to occur (from particles ejected in -910) at the observed time in 2007 is satisfied if initial semi-major axis is around 17.22 AU, but the total suitable range in initial semi-major axis and ejection velocities for meteoroids are $17.20 \text{ AU} < a < 17.25 \text{ AU}$ and $-16.53 \text{ m/s} < v < -15.05 \text{ m/s}$ respectively. The plots are similar for other ejection epoch / outburst year pairs as well.

Our simulations indicate meteor outbursts from 1436-1440 A.D. due to 1:6 resonant meteoroids which were ejected around Halley's -1265, -1197, -985, -910 and -836 returns (details in Table 2.1). The initial orbital periods of ejected meteoroids which lead to these five outbursts show that most of them had almost 6 times the Jovian period. There are also historical observational records which show heightened activity, indicating hundreds of bright meteors, in 1436 and 1439 (Imoto & Hasegawa 1958) and

Table 2.1: Data of resonant dust trails which caused/can cause various Orionid outbursts (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014b)

Ejection year	Expected peak time (UT)	λ_{\odot} (J2000.0)	Δr (AU)	Ejection velocity (m/s)	Period at ejection (years)
-1197	1436 Oct 13 01:44	207.551	+0.0012	+13.16	71.76
-985	1436 Oct 14 17:40	208.212	+0.0027	-12.79	71.64
-910	1437 Oct 14 03:00	208.344	-0.0013	-13.60	71.95
-836	1438 Oct 14 13:30	208.522	+0.0010	-22.08	70.12
-1265	1439 Oct 14 23:54	208.698	+0.0021	+11.88	70.67
-985	1439 Oct 15 00:00	208.702	-0.0001	-14.74	71.23
-910	1439 Oct 16 15:03	210.324	-0.0008	-18.07	71.01
-910	1440 Oct 13 19:17	208.258	+0.0037	-20.37	70.54
-985	1916 Oct 17 07:40	204.771	+0.0002	+10.64	77.22
-910	1916 Oct 17 12:57	204.990	+0.0014	+8.79	77.29
-1265	1933 Oct 21 02:24	208.170	+0.0011	+15.69	71.54
-985	1933 Oct 21 02:52	208.190	+0.0086	-12.18	71.77
-1333	1934 Oct 21 12:14	208.321	+0.0044	+9.13	71.82
-985	1934 Oct 21 12:28	208.330	+0.0002	-11.16	71.99
-910	1935 Oct 22 05:16	208.771	+0.0087	-14.35	71.79
-1265	1936 Oct 21 16:19	208.982	-0.0073	+17.35	71.93
-1197	1936 Oct 22 06:28	209.568	+0.0058	+10.77	71.21
-1265	1937 Oct 21 20:24	208.890	+0.0067	+17.27	71.91
-836	1937 Oct 21 23:02	208.998	+0.0022	-13.68	71.85
-1197	1938 Oct 21 21:21	208.675	-0.0091	+7.00	71.37
-1265	1938 Oct 22 02:24	208.883	+0.0001	+14.31	71.22
-1333	1993 Oct 17 22:48	204.662	+0.0039	+31.88	77.70
-985	1993 Oct 18 00:14	204.724	+0.0041	+12.68	77.77
-910	1993 Oct 18 02:26	204.774	-0.0017	+8.98	77.34
-835	1993 Oct 18 02:40	204.782	+0.0088	+10.45	77.64
-1265	2006 Oct 21 02:09	207.452	+0.0005	+11.03	70.48
-910	2006 Oct 23 03:38	209.461	-0.0069	-17.73	71.08
-1333	2007 Oct 21 18:14	207.858	+0.0043	+8.60	71.70
-1265	2007 Oct 22 00:28	208.118	-0.0004	+12.95	70.91
-1197	2007 Oct 22 04:36	208.252	+0.0032	+11.25	71.32
-985	2007 Oct 22 09:21	208.486	+0.0047	-15.22	71.13
-910	2007 Oct 22 10:04	208.513	+0.0002	-15.81	71.48
-836	2007 Oct 23 01:12	209.140	-0.0071	-15.76	71.41
-1333	2008 Oct 23 05:16	210.050	+0.0073	+6.61	71.25
-1265	2008 Oct 20 14:40	207.412	+0.0022	+14.65	71.30
-1197	2008 Oct 21 07:28	208.114	-0.0019	+9.30	70.88
-985	2009 Oct 21 15:07	208.214	+0.0077	-18.72	70.41
-910	2009 Oct 21 19:43	208.367	-0.0008	-17.34	71.16
-836	2010 Oct 21 21:36	208.225	-0.0011	-17.88	70.97
-1333	2010 Oct 21 23:31	208.302	+0.0056	+6.30	71.18
-1265	2010 Oct 22 02:24	208.424	+0.0013	+15.26	71.44
-910	2070 Oct 18 19:12	204.770	-0.0029	+9.24	77.41
-910	2070 Oct 18 19:26	204.779	+0.0003	+9.80	77.56

match our theoretical simulations well. We converted the dates from Julian calendar to proleptic Gregorian calendar in order that all dates in Table 2.1 are referred to a single calendar. No observational records could be traced or identified for 1437, 1438 and 1440 though. Either there were no observations done in those years (unfavourable lunar phase is a possible explanation only in 1438) or the meteor outbursts would have been insignificant in 1437, 1438 and 1440 compared to the ones in 1436 and 1439.

In our simulations we find that resonant meteoroids ejected with positive ejection velocity (higher orbital period) encountered Earth in 1436 and 1439. The ones with negative ejection velocity (smaller period) encountered Earth in 1437, 1438 and 1440. Radiation pressure (not included in our integrations) would always act in the direction which would increase the orbital period of meteoroids, i.e. affects the period in the same sense as positive ejection velocities. In general we expect the peak of the ejection velocity distribution is close to zero and so the largest number of particles, if affected by radiation pressure, is represented by particles having positive ejection velocities in our gravitational integration model. Radiation pressure is having a detrimental effect (with regard to causing meteor outbursts) when we calculate that negative ejection velocities are required to produce a meteor outburst in a particular year. This can explain why we find this trend in ejection velocities for resonant meteoroids reaching Earth in 1436 and 1439 which caused meteor outbursts (agreeing with past observations as shown in Imoto & Hasegawa 1958) and possibly no (or very low) activity in 1437, 1438 and 1440.

We calculate that the meteor outburst in 1993 was due to 2:13 resonant meteoroids ejected around Halley's -1333, -985, -910 and -835 returns. The outburst (Miskotte 1993; Rendtel & Betlem 1993) occurred when solar longitude of node was between 204.7 to 204.9 degrees, a notably different time compared to other known outbursts. Our theoretical calculations match this unusually early peaking on 1993 Oct 18. Our simulations also indicate a meteor outburst in 1916 from the 2:13 resonance and there is a hint of enhanced meteor rates from past observations in 1916 (Olivier 1921) compared to the adjacent years of 1915 and 1917. For the future we predict a similar outburst

(like in 1993 because favorable ejection velocities are similar in both cases) from the 2:13 resonance mechanism in 2070 (see Table 2.1).

The ejection epochs for 1:6 resonant meteoroids which caused continuous enhanced activity in 2007, 2008, 2009 and 2010 (Trigo-Rodriguez et al. 2007; Arlt et al. 2008; Kero et al. 2011; International Meteor Organization database) are also given in Table 2.1. These ejection years correspond to the time when the comet itself was 1:6 resonant. Hence it is obvious that a large number of meteoroids would have been trapped into this resonance during those time frames which would clearly indicate the reason for high ZHR apart from the contribution due to the inherent geometry (see Section 2.3.1.1) of these zones. Our simulations match the observed ranges (207-210 degrees) of solar longitude and outburst times (Trigo-Rodriguez et al. 2007; Arlt et al. 2008; Kero et al. 2011; IMO database) for these outburst years very well.

Even though the uncertainties in semi-major axis (to directly compare with theoretical values in our calculations) of observed meteoroids from these are quite high (which is the typical case for all meteor observations, especially when the semi-major axis itself is high), the matching of outburst time frames and solar longitudes from these papers itself is a very effective way of constraining the orbital evolution of resonant meteoroids from real observations. Our results show that 1:6 resonant meteoroids ejected from the resonant comet also caused enhanced activity from 1933-1938 which match old observational records (Millman 1936; Lovell 1954). Most of these meteoroids had positive ejection velocities which is more favorable for stronger outbursts as discussed before.

Fig. 2.10 clearly shows that meteoroids with initial orbital periods corresponding to 1:6 (around 71 years) and 2:13 (around 77 years) resonances have their ascending nodes near the orbit of the Earth. Hence it can be concluded that resonance mechanisms (specifically 1:6 and 2:13 MMR in this case) aid these particles to come near the Earth at the present epoch while the non-resonant ones precess away from the Earth's orbit. This is typical of other ejection epochs (as shown in Table 2.1) as well.

In figure 2.10, one can clearly see that the number of particles trapped in 1:6 res-

onance is considerably larger than the number trapped in 2:13 resonance. Moreover in Fig. 2.10, we notice that particles having orbital periods of almost $5P_j$ (59.2 years), $6P_j$ (71.1 years) and $7P_j$ (83.0 years) come near the Earth's orbit which agrees with earlier calculations done by Sato & Watanabe (2007).

The typical ZHR for Orionids during non-outburst years is about 20 (Rendtel & Betlem 1993; Rendtel 2008; IMO records). From the recorded previous observations it is seen that the ZHR is about 60 (Rendtel 2007; Kero et al. 2011; IMO records) due to 1:6 MMR during 2006-2010 and about 35 (Rendtel & Betlem 1993) due to 2:13 MMR in 1993.

2.3.2 Leonid Stream

2.3.2.1 Orbital Element Maps

Integrations were done by taking 7200 particles, varying the initial a_n from 10.2 to 10.5 in steps of 0.003 AU for 5:14 MMR and from 10.0 AU to 10.4 AU in steps of 0.004 AU for 4:11 MMR, and initial M from 0 to 360 degrees in steps of 5 degrees, keeping all other orbital elements (namely e , i , ω and Ω) constant.

The actual resonant value differing by a small amount from the nominal resonance location applies in the same way for Leonids as well (as discussed in previous section). Zero precession is just an ideal case and never realistic.

The starting epochs for Fig 2.11 and Fig 2.12 are 55P/Tempel-Tuttle's perihelion return times in 1366 AD. All the particles were integrated for 1,000 years with the MERCURY package using the RADAU algorithm with accuracy parameter set to 10^{-12} . Output data were generated for every 10 years.

Figures 2.11 and 2.12 show the resonant zones for 5:14 ($a_n=10.33$ AU) and 4:11 ($a_n=10.22$ AU) resonances in Leonids respectively. The geometry and explanation is similar to the one given in the previous section except that in this case it is 14 and 11

clouds of particles respectively. If Earth goes through one of these 14 or 11 clumps, a meteor outburst or storm could occur.

Both these plots show the existence of resonant zones at the epoch of Tempel-Tuttle's 1366 A.D. return. It is evident that meteoroids ejected in this perihelion return could feed into one of the zones effectively. For populating the 5:14 zones, the required ejection velocities are in the range of -23 to 8 m/s. For populating the 4:11 resonant zones, the velocities required are -45 to -2 m/s. Both these ranges are very much feasible in nature because it is much lower than the limit imposed by gas drag velocity which is about ± 1 km/s.

The negative ranges shown here would not be favourable for real observations if we take the effect of radiation pressure into account. The small positive range would be the subset most favourable for correlating with real Leonid observations.

All the particles were integrated for 1,000 years. The logic behind the identification of resonant particles is the same as that applied in the case of Orionids. Typically we see the resonant clusters surviving for 1,000 years for both these resonances. Obviously these velocity ranges are specific for the 1366 epoch only.

Another interesting fact is that by looking at the number of zones, one could estimate the probability for Earth passing through one of them. For example in the case of 5:14 Jovian resonance, there are 14 zones spread along 360 degrees whereas in the case of the 1:3 Saturnian resonance (discussed in chapter 3 for Orionids), there are 3 zones spread along the whole 360 degrees. The gaps between zones are evidently higher in the case of 14 zones compared to 3 zones. This means that in such higher order resonances there is more chance for Earth to miss these dense clumps. On the other hand, for low order resonances like 1:3 Saturnian case, there are more chances for Earth to pass through one of the dense clusters.

It should be clarified that the intensity of meteor phenomena would primarily depend on the specific sub-structures inside these resonant zones. But nevertheless it is still

worthwhile to note the differences in probability for missing zones in the case of very high and low order resonances.

2.3.2.2 Specific Calculations

Previous works (Asher 1999; McNaught & Asher 1999; Vaubaillon et al. 2003) have commented on the observations of historically spectacular Leonid storms and accurate correlations with numerical integrations. However they were due to ejected dust trails which were a few revolutions old. There was not enough time for resonant mechanisms to come into play.

Asher (1999) presents the calculations pertaining to Leonid meteor storms in 1833 and 1966. They were widely observed and are considered as one of the most spectacular meteor phenomena observed so far. It was found that during those times the comet Tempel-Tuttle was significantly nearer to Earth compared to as of now. This work correlates the dust trails ejected in 1800 and 1899 returns with 1833 and 1966 storms respectively.

McNaught & Asher (1999) deals with one of the most remarkably accurate meteor storm forecasts in history. The exact orbital evolution of dust trails ejected during different times in the past was analysed. The precise time when these dust trails would encounter Earth in future was calculated. It turned out that in some cases the accuracy was within 10 minutes which was not done before. Radiation pressure was taken into account for all these calculations.

Vaubailon et al. (2003) gives forecasts for the Leonids in 2003. It was found that although no storm is expected, significant activity from old trails of about 14 revolutions old or more would be observable. Specifically the 1499 trail was likely to produce enhanced activity on 2003 Nov 13. Estimated ZHR is about 100.

But the Leonid outburst in 1998 was found (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999) to be due to 5:14 resonant dust trails ejected at the 1333 return of the comet. My

simulations find that a very small subset particles which encountered Earth in 1998 also came from the 1366 return of the comet. Few of them were found to be librating in the 5:14 Jovian resonance. Table 2.2. gives the important parameters concerning the Earth intersecting particles. They are in close agreement with real observations. But it must be clarified that this was only a very small sub-set of particles compared to the 1333 ejected dust trail which was discussed in detail by Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko (1999). Both these ejection time frames can be directly linked to the period when the parent body itself is 5:14 resonant with Jupiter.

The method of ejection and simulation was exactly as mentioned in section 2.3.1.2. Radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson effects were not taken into account. Ejection epoch was the perihelion return of the comet in 1366 A.D.

For comparison between simulations and real observations, it is important to correlate the time when meteoroids reach the descending node, solar longitude at the node and heliocentric distance of descending node. Figures 2.13, 2.14 and 2.15 are plots of heliocentric distance of descending node, solar longitude and difference in nodal crossing times of particles from the observed outburst (all three parameters calculated at 1998 Nov 17) versus initial semi-major axis of meteoroids (ejected at 1366 return). Heliocentric distance of Earth on 1998 Nov 17 was 0.988 AU. These plots show that the conditions for an outburst to occur on this observed date are satisfied if the initial semi-major axis is around 10.305 AU. This is very much inside the libration width of the 5:14 Jovian resonance. Figure 2.16 shows that only the ejected meteoroids with initial orbital period of around 33.02 to 33.26 years (or $a = 10.29$ to 10.34 AU) come near the Earth's orbit in 1998 Nov 17.

Figure 2.16 shows the descending nodal distance in 1998 vs initial orbital period of ejected meteoroids in 1366. It was found that some 5:14 resonant particles ($P \sim 33$ yr) come near the Earth in 1998. However some non-resonant meteoroids were also seen to intersect the Earth. The exact theoretical value conducive for the observed outburst are the meteoroids with initial semi-major axis $a \sim 10.305$ AU.

Table 2.2: Data of dust trails which caused Leonid outbursts.

Ejection year	Expected peak time (UT)	λ_{\odot} (J2000.0)	Δr (AU)	Ejection velocity (m/s)	Period at ejection (years)
1366	1998 Nov 17	234.44	-0.0011	-12.60	33.06
1366	1998 Nov 17	234.21	+0.0017	-12.59	33.11
1366	1998 Nov 17	234.41	-0.0021	-8.29	33.26
1366	1998 Nov 17	234.36	+0.0014	-13.22	33.02
1366	1998 Nov 17	234.53	-0.0017	-9.75	33.19

Table 2.2 shows the orbital properties of particles which can come to Earth intersection in 1998. The required ejection velocities in the negative range are not very favourable because of the effect of radiation pressure (as discussed in the case of Orionids). This would be one of the main reasons why greater numbers of particles from 1333 epoch contributed more than the 1366 epoch for matching real observations.

Table 2.2 does not discuss the meteor storms in 1833 or 1966 or other historical observations because of the fact that they were already identified in detail by previous work (Kondrat'eva & Reznikov 1985; Kondrat'eva, Murav'eva & Reznikov 1997; Asher 1999) and the resonance mechanism is very unlikely in such young dust trails. In this chapter, I am only focusing on the resonance mechanism and not other storms or enhanced activity in general. 1800 and 1899 were the ejection epochs (Asher 1999) which led to the 1833 and 1966 storms respectively. They were indeed very dense dust trails but resonance was not the primary reason for such intense clustering.

2.4 Orbital Evolution in the Past

The motivation for doing backward integrations of 1P/Halley and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle was to understand the possible time frame during which the parent bodies stay in similar orbits to that of present day meteor showers which they produce. Furthermore, it gives a good constraint as to the lifespan of the meteoroid stream and the epoch beyond which ejecting particles would not correspond to the present day showers.

2.4.1 *1P/Halley*

Calculations show that the orbit of Halley was substantially different from the present orbit at about 12,000 years in the past. Fig. 2.17 shows the time evolution of semi-major axis, indicating a drastic change in the semi-major axis near this time frame. A similar sudden change occurred in eccentricity, inclination and longitude of pericentre. Fig. 2.18 plots the time evolution of heliocentric distance of descending node, showing that close encounters with Jupiter are the reason for this drastic variation in the comet's orbit.

100 clones with orbits very similar (varying semi-major axis and eccentricity minutely while keeping the perihelion distance as constant) to the comet were integrated 30,000 years backwards in time from 240 B.C. and this behaviour is typical for about 95% of the clones.

From these orbital integrations it is clear that any meteoroid ejection before 12,000 years in the past would not correspond to the present day Orionid meteor shower. Hence this particular time constraint can be used as a starting epoch for ejection to simulate the present day Orionid stream. It is also interesting to note that this timescale is close to the physical lifetime of the comet itself.

In our test simulations, almost 80% of the clones get trapped into 1:6 and 2:13 resonances for at least a few thousand years between -10,000 and -1403. Hence it is confirmed that the phenomenon of resonance plays a vital role in the long term dynamical evolution of Halley itself which further stresses the motivation in looking into more resonant structures in the present day Orionid stream. This gives good scope for a lot of interesting further work.

2.4.2 *55P/Tempel-Tuttle*

Simulations show that the orbit of Tempel-Tuttle was very much different from the present orbit at about 3,000 years in the past. Fig 2.19 shows the evolution of semi-major axis. One can see the sudden change in semi-major axis near this time frame. Fig 2.20 shows the evolution of ascending nodal distance of the comet. It was found that close encounters with Jupiter were the reason behind this sudden shift in orbit. 100 clones were integrated back in time for 30,000 years from the 1366 A.D. return of the comet. This behaviour where the comet's orbit changes significantly near 3 kyr in the past is typical for 90 percent of the clones.

In order to simulate the present day Leonids, one could consider this time frame as a starting epoch, because any ejection before that point would never correspond to the present day Leonid meteor shower. One could envisage the comet falling into another resonance mechanism in the distant past which all the more proves that resonances play a key role in the past, present and future of such comets.

It is seen (in section 2.4.1) that Halley's orbit drastically changes at about 12 kyr in the past due to a strong close encounter with Jupiter. The past beyond that is very much uncertain because of the large nature of perturbations. Its no longer a Halley type comet then. It is shown beyond doubt that such a change in orbital elements would mean that present day Orionids can never be simulated at ejection times beyond this close approach.

On the other hand in the case of Tempel-Tuttle, although there is some change in the orbital elements near 3 kyr in the past, the change is not that drastic (minimum distance between Tempel-Tuttle and Jupiter was 0.3 AU) to make it non-Halley type. It is not a strong close encounter with Jupiter like in the case of Halley (close encounter distance between Halley and Jupiter was 0.05 AU). Hence one could assume that ejected particles beyond this close approach could also lead to a Halley type meteor shower although significantly different from present day Leonids. All this analysis pertains to

dynamical lifetimes of both these comets.

The physical lifetime is estimated about 0.5 percent mass loss every revolution (Whipple 1951). This in turn means about 200 revolutions. Assuming the typical orbital period of Halley of about 75 years, this is about 15 kyr. In the case of Tempel-Tuttle, considering the typical orbital period of about 33 years, this amounts to 6.6 kyr. Of course the orbital period varies over time as seen both plots 2.17 and 2.19. Hence these are just rough estimates although on an order of magnitudes scale they are reasonable.

2.5 Summary and Discussion

It was found that dust trails formed by 2:13 resonant meteoroids caused the unusual Orionid meteor outbursts on 1993 Oct 18 (Miskotte 1993; Rendtel & Betlem 1993) and 1916 Oct 17 (Olivier 1921). Meteor outbursts from 1436-1440 and 1933-1938 were due to the 1:6 resonance mechanism which matches historical observations in 1436 and 1439 (Imoto & Hasegawa 1958) and 1933-1938 (Millman 1936; Lovell 1954). Furthermore we are able to correlate the recent observations of outbursts from 2006-2010 (Rendtel 2007; Trigo-Rodriguez et al. 2007; Arlt et al. 2008; Kero et al. 2011; IMO database) due to 1:6 resonant meteoroids with our theoretical simulations. Similarly the Leonid outburst in 1998 could be linked partly with 5:14 resonant particles ejected in 1366 A.D. But the major cause of this outburst was the dust trails ejected in 1333 (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999). These correlations are very promising and give us great confidence in confirming theory with observations. Using similar techniques one could also predict similar events for the future. We foresee an Orionid meteor outburst in 2070 (due to the 2:13 resonance) similar to the 1993 outburst. Unfortunately no immediate Leonid storm or outburst (for the next 50 years) could be predicted from 5:14 or 4:11 resonance mechanism from the epochs 1333 and 1366.

Although non-resonant particles can produce random outbursts, our calculations

show that a substantial majority of Orionid outbursts are due to resonant structures in the meteoroid stream. It is just the opposite in the case of Leonid storms. The most spectacular activity was never directly linked with known resonances (Asher 1999).

Most of the theoretical aspects of these two resonances can have very significant and interesting effects on real observations. The compact dust trails getting preserved for many 10 kyr due to 1:6 MMR hint at an exciting possibility that strong meteor outbursts could occur in the future even after the comet becomes extinct, i.e. survival times of some resonant structures could be much higher than the physical lifetime of the parent body. In the case of Leonids, the typical survival times are about 1,000 years which is much less than the expected physical lifetime (close to 200 revolutions) of the comet.

Understanding the history of comets is crucial to predicting meteor showers. In this work we find that Orionid outbursts in 1436-1440, 1916, 1933-1938, 1993 and 2006-2010 were caused by resonant particles ejected from Halley before 240 B.C., the date beyond which there are no direct observational records of the comet. Previous works have correlated the 1998 Leonid outburst with the 1333 return of the comet (which is also beyond the known direct observation). As a corollary to the above point about the importance of knowing comets' histories, one could argue that non-uniform meteor rates can act as a great tool to backtrack the history of a comet beyond the time frame in which there are direct sightings of the comet itself. All of these prove how useful the comparison between meteor observations and these simulations are. In short the theoretical simulations act as an indirect confirmed observation of Halley and Tempel-Tuttle beyond 240 B.C. and 1366 A.D. respectively.

Even though the Eta Aquariid shower is considerably different (McIntosh & Hajduk 1983) from the Orionid shower in many ways, it would be worthwhile to verify whether all these resonant phenomena and enhanced activity are applicable in its case as well (CBET 944, 2007). The low number (compared to Orionids) of credible observations of Eta-Aquariids is a limitation in this regard though.

Negative observations, comprising diminished meteor rates of Orionids in some particular years compared to adjacent years (e.g. ZHR reaching only 7 in 1900: Kronk 1988) could be as scientifically valuable as enhanced meteor phenomena which we have investigated in this work. Williams (1997) has discussed the role of Uranus's effects in removing meteoroids from certain parts of the Leonid stream. This mechanism was also linked with resonance phenomena. A future careful study of such events and comparisons with real observations can also be intriguing in many aspects.

Figure 2.1: Evolution of 1:6 resonant argument of 1P/Halley over 6000 years from 2404 B.C.

Figure 2.2: Evolution of 2:13 resonant argument of 1P/Halley over 6000 years from 2404 B.C.

Figure 2.3: Evolution of 5:14 resonant argument of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle over 6000 years from 1366 A.D.

Figure 2.4: Evolution of 4:11 resonant argument of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle over 6000 years from 1366 A.D.

Figure 2.5: (a, M) space for 1:6 resonance in Orionids showing regions where particles undergo resonant librations, as a function of initial semi-major axis and mean anomaly at the initial epoch JD 1208880.5.

Figure 2.6: (a, M) space for 2:13 resonance in Orionids; initial epoch JD 1633920.5

Figure 2.7: Ascending Nodal Distance in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.

Figure 2.8: Solar Longitude of Node in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910.

Figure 2.9: Difference in Nodal Passage Times in 2007 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in -910. The difference is computed by subtracting the time of particle's arrival at the node and the time of observed outburst.

Figure 2.10: Ascending Nodal Distance in 2007 vs Initial Orbital Period of Meteoroids in -910. For comparison, comet Halley's $r_a \sim 1.8$ AU in the 1986 return. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.

Figure 2.11: (a, M) space for 5:14 resonance in Leonids; initial epoch JD 2220280.5

Figure 2.12: (a, M) space for 4:11 resonance in Leonids; initial epoch JD 2220280.5

Figure 2.13: Descending Nodal Distance in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.

Figure 2.14: Solar Longitude of Node in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366.

Figure 2.15: Difference in Nodal Passage Times in 1998 vs Initial Semi-major Axis of Meteoroids in 1366. The difference is computed by subtracting the time of particle's arrival at the node and the time of observed outburst.

Figure 2.16: Descending Nodal Distance in 1998 vs Initial Orbital Period of Meteoroids in 1366. Dotted line represents the position of Earth at the same time.

Figure 2.17: Evolution of 1P/Halley's semi-major axis in an integration going back in time from 240 B.C.; close encounter with Jupiter at 0.05 AU leads to sudden change in orbit at about 12 kyr in past.

Figure 2.18: Heliocentric distance of descending node of 1P/Halley in an integration going back in time from 240 B.C. (same integration as figure 2.17).

Figure 2.19: Evolution of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle’s semi-major axis in an integration going back in time from 1366 A.D.; close encounter with Jupiter at 0.3 AU leads to change in orbit at about 3.5 kyr in past.

Figure 2.20: Heliocentric distance of ascending node of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle in an integration going back in time from 1366 A.D. (same integration as figure 2.19).

Chapter 3

Saturnian Resonances

3.1 Overview

Jovian mean motion resonances are known to have played an important role in determining the long term evolution of many meteoroid streams (Asher & Emel'yanenko 2002; Ryabova 2003; Jenniskens 2006; Vaubaillon, Lamy & Jorda 2006; Soja et al. 2011). As discussed in the previous chapter, Jovian effects lead to significantly different orbital evolution when it comes to resonant particles. This can notably influence the occurrence of sub-structures in the meteoroid stream.

In many cases the compact dust trails due to such Jovian resonances have led to observed outbursts and storms (Yeomans 1981; Kondrat'eva & Reznikov 1985; Asher & Clube 1993; Rendtel & Betlem 1993; McNaught & Asher 1999; Brown et al. 2002; Vaubaillon et al. 2003; Lyytinen & van Flandern 2004; Trigo-Rodríguez et al. 2007; Rendtel 2008; Kero et al. 2011) in many meteor showers. Most of these observational records match with theoretical orbital simulations and predictions to a good degree.

Yeomans (1981) studies the distribution of dust from 55P/Tempel-Tuttle by comparing the Leonid meteor shower data over the 902-1969 A.D. interval. It was found that planetary perturbations and radiation pressure, rather than ejection processes,

dictate the dynamical evolution of the Leonid meteoroids. Significant meteor activity is possible roughly 2500 days before or after the perihelion passage of the comet but only if the comet passes closer than 0.025 AU inside or 0.010 AU outside the Earth's orbit. The orbit of the comet was determined to reasonable accuracy for the period 1366-1966.

Kondrat'eva & Reznikov (1985) made forecasts for Leonid meteoroid swarms intersecting the Earth causing intense outbursts for the years 1999-2002. The meteoroids were assumed to be ejected in all directions as the comet reaches perihelion. The perturbations by giant planets were taken into account. The probabilities of these swarms intersecting the Earth were calculated by finding the difference between nodal distances of the meteoroid particles and the heliocentric distance of the Earth in the years of interest.

Asher & Clube (1993) presents an elaborate study on the occurrence and importance of the events generating meteoroids and dust in the inner solar system. The work is primarily focused on the Taurid complex (which originates from comet 2P/Encke). The dynamics of the 7:2 Jovian resonance is studied in this context. Many prominent events concerning the stream were found to be directly related to this resonance. The forthcoming encounters with the swarm are studied in this paper. The dynamical lifetimes of some of these resonant swarms and their future evolution was analysed in detail.

McNaught & Asher (1999) studies the orbital evolution of Leonid dust trails and their interactions with Earth. This is a significant work in the sense that the observed meteor phenomena and the theoretical simulations matched to the accuracy of 10 minutes or better for the first time after the predictions. Various predictions for enhanced activity were done for the 2031 A.D. return of Tempel-Tuttle. The detailed calculations of orbital elements concerning the encounters for 1999-2002 were presented in this work. In parallel, the outcomes of these forecasts are applied to assess the satellite threat.

Vaubailon et al. (2003) presents Leonid meteor shower forecasts for 2003. It was

expected that the ejected 1499 trail would provide the enhanced activity on 2003 Nov 13 with ZHR of about 100.

Brown et al. (2002) presents video and radar observations of the Leonid shower in 2000. It was found that the first peak of the shower on 2000 Nov 17 (produced from the 1932 ejection epoch) was much stronger in radar compared to the broader peak on 2000 Nov 18 (resulting from the 1866 and 1733 ejection times). ZHR of around 900 (assuming a mass index of 1.7) was estimated. The broader peak had a ZHR of about 600. The same trend was confirmed by other independent observations. However in visual data, the first peak was much smaller relative to the second peak. This shows the significant difference in size distribution although it should be pointed out that visual observations were severely affected by lunar interference in this year. Such comparisons done in that work help for understanding and predicting future events in a better way.

Lyytinen & van Flandern (2004) discusses the possibility of a moderately strong Perseid outburst consisting of mainly faint meteors for 2004 Aug 11 at about 21h UT. It was found that a single-revolution-old dust trail would be the cause of this enhanced meteor activity. It was calculated to pass within 0.0013 AU of Earth's orbit. This work also discusses the effects of Jupiter leading to Earth encountering the densest parts of the Perseid stream.

Generally it is seen that the orbital evolution of resonant meteoroids is dramatically different from that of the non-resonant ones (Sato & Watanabe 2007; Christou, Vaubaillon & Withers 2008). The remarkably different precession rates and particle concentrations of resonant swarms, in comparison to non-resonant meteoroids, lead to varying levels of meteor activity in various showers. This makes the whole study of resonances very interesting and relevant in the context of meteor shower observations.

Hence correlating enhanced meteor activity with known Jovian resonances (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999; Jenniskens et al. 2007; Rendtel 2007; Sekhar & Asher 2014b) and subsequent predictions of future meteor outbursts have been a very active field for some decades. The precision of such calculations has increased significantly

over the years (Jenniskens et al. 1998; McNaught & Asher 1999). It must be noted that the elegant modelling of some of these authors led to the meteor shower forecasts being accurate to the order of few minutes. This was a remarkable achievement of modern day meteor science.

Because many meteoroid stream structures (both in Jupiter family and Halley-type comets) are resonant with Jupiter, almost all past works have concentrated solely on the dynamics of Jovian resonances. One realises that no detailed simulations or analysis were done regarding resonances in meteoroid streams due to Saturn's gravitational effects except a brief mention of a possible 8:9 MMR in Leonids (Adams 1867; Stoney & Downing 1898; Brown 2001; Svoren, Kanuchova & Jakubik 2006). They were never pursued in great detail or rigour like the works focusing on Jovian resonance mechanisms. Most scientists seem to have presumed that Saturnian resonances are either too weak or practically non-existent when it comes to producing enhanced meteor phenomena on Earth. On the overall picture, it makes sense to expect that this is intuitively so because of the smaller mass (and hence weaker gravitational effects) of Saturn compared to Jupiter. But we felt it was important to check whether the intuitive guess is true. Hence detailed calculations were done to understand the dynamics of periodic effects due to Saturn.

Adams (1867) studies briefly the nature of perturbations from different planets on the November meteors (present day Leonids). Some calculations were compared and fine tuned with Professor Hubert Newton's earlier computations on the same topic. Emphasis is mainly given to understanding the periodic nature of this meteor shower. Although perturbations on the node are studied, no detailed calculations were done related to any possible periodic relationship with the planets.

Stoney & Downing (1898) is the first work which looks at the various possible periodicities of Leonids with planets. 5:14, 8:9 and 5:2 possible commensurabilities with Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus respectively are mentioned. The change in densities in different parts of the stream was studied.

Brown (2001) concentrates primarily on the observations and theoretical simulations of Perseids and Leonids. In the case of Leonids, this work looks closely at the 5:14 Jovian resonance and its role in enhanced meteor activity. There is some brief analysis of a possible 8:9 resonance with Saturn and 5:2 resonance with Uranus. But it is found that Saturnian and Uranian resonances are weak compared to the already known Jovian resonances. Elaborate modelling is done to compare the evolution of ejected meteoroids (both non-Jovian resonant and Jovian resonant) with observational records.

Svoren, Kanuchova & Jakubik (2006) studies the filaments within the Perseid meteoroid stream in the context of mean motion resonances. They find 17 filaments inside the Perseid stream which can be related to low order resonances with Jupiter and Saturn. The data comes from photographic orbits. Although a rigorous check on the separation of Jovian and Saturnian resonances is not pursued, they correlate the fine structures with individual resonances involving Jupiter and Saturn. The existence of gaps in the semi-major axis distribution was analysed.

Our simulations in this chapter show that this assumption of Saturn having a negligible role in resonance mechanisms is not true. We find conclusive evidence that strong Saturnian resonances are effective (in our solar system) in trapping large numbers of meteoroids which can lead to formation of compact dust trails in space. Even though Saturnian resonances are quite rare (in terms of the number of commensurabilities involved) compared to Jovian resonances in the context of known meteoroid streams, the newly found Saturnian resonances in this work show significant strength and stability which can in turn relate to spectacular meteor outbursts in the past and future. This chapter investigates such Saturnian resonances in two major streams which are known to exhibit exterior Jovian resonances (Emel'yanenko 2001) namely the Orionids and Leonids.

3.2 Separation of Jovian and Saturnian Resonances

Since there is a well-known 2:5 near commensurability (discussed in the introduction of thesis; see section 1.2), widely known as the great inequality (Kepler 1672; Halley 1676; Laplace 1785; Hill 1890; Lovett 1895; Brouwer & van Woerkom 1950; Milani & Knežević 1990), between the orbits of Jupiter and Saturn, it is vital to check the evolution of resonant arguments (for any particular resonance ratio involving Saturn) of the meteoroid particle for these two nearby resonances simultaneously. Otherwise it could lead to misleading conclusions because of the nearby strong Jovian resonances.

For example in the case of 1:3 MMR (Saturnian), multiplying this ratio by 2:5 gives the nearby 2:15 MMR (Jovian). The current investigation confirms the presence of 1:3 Saturnian MMR (semi-major axis $a_n = 19.84$) in the Orionids. It is essential to check the adjacent 2:15 Jovian resonant argument ($a_n = 19.93$) to avoid being misled from this nearby Jovian MMR. This is a critical test to rule out the direct Jovian effects.

As in chapter 2, we use $a = a_n =$ the ‘nominal resonance location’ (Murray & Dermott 1999, section 8.4) for exterior resonances (Peale 1976) of the form $p:(p+q)$ where q is the order of resonance and repeated conjunction occurs for every p orbits of the particle. This concept is explained in more detail in section 1.1.

Figure 3.1 (a) shows the 1:3 Saturnian resonant argument σ (definition of σ given below) librating continuously for about 4 kyr, then briefly becoming non-resonant (overall range of σ becomes 360° for a short while) and subsequently falling into the same resonance for a further 2 kyr, in the case of an Orionid test particle.

Figure 3.1 (b) shows the 2:15 resonant argument (Jovian) clearly circulating during the same time frame. The starting epoch for both these plots is JD 1208900.18109 = 1404 B.C. October 15.68109, which is the oldest computed perihelion passage time of 1P/Halley (Yeomans & Kiang 1981).

For the Leonids we confirm the presence of 8:9 Saturnian MMR ($a_n = 10.32$).

Figure 3.2 (a) shows σ for this MMR librating for ~ 700 yr before starting to drift from the libration centre (initial epoch = JD 2220280.1685 = computed return time of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle in 1366).

Figures 3.2 (b) and (c) show the adjacent 16:45 ($a_n = 10.36$) and 5:14 ($a_n = 10.33$) resonant arguments (Jovian) clearly circulating for the same test particle during the same time frame. Multiplying 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) by 2:5 (as per the logic of the great inequality discussed before) gives the nearby 16:45 MMR (Jovian). In terms of a_n , 5:14 MMR (Jovian) is even nearer than 16:45 is to 8:9 MMR (Saturnian). It is always important to look for the closest resonance location from Jupiter's point of view. Hence both these Jovian MMRs were verified to avoid being led to incorrect conclusion.

In order to confirm the presence of Saturnian MMR and rule out effects by the nearby Jovian MMR, many of the different possible combinations (see Table 3.1) of 1:3 (Saturnian), 8:9 (Saturnian) and 2:15 (Jovian), 16:45 (Jovian), 5:14 (Jovian) resonant arguments allowed by D'Alembert rules (Murray & Dermott 1999, sections 6.7 and 8.2) were checked to confirm libration and circulation respectively (discussed in section 1.1). Hence about a hundred arguments were plotted to ensure that our conclusions regarding Saturnian resonances are correct. The plots shown in this chapter are carefully chosen so that they act as a typical representation of most of the plots of allowable combination of angles under D'Alembert rules.

A general closed expression for the number of possible resonant arguments $|S|$ (shown in Table 3.1) allowed by the D'Alembert rules can be arrived at (personal communications with Yadu Vasudev from The Institute of Mathematical Sciences, India):

$$|S| = \sum_{i=0}^{(q/2)} (2i+1)(q-2i+1) \quad (3.1)$$

The resonant arguments plotted in Figures 3.1 (a) and 3.2 (a) are respectively $\sigma = \lambda_s - 3\lambda_m + 2\varpi_m$ and $\sigma = 8\lambda_s - 9\lambda_m + \varpi_m$, where λ and ϖ denote mean longitude

Table 3.1: Order of resonances discussed in this work and applying combinatorics to calculate resonant arguments permitted by D’Alembert rules (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2013). T is the approximate number of successive years for the Earth to encounter a single Leonid/Orionid resonant zone. P is the interval until the next series of successive encounters. In previous work (Sekhar & Asher 2014b) on Orionids, $T \sim 5\text{-}6$ yr & $P \sim 71$ yr for 1:6 Jovian, and $T \sim 1\text{-}2$ yr & $P \sim 77$ yr for 2:13 Jovian.

MMR p:(p+q)	Order q	Number of Possible Resonant Arguments S	P (yr)	T (yr)
8:9 S	1	2	33	2
1:3 S	2	6	88	22
5:14 J	9	110	33	1
2:15 J	13	280	-	-
16:45 J	29	2480	-	-

and longitude of pericentre respectively. The subscripts s and m stand for Saturn and meteoroid particle respectively.

Because both Halley’s and Tempel-Tuttle’s orbits are retrograde, here we use the modified definition of $\varpi = \Omega - \omega$ (Saha & Tremaine 1993; Whipple & Shelus 1993). One should be careful to distinguish between prograde and retrograde orbits in order to apply the correct definition when it comes to resonance mechanism. This modified definition of ϖ is different from the convention used by Morais & Namouni (2013) although there is no loss of physics in both cases.

Morais & Namouni (2013) discusses the resonances of a set of asteroids among Centaurs and Damocloids which get trapped in resonances with Jupiter and Saturn. Their orbits are retrograde. They find that these asteroids remain resonant for several thousands of years. When the motion is retrograde, they apply a transformation in which the usual ascending node becomes descending node. To conserve the nature of the longitude of pericentre, which is measured from the true ascending node, they define $\varpi = \omega - \Omega$ which is simply opposite to Saha & Tremaine (1993). But after careful scrutiny, we find that the notations used by Morais & Namouni (2013) are different for the expression of their critical resonant argument. This compensates for the change in definition of ϖ . Hence both notations and definitions remain correct provided that the right substitutions are made.

These techniques (concerning the evolution of various combinations of resonant arguments) clearly show that Saturnian resonances are indeed real and distinct from the near commensurate Jovian resonances. Due to the very high numbers of various combinations possible as per the D'Alembert rules, we do not show all the permissible plots of resonant arguments and their comparison. But a thorough investigation was done to confirm the analysis.

In section 3.3, we integrate individual particles to show dense clusters of Saturnian resonant meteoroids in real space retaining their compact structure for many kyr (unlike the plots showing the libration of resonant argument for a single particle). This could be considered as an independent test for confirming the presence of a particular resonance mechanism.

As elsewhere in this thesis, the numerical integrations in this chapter were done using the MERCURY package (Chambers 1999) implementing the RADAU algorithm (Everhart 1985) with accuracy parameter set to 10^{-12} and including the sun and eight planets, whose orbital elements were retrieved from JPL Horizons (Giorgini et al. 1996). Elements for the parent bodies 1P/Halley and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle were taken from Marsden & Williams (2008). Radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson effects were not included in any integrations.

3.3 Geometry of Resonant Zones

3.3.1 *Orionids*

Figures 3.3 and 3.4 show the general picture of resonant zones for the 1:3 Saturnian MMR ($a_n = 19.84$ AU). In each of figures 3.3 and 3.4, 7200 particles were integrated forward from 1404 B.C. and 1986 A.D. respectively, varying the initial a from 19.0 to 20.8 AU in steps of 0.018 AU, and initial M from 0 to 360° in steps of 5° , keeping other elements (namely q , i , ω and Ω) the same as 1P/Halley. 1404 B.C. is the oldest

computed perihelion passage time (Yeomans & Kiang 1981). 1986 A.D. is the latest observed perihelion return of Halley.

The plotted particles that librate continuously for 4 kyr. The plot shows the distribution of their initial semi-major axis a and mean anomaly M . Resonant particles were identified (cf. section 3.2) by a simple algorithm which looks at the overall range of resonant arguments (for different combinations allowed by D'Alembert rules) for each particle every 10 yr during the whole 4 kyr. A snapshot of the same (a, M) phase space 4 kyr later (for either figure 3.3 or 3.4) shows a similar picture with three dense clouds of resonant particles. The only difference is in the slight movement of zones (in terms of mean anomaly) due to many orbital revolutions where orbital periods vary as time progresses. But they do not affect the overall structure or geometry of the resonant clusters.

The overall geometry (in terms of the number and density) is nearly identical for both figures 3.3 and 3.4. But there are slight differences in the detailed substructure. These are due to the different perturbations from other planets at the different epochs of integrations. This shows the fact that meteoroid ejection from different perihelion passages lead to the occurrence of significant different substructures in the resonant trails which can in turn lead to significantly different future meteor phenomena. For example the libration width (range in a) in figure 3.4 is slightly less than that in figure 3.3. The plots show a snapshot of events occurring in the real solar system due to various perturbations. This means that at some epochs only a smaller subset of the structures in resonant zones could contribute towards meteor outbursts or storms.

The presence of 3 dense clouds instead of 15 itself identifies the phenomenon of 1:3 Saturnian resonance rather than 2:15 Jovian resonance.

Our simulations show that 1:3 resonant meteoroids can remain as compact structures for many kyr (4 kyr is typical). A resonant meteor outburst is a possibility if Earth passes through one of these three clumps in space. When the Earth misses these dense clouds, a normal meteor shower can still occur. This is the typical case for most years

because many conditions have to be satisfied simultaneously for a meteor outburst or storm to occur.

The a range spanned by the resonant zone (Fig. 3.3 and 3.4) is equivalent to perihelion tangential ejection speeds in the range of about $+39$ to $+68 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $+40$ to $+69 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at the 1404 B.C. and 1266 B.C. return of 1P/Halley respectively. These ejection velocities are consistent with cometary activity (Whipple 1951).

Moreover radiation pressure acts in the same way as positive (= forward) ejection velocities, i.e. increasing the orbital period, and for visual meteor sized meteoroids the effect of radiation pressure on the period is quantitatively comparable to these ejection speeds (cf. Kondrat'eva & Reznikov 1985; Asher & Emel'yanenko 2002). Hence these positive ejection velocities (in the gravitational integration model) required to populate this 1:3 resonant zone at this epoch imply that significant numbers of real meteoroids were released by 1P/Halley into this resonance.

If the comet itself is in resonance, it would keep populating only one resonant zone. But because the parent body is not resonant with Saturn (in chapter 1, it is shown that Halley is in the Jovian 1:6 MMR during the ejection epochs discussed here), over centuries the comet will drift through the three 1:3 resonant zones and populate all of them.

3.3.2 *Leonids*

To explore the 8:9 MMR ($a_n = 10.32$) in the Leonid stream, we integrated two sets of 7200 particles varying initial a from 10.16 to 10.46 in steps of 0.0030 and M in steps of 5° . Figures 3.5 and 3.6 show the distribution of particles with various values of initial (a, M) that have not circulated through 360° for the entire period of 1000 years starting from 1366 A.D. and 1998 A.D. respectively. Virtually all such particles are resonant for at least 700 yr (like shown in the figure 3.2 a).

The inherent mechanism of resonant zones is the same as described for Orionids (section 3.3.1) except that there are nine dense clumps in this case. A snap shot of the same phase space after 700 years (in the case of either figure 3.5 and 3.6) shows a similar picture with nine clumps of resonant particles. Our simulations show that 8:9 resonant meteoroids can remain as compact structures for up to many centuries (typically ~ 700 yr; cf. Fig. 3.2 a). The existence of 9 zones instead of 14 zones show the absence of 5:14 Jovian resonance and indicate the presence of 8:9 Saturnian resonance.

Meteoroid ejection velocities in the range of about -28 to $+3$ m s^{-1} and -18 to $+12$ m s^{-1} , consistent with gas-driven ejection from the comet, can populate the entire resonant zone (shown in figure 3.5 and 3.6) at the 1366 and 1998 return of 55P/Tempel-Tuttle respectively. The requirement for negative ejection velocities (in a gravitational integration model) will have an opposite effect to that discussed in section 3.3.1, i.e. the real population of resonant meteoroids will consist of particles less affected by radiation pressure. This would mean enhanced chances of narrow trails of larger meteoroids in turn leading to higher number of bright meteors when they intersect Earth.

Asher et al. (1999) and Brown & Arlt (2000) have shown the relevance of 5:14 Jovian MMR in causing intense meteor outbursts in the recent past.

Williams (1997) studies the gravitational effects of Uranus on the Leonid meteoroid stream. Some particular sets of geometric combinations can affect the stream structure significantly. This is mainly due to the fact that the ascending node of the Leonids (~ 18 AU) is close to the mean heliocentric distance of Uranus (~ 19.20 AU). The perturbations due to Uranus lead the subset of meteoroids to miss the Earth in subsequent revolutions. This leads to a gap of 14.8 years when there will be hardly any meteor activity. It is found that every 84 years, Uranus produces such a gap in the stream. Of course such gaps will be filled in due course by particles ejected from subsequent perihelion passages. That work discusses the 5:2 mean motion resonance between Uranus and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle as well.

3.4 Ecliptic Plane Crossings and Orbital Distribution

3.4.1 *Orionids*

Here we compare distributions of resonant and non-resonant particles. In the resonant case, 2000 particles were integrated around each of Halley's 1404 B.C. and 1266 B.C. returns, varying the initial a from 20.0 to 20.1 AU in steps of 5×10^{-5} AU and keeping q , i , ω and Ω the same as the comet. Offsets of up to 8 years are given so that meteoroids could be fed efficiently to the resonant zones. One of the ejection epochs is 1404 B.C. which is the oldest computed perihelion passage of the comet. 1266 B.C. was chosen as another ejection epoch because the particles come near Earth's orbit in recent times at the solar longitude range corresponding to present day Orionids.

All parameters were the same for the non-resonant particles except the starting epoch was adjusted so that the evolution of non-resonant Orionids can be studied for the same time frame. There were no significant close encounters with planets during this extra integration time of up to a few years.

The active role of 1:6 and 2:13 Jovian MMRs in causing strong Orionid meteor outbursts has previously been demonstrated (Rendtel 2007; Sato & Watanabe 2007; Sekhar & Asher 2014b) in chapter 2. The 1:3 Saturnian MMR can produce similarly compact structures in the Orionid stream.

Figures 3.7 and 3.9 show the (ascending) nodal crossing distribution for particles from a single 1:3 resonant zone, contrasted with non-resonant particles (cf. librating and circulating model comparisons of Emel'yanenko & Bailey 1996, e.g. their fig. 3). High density in the resonant case is in sharp contrast with significantly lower density in the non-resonant case.

The compact structures in figures 3.7 and 3.9 for the librating particles demonstrate the physical presence of dense meteoroid concentrations in real space. Moreover the particle distribution along the orbit (see figures 3.8 and 3.10) shows the non-resonant

ones to be dispersed over a large range of heliocentric distances which in turn leads to low meteoroid concentrations. This is the key feature to be noted in the context of resonant confinement of cometary particles.

Elaborate simulations were done and many tens of plots for ecliptic-plane crossings at multiple times in future were analysed for different ejection epochs. Of all those examples, the ejection epochs of 1404 B.C. and 1266 B.C. and the respective times of 2D phase space plots (450 A.D. and 750 A.D.) for orbital distribution were carefully chosen so that one could clearly see the resonant particles densely clustering near the Earth's orbit. During other ejection epochs, the particles do not come near the Earth's orbit or match the solar longitude (of observed shower) during present times. When 2D space plots are generated for certain years, the resonant clusters (although densely packed) can be seen far away from Earth's orbit. This again is not a good visualisation when we think in the context of meteor showers on Earth. This is the key reason why certain points in time were chosen. Most of the time, the non-resonant particles are significantly away from Earth's orbit in the particular plots. Specific times for the plots were chosen so that clustering of resonant particles near Earth could be clearly seen for comparison.

3.4.2 *Leonids*

For figures 3.11, 3.12, 3.13 and 3.14, the integrations were of two sets of 2000 particles with initial a from 10.35 to 10.36 in steps of 5×10^{-6} and q , i , ω and Ω the same as Tempel-Tuttle. All the particles were integrated for 700 years from the 1333 A.D. and 1366 A.D. returns ($M=0$). The non-resonant sets had the same initial conditions except that, as in section 3.2., the starting epochs were offset so that the dynamics of non-resonant Leonids can be analysed. No relevant close encounters occurred during this additional integration time.

Figures 3.11 and 3.13 show the (descending) nodal crossing distribution in 2000 A.D.

and 1998 A.D. respectively, for meteoroids from a single 8:9 (Saturnian) resonant zone and for non-resonant meteoroids. The resonance leading to the compact distribution is similar to the mechanism discussed in section 3.4.1. The amount of change in nodal dispersion due to two different ejection epochs can be compared. The ejected meteoroids are from the same resonant zones for both ejection epochs 1333 A.D. and 1366 A.D.

Also, as in section 3.4.1, the non-resonant meteoroids are dispersed over a significantly larger range of heliocentric distance (see figures 3.12 and 3.14). Again the epochs and 2D time frames are chosen so that resonant particle clumps could be seen near Earth's orbit whereas the non-resonant particles are demonstrably away from Earth's orbit. The sharp change in density can be noted from these plots. The plots shown here were carefully selected out of tens of other plots so that the existence of narrow dust trails near Earth's orbit (matching solar longitudes of the observed shower) during present times can be seen clearly.

It must be highlighted that the year 1998 had a meteor outburst from 5:14 (Jovian) resonant meteoroids (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999) ejected from 1333. Unfortunately the 8:9 (Saturnian) dust trails miss the Earth by a few months although they come near the Earth's orbit in that year (as shown in figures 3.13 and 3.14). In figure 3.13, the Saturnian resonant particles precisely match the nodal distance and solar longitude as observed for the Jovian resonant particles which caused the 1998 outburst. But the time of nodal crossing is not quite the same and hence they did not contribute for the observed phenomena. It is very much possible that in future we could get spectacular meteor storms or outbursts from these dust trails resonant with Saturn.

Hence these stable resonances exhibited by Saturn can play an important role when it comes to spectacular meteor outbursts or storms just like the previously observed Jovian resonant meteoroids.

3.5 Earth Intersection Possibilities

Looking through the previous literature regarding resonances in meteoroid streams, it is clear that there were no simulations and comparisons with real observations when it comes to Saturnian resonances. Hence it would have been an excellent and a totally new result if a real observation of outburst or storm could be matched by these newly found Saturnian resonances.

Unfortunately the simulations clearly do not show any ideal resonant trail-Earth intersections in the near past or future. Many tests were done to check for any possible events for about 100 years in past or future. For most ejection epochs in both Orionids and Leonids, the results are not very encouraging. Nevertheless it must be clarified that detailed checks were not done to correlate/predict for the distant past/future. It is certainly an interesting and worthwhile exercise. Much more elaborate future work is planned along those lines.

3.6 Summary and Discussion

We have shown that Orionid meteoroids can stay continuously in 1:3 MMR with Saturn for ~ 4 kyr and Leonid meteoroids in 8:9 MMR with Saturn for ~ 700 yr. It is verified that none of these resonant signatures are due to nearby Jovian resonances such as 2:15 and 5:14 in Orionids and Leonids respectively.

The survival times (of the order of 10^3 yr) and density distributions of these Saturnian resonances, which can in turn lead to very compact dust trails producing enhanced meteor activity, are comparable to those due to previously known Jovian resonances like 2:13 MMR in the Orionids discussed in chapter 2.

In Table 3.1, T is the approximate number of successive years for the Earth to encounter a single Leonid/Orionid resonant zone. P is the interval until the next series of successive encounters. In previous work (Sekhar & Asher 2014b) on Orionids, $T \sim$

5-6 yr & $P \sim 71$ yr for 1:6 Jovian, and $T \sim 1-2$ yr & $P \sim 77$ yr for 2:13 Jovian.

Generally the lower the order q of a resonance, the higher its strength (which directly means resonant dust trails staying resonant for more time). In the resonances mentioned above, it is then fair to assume that the weaker gravitational effect (in comparison to Jupiter) of Saturn is compensated by the difference in order of resonance.

In the case of the 8:9 and 1:3 MMR (Saturnian) q is 1 and 2 respectively, very low compared to the values of 9 and 13 in the case of 5:14 and 2:15 MMR (Jovian) respectively. Saturn's effects can become significant in such cases. Hence one cannot rule out the possibility of a time (in past or future) when there could be spectacular Orionid or Leonid meteor displays due to Saturn's effects comparable to those due to Jovian effects.

Figure 3.1: (a) Libration of 1:3 (Saturnian) resonant argument for an Orionid test particle, confirming presence of 1:3 MMR with Saturn. (b) Circulation of 2:15 (Jovian) resonant argument for the same particle, confirming absence of 2:15 MMR with Jupiter.

Figure 3.2: (a) Libration of 8:9 (Saturnian) resonant argument for a Leonid test particle, confirming presence of 8:9 MMR with Saturn. Circulation of (b) 16:45 (Jovian) and (c) 5:14 (Jovian) resonant arguments for the same particle confirm absence of 16:45 and 5:14 MMR with Jupiter.

Figure 3.3: three resonant zones (integrated for 4 kyr) for 1:3 Saturnian MMR in Orionids as a function of a and M at initial epoch JD 1208900.18109; 1404 B.C. Oct 15 return

Figure 3.4: three resonant zones (integrated for 4 kyr) for 1:3 Saturnian MMR in Orionids as a function of a and M at initial epoch JD 2446470.5.; 1986 Feb 9 return

Figure 3.5: nine zones (integrated for 1 kyr) for 8:9 Saturnian MMR in Leonids as a function of (a, M) at initial epoch JD 2220280.1685; 1366 Oct 19 return

Figure 3.6: nine zones (integrated for 1 kyr) for 8:9 Saturnian MMR in Leonids as a function of (a, M) at initial epoch JD 2451040.5; 1998 Aug 14 return

Figure 3.7: Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 450 A.D.; particles ejected in 1404 B.C. return

Figure 3.8: Distribution of heliocentric distances, for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 450 A.D.; particles ejected in 1404 B.C. return

Figure 3.9: Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 750 A.D.; particles ejected in 1266 B.C. return

Figure 3.10: Distribution of heliocentric distances, for sets of 1:3 Saturnian MMR and non-resonant Orionid particles in 750 A.D.; particles ejected in 1266 B.C. return

Figure 3.11: Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 2000 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1366 A.D. return time frame.

Figure 3.12: Distribution of heliocentric distances for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 2000 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1366 A.D. return time frame.

Figure 3.13: Ecliptic plane crossings for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 1998 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1333 A.D. return time frame.

Figure 3.14: Distribution of heliocentric distances for sets of 8:9 MMR (Saturnian) and non-resonant Leonid particles in 1998 A.D., both sets having evolved over the same time; particles ejected in 1333 A.D. return time frame.

Chapter 4

General Relativistic Effects

4.1 Overview

One of the greatest triumphs of general relativity (GR) was the prediction (Einstein 1915) and subsequent confirmation of the additional precession of perihelion of Mercury.

Einstein (1915) was a ground breaking work which formulated and explored many different aspects of general relativity. In this theory, Albert Einstein postulated a space-time continuum structure for the universe in which massive celestial bodies create curvatures. These curvatures dictate the dynamics of motion where the bodies follow geodesics in this 4 dimensional space-time fabric. The effects of gravity are considered to be a manifestation of this space-time curvature. Bending of star light due to gravitational fields was an exceptionally radical example of this property. One of the other key predictions from the general theory was the accurate calculation of the anomaly in the precession of the perihelion of Mercury. Newtonian effects cannot account for the observed shift in perihelion of Mercury. The additional precession was found to be the contribution from relativistic effects.

Ever since this important discovery, only few works (Shapiro, Ash & Smith 1968, Lieske & Null 1969, Fox, Williams & Hughes 1982, Sitarski 1992, Shahid-Saless &

Yeomans 1994, Venturini & Gallardo 2010) have undertaken applications of general relativity to the long term orbital evolution of small solar system bodies.

Shapiro, Ash & Smith (1968) confirms the relativistic precession in 1566 Icarus from optical observations and compare it with the theoretical prediction of GR to well within the uncertainty of 20 percent. A comparison with the observed GR precession of Mercury's orbit is done. Furthermore an indirect method of estimating the mass of Mercury is employed by using its perturbations on the orbit of Icarus.

Lieske & Null (1969) presents the results of photographic observations of Icarus from 1949 to 1968 and Doppler shift observations in 1968. The observations confirm the predictions of GR using both the Schwarzschild non-isotropic and isotropic line elements. Furthermore the dynamical oblateness of the sun is estimated. Oblateness of the sun can lead to precession in orbiting bodies.

Fox, Williams & Hughes (1982) was the first work concerning the orbit of a meteoroid stream where the general relativistic effects were applied. They find that there is a change of 9.17 arc seconds per century in the argument of pericentre in Geminids due to GR effects. It was proposed that although this is a small value compared to the Newtonian precession, it is still noteworthy for investigation over long time scales.

Sitarski (1992) did a study on the relativistic motion of 1566 Icarus. Accurate astrometric observations were done to confirm the predictions of general relativity. Icarus is the only body apart from Mercury where detailed observations match theoretical tests of general theory. The shift in perihelion due to GR is about 10 arc seconds per century for Icarus. It was found that orbital motion of Icarus agrees perfectly with observations without the necessity of any non-gravitational forces if GR corrections are taken into account.

Shahid-Saless & Yeomans (1994) discusses the inclusion of relativistic contributions in the equations of motion of many asteroids and comets to significantly improve the orbital solutions. It was demonstrated that for bodies with small semi-major axes and

large eccentricities, relativity plays an important role in dynamical modelling.

Venturini & Gallardo (2010) discusses relativistic corrections in cometary orbits and the implementation of such effects in a numerical integrator. Some simpler models are proposed to take into account the change in the argument of perihelion. The key goal of this work is to match the mean anomaly evolution accurately by varying eccentricities when GR effects are considered.

Previous calculations mentioned in chapters 2 and 3 have shown that the resonant structures (due to effects of both Jupiter & Saturn) in meteoroid streams can retain their compact structures for the order of few thousand years. There are various previous works (Yeomans 1981, Asher & Clube 1993, Jenniskens et al. 1998, Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999, McNaught & Asher 1999, Brown 2001, Ryabova 2003, Lyytinen & van Flandern 2004, Rudawska, Jopek & Dybczynki 2005, Watanabe, Sato & Kasuga 2005, Wiegert & Brown 2005, Vaubaillon, Lamy & Jorda 2006, Jenniskens et al. 2007, Maslov 2007, Rendtel 2007, Sato & Watanabe 2007, Christou, Vaubaillon & Withers 2008, Wiegert, Vaubaillon & Campbell-Brown 2009, Christou 2010, Soja et al. 2011, Sekhar & Asher 2013, 2014b) which focus on orbital evolution of dust trails for hundreds to many thousands of years. It would be worthwhile to look at the effects of general relativistic precession for such long term evolution of meteoroid orbits and check whether such effects are important in the long term prediction of meteor outbursts or storms. During that time frame, changes in a and e are quite small for the purpose of study presented here.

Rudawska, Jopek & Dybczynki (2005) do orbital simulations for 1P/Halley, 2P/Encke, 55P/Tempel-Tuttle, 109P/Swift-Tuttle, 3200 Phaethon and 2002 SY₅₀. An equation relating the ejection velocity and change of semi-major axis was applied with two slight variations. The results obtained from both these variations are compared and checked for accuracy.

Watanabe, Sato & Kasuga (2005) presents the orbital evolution of the Phoenicids. The outburst in 1956 was investigated in detail. The orbit of the shower was linked to

the orbit of asteroid 2003 WY₂₅ and comet D/1819 W1. Extensive simulations were done for this correlation. It was found that a big subset of particles ejected in the 18th and 19th centuries came near the Earth in 1956 and caused the observed outburst.

Maslov (2007) summarises the Leonid meteor shower forecasts for the period of 2001-2100. All of them contain maxima, their expected intensity and average brightness. Overall the long term orbital evolution of Leonids was studied for understanding the precise Earth intersection possibilities.

Christou (2010) explores the list of comets and meteoroid streams which can be likely candidates for producing meteor activity on Mars and Venus. The dynamical class, orbital period and the proximity of their orbits to these planetary bodies are studied in detail. It was found that the Martian candidates consisted of six Halley-type comets, eleven long period comets and eight showers originating from Encke and Jupiter family types. The meteor showers on other planets could also be variable on seasonal scales.

Relativistic effects would become more pronounced when a body moves with a high velocity. Hence low perihelion distance (q) would lead (due to Kepler's second law) to greater precession per revolution. Since this precession occurs during every perihelion passage, a larger number of revolutions means this effect accumulates very efficiently over a long period of time. In short, a body with small q and reasonably small a will have maximum contribution due to relativistic precession.

Another important effect when a body comes very close to a massive rotating body is the Lense-Thirring effect which is due to the dragging of space-time by a rotating body (Iorio 2005). It is not included in our calculations in this work mainly because it is typically four orders of magnitude smaller (Iorio 2005) than the effect discussed here.

Iorio (2005) studies the Lense-Thirring secular effect on planetary orbital evolution. It is found that the deviation in perihelion and nodes is of the order of 10^{-3} arc seconds

per century for Mercury. A novel approach of using a suitable linear combination of orbital residuals of the nodes of Mercury, Venus and Mars is employed to avoid the complications of classical secular **precessions from the perturbation theory**.

4.2 Drift in argument of pericentre due to GR and its subsequent effect on nodal distances

Change in the argument of pericentre (ω) of an orbit due to GR effects is given by (page 197, Weinberg 1972):

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{6\pi GM}{a(1 - e^2)} \quad (4.1)$$

where a and e are the semi-major axis and eccentricity of the orbit respectively. Equation 4.1 gives the result in radians per revolution. The same expression can be applied to any cometary/meteoroid orbit in the solar system (Fox, Williams & Hughes 1982, Shahid-Saless & Yeomans 1994).

$$r_a = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{(1 + e \cos \omega)} \quad (4.2)$$

$$r_d = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{(1 - e \cos \omega)} \quad (4.3)$$

Equation 4.2 gives the expression for the heliocentric distance of ascending node (r_a). Equation 4.3 gives the expression for the heliocentric distance of descending node (r_d). These two quantities are critical for any meteor shower prediction calculations because the heliocentric distances of ascending or descending node should be close to Earth's orbit in order to produce any meteor activity. Hence significant changes in these parameters can directly decide the outcome of shower prediction models.

The relationship between the change in nodal distances (Δr) with respect to the

Table 4.1: $\Delta\omega$ and Δr due to general relativistic effects for different parent bodies and meteoroid streams in 1000 years. Ascending nodes for Orionids and Halley. Descending nodes for Geminids, Phaethon, Leonids and Tempel-Tuttle (taken from Sekhar 2013).

Body/Meteoroid Stream	q (AU)	a (AU)	e	ω (Deg.)	$\Delta\omega$ ($\times 10^{-2}$ Deg.)	Δr ($\times 10^{-4}$ AU)
Icarus	0.187	1.078	0.827	31.348	2.8	8.3
Phaethon	0.140	1.271	0.890	322.148	2.7	8.0
Geminids	0.141	1.372	0.890	324.420	2.3	7.7
Halley	0.575	17.871	0.968	112.279	0.013	0.054
Orionids	0.578	18.000	0.968	81.500	0.012	0.018
Tempel-Tuttle	0.977	10.337	0.906	172.499	0.017	0.0020
Leonids	0.984	10.300	0.904	172.400	0.017	0.0019

change in argument of pericentre ($d\omega$) could be computed by differentiating equations 4.2 and 4.3.

$$dr_a = \frac{ae(1 - e^2) \sin \omega d\omega}{(1 + e \cos \omega)^2} \quad (4.4)$$

$$dr_d = \frac{-ae(1 - e^2) \sin \omega d\omega}{(1 - e \cos \omega)^2} \quad (4.5)$$

These expressions are used to compute the orbital changes in various meteoroid streams and parent bodies as mentioned below. The values of $\Delta\omega$ and Δr given in Table 4.1 and 4.2 are calculated using the equations 4.1, 4.4 and 4.5. The orbital elements a, e and ω of 1P/Halley (JD 2456400.5), 55P/Tempel-Tuttle (JD 2450880.5), 3200 Phaethon (JD 2456400.5) and 1566 Icarus (JD 2456400.5) are taken for epochs (mentioned in brackets) from IAU-Minor Planet Center. Latest orbital parameters for various meteoroid streams are substituted from IAU-Meteor Data Center.

Calculations for 1566 Icarus were done because it is a well known low q body and has the highest precession rate due to GR among small solar system bodies. Hence it is a good example to compare with other parent bodies like Phaethon, Halley and Tempel-

Table 4.2: $\Delta\omega$ and Δr for different low q (≤ 0.15 AU) and low a (≤ 1.5 AU) meteoroid streams (taken from the list of established meteor showers in IAU-MDC) due to general relativistic precession in 1000 years (taken from Sekhar 2013).

IAU Code	Meteoroid Stream	q (AU)	a (AU)	ω (Deg.)	$\Delta\omega$ ($\times 10^{-2}$ Deg.)	Δr ($\times 10^{-3}$ AU)
004 GEM	Geminids	0.141	1.372	324.420	2.3	0.8
164 NZC	Northern June Aquilids	0.114	1.348	329.500	3.1	1.3
390 THA	November θ Aurigids	0.116	1.130	330.070	4.0	1.4
165 SZC	Southern June Aquilids	0.110	1.150	152.000	4.1	1.6
152 NOC	North. Daytime ω Cetids	0.108	0.967	25.600	5.4	1.9
171 ARI	Daytime Arietids	0.085	1.376	25.900	4.0	2.0

Tuttle as shown in Table 4.1. Although the orbital elements of meteoroid streams are slightly different from those of the corresponding parent bodies, the changes in $\Delta\omega$ and Δr are practically small in terms of order of magnitude (as shown in Table 4.1).

Table 4.2 shows the list of established meteor showers which have low q (≤ 0.15 AU) and low a (≤ 1.5 AU). All the latest orbital elements are taken from IAU-Meteor Data Center. Although the parent bodies of most showers in this list are not confirmed, it is still worthwhile to calculate and compare the GR precession and the subsequent nodal displacement in these streams.

It can be clearly seen that $\Delta\omega$ in Northern Daytime ω Cetids, daytime Arietids and Geminids is about 100 times that of Leonids and Orionids for an orbital evolution of 1000 years. Subsequently our calculations show that Δr due to $\Delta\omega$ in daytime Arietids, Northern Daytime ω Cetids and Geminids can be around 1000 times that in Leonids. Overall the substantial effect of GR in low q showers compared to other showers can be understood from this analysis.

It could be found that the Northern Daytime ω Cetids (Sekanina 1976) have the highest rate of GR precession in ω ($\Delta\omega \sim 5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees in 1 kyr). Low values of q and a make this stream favourable for efficient accumulation (precession adds up as time progresses) of the GR effect over many revolutions. However the maximum Δr

($\sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ AU in 1 kyr) is exhibited by Daytime Arietids (Sekanina 1976) due to low q and low a compounded by a slightly favourable value in ω .

Sekanina (1976) gives elaborate calculations for mean radiant and D-distribution of various streams. Possible association between streams and parent bodies are made. Also derived absolute stream density matches with the estimate of space densities from cometary production rates of comparable size. Orbital properties of Northern Daytime ω Cetids is mentioned here.

4.3 Conditions for maximum relativistic precession in pericentre

The nature of equation 4.1 makes it clear that relativistic precession can have extreme values for some combinations of q and a . It is important to find the validity of such solutions to check whether they can be realistic in real solar system bodies.

4.3.1 Analytical treatment

According to Kepler's third law:

$$P = a^{3/2} \tag{4.6}$$

where P and a are in units of years and AU respectively.

Hence equation 4.1 (which gives the precession in radians per revolution) can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta\omega' = \frac{6\pi GM}{a(1 - e^2)a^{(3/2)}} \tag{4.7}$$

to find the GR precession per year.

One could find the limiting conditions analytically by considering the right hand side of equation 4.7 as a function in q and a (where e can be expressed in terms of a and q). $6\pi GM$ is a constant and hence not considered in the function.

The expression for $\Delta\omega'$ can be written as a function:

$$F(a, q) = \frac{1}{(2qa^{3/2} - q^2a^{1/2})} \quad (4.8)$$

The denominator is zero when $2a = q$. This leads to asymptotic values as shown in figures 4.1 and 4.2. This is obviously an unreal case as per the definition of q in celestial mechanics.

Also the extreme values of this function can be derived analytically. In order to find the extreme values for different values of a at a constant value in q , one has to differentiate equation 4.8 with respect to a and equate to zero.

$$\frac{dF(a, q)}{da} = 0 \quad (4.9)$$

After further simplification, one arrives at the condition that:

$$q = 6a \quad (4.10)$$

This condition cannot occur as per the definition of q and a in celestial mechanics. This means that extreme values (or turning points of the function) in $\Delta\omega$ occur only in the abstract part (which implies that it is unreal in nature) of this function's domain (cf. section 4.3.2 below).

Similarly to find the extreme values of this function for different values of q at a constant value in a , one has to differentiate equation 4.8 with respect to q and equate

to zero.

$$\frac{dF(a, q)}{dq} = 0 \quad (4.11)$$

Simplification leads to the condition below:

$$q = a \quad (4.12)$$

This is a turning point (which corresponds to minima showing the case for circular orbit when $q=a$; which means pericentre cannot be distinguished for the orbit) in the function as shown in figure 4.2.

4.3.2 Numerical treatment

The same points could be argued using numerical solutions as well.

Figure 4.1 clearly shows that extreme values of the function occur at impossible conditions (as shown in equation 4.8) relating q and a . The turning point at $a=0.018$ AU directly corresponds to the condition shown in equation 4.10. That is one of the extreme points in the function. There is a feature showing an asymptotic nature at $a=0.054$ AU as well. All these correspond to unreal parts (unreal and real regions are separated by the vertical dotted line in the figure) of the function because a can never be less than q according to the definition of Keplerian elements. These unreal parts (left hand side of the dotted line) in the function phase space have drastically high values compared to the near zero values in the real part (right hand side of the dotted line). This means that in abstract mathematical space (which corresponds to impossible configurations in real nature), the function can exceed classical precession by many orders of magnitudes. But in reality the Einsteinian or relativistic precession is very small compared to the Newtonian or classical precession. Overall the non-abstract regime of function matches well with the observed reality in the solar system.

Figure 4.2 shows that the extreme values (one turning point of function is shown by vertical dotted line on the right) of function are possible for conditions (as shown in equation 4.12) in q and a . Furthermore, at $q=1.934$ AU, one could see the asymptotic feature of the function. This is impossible in nature because q cannot exceed a (shown by the vertical dotted line on the right; region to the right of this line is unreal) as per the definition of Keplerian elements. Hence the feasible part is the regime where $q \leq a$ (left of the dotted line). In most of this real part (between the two dotted lines), the value of function is near zero compared to the peaks in the unreal part. This is perfectly correlating with the real solar system because relativistic precession is always significantly smaller (corresponds to function when it has minimal values in the real regime) compared to Newtonian precession (typically of the order of tens of degrees per kyr in many showers). In the real regime of the function, one could see there is an asymptotic feature when q is very close to zero. According to the definition of Keplerian elements, q is measured from the centre of the sun. In reality there are no bodies which can exist at such small distances because the sun is not a point object and it has a radius of about 0.005 AU (shown by the vertical dotted line on the left). Hence that feature of the function can also be ruled out from the real solar system. The feasible region lies between the two dotted lines.

For both figures 4.1 and 4.2, the example of Northern Daytime ω Cetids (Sekanina 1976) was chosen because it shows the maximum GR precession in ω amongst all the established meteoroid streams taken from IAU-MDC.

In the abstract mathematical phase space, for some combinations of q and a this function gives asymptotic values. But in the real world, GR precession cannot exceed Newtonian precession for any realistic combinations. The approach mentioned in this sub-section could be considered as an independent theoretical proof for this fact.

4.4 Values of argument of pericentre for maximum change in nodal distances

Equations 4.4 and 4.5 show that Δr at any instant would depend on ω for a constant value of $\Delta\omega$. For a stream defined by a given q and a , the value of $\Delta\omega$ per unit time is constant. This means that at some values of ω (at different times in the orbital history), a very small constant $\Delta\omega$ could lead to magnification (from the geometric effect induced due to the very nature of the function) of the effect in Δr . Hence it is important to find as to which of all possible values in ω can lead to maximum nodal displacements in the dust trail. This can be very crucial for meteor outburst or storm forecasts. This phenomenon becomes extremely important when we deal with larger meteoroid particles (≥ 1 mm) whose orbital evolutions are not considerably affected by radiative forces (Burns, Lamy & Soter 1979). In such cases, the GR effects can be cumulative and very effective over long time scales i.e. precession in argument of pericentre keeps on increasing as time progresses.

4.4.1 Numerical treatment

Numerical solutions were done (see figures 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6 and 4.7 for five of the showers analysed in section 4.2) to compute the limiting values of ω . Here the limiting value means the points in ω at which the Δr is maximised and can possibly be substantial enough to affect the dust trail-Earth intersections. There are some values in ω at which the GR precession does not matter at all for practical purposes. Figure 4.5 and 4.7 show that Δr in Geminids and Leonids has extreme values when $\omega \sim 16^\circ$ and 343° . Figure 4.6 indicates that Δr in Orionids has peak (positive and negative) values when $\omega \sim 171^\circ$ and 188° . Understanding the maximum change in nodal distances is crucial in meteor forecast models.

Please note Y-axis scale for figure 4.5 representing Geminids. It clearly shows how

substantial the error (of the order of 10^{-3} AU) in nodal distances (if GR effects are not included) could be, when the particles have $\omega \sim 343^\circ$ (non-Earth intersecting though) during its past or future. In such cases, general relativistic precession could actually play as decisive a factor in the intersection or miss of a concentrated dust trail with Earth (diameter $\sim 10^{-4}$ AU) when long term predictions (of the order of kyr) are involved. During present times, Geminids have $\omega \sim 324^\circ$ (IAU-Meteor Data Center) which is not too far from producing an error of the order of 10^{-3} AU when GR effects are ignored. $\omega \sim 324^\circ$ gives Earth intersection at all times when a and e are constant.

All other established meteoroid streams in Table 4.2 have $\Delta r \sim 10^{-3}$ AU. The same can be understood from the figures 4.3 and 4.4. Previous calculations (Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999, McNaught & Asher 1999) have shown that the Leonid meteor storms in the past were caused by dust trails with widths of the order of 10^{-3} AU. It must be clarified that GR effects and errors in nodal distances are not very substantial in the case of Leonids (as evident from Table 4.1 and Figure 4.7). Hence ignoring GR precession in such cases is perfectly legitimate and sensible.

But emphasis is made on the point that dust trails causing enhanced meteor activity in the past were having dimensions similar to the order of errors found in more GR relevant streams. This is a significant testimony to the fact that neglecting GR effects in some cases could lead to wrong meteor shower forecasts when dense dust trails are involved. Although GR effect (in 1 kyr) is less than width of most streams, sometimes observable features within streams (namely trails) can have width comparable to GR effect.

4.4.2 *Analytical treatment*

One could find these limiting values in ω analytically as well, for clarity and rigour. The simple analytical approach (using standard techniques in calculus) is described below.

$$\frac{d^2 r_a}{d\omega^2} = \frac{ae(1 - e^2)[(1 + e \cos \omega) \cos \omega + 2e \sin^2 \omega]}{(1 + e \cos \omega)^3} \quad (4.13)$$

$$\frac{d^2 r_d}{d\omega^2} = \frac{-ae(1 - e^2)[(1 - e \cos \omega) \cos \omega - 2e \sin^2 \omega]}{(1 - e \cos \omega)^3} \quad (4.14)$$

Equations 4.13 and 4.14 give the derivative of equations 4.4 and 4.5 respectively. In order to find the value of ω corresponding to the extreme values of Δr_a and Δr_d for a constant value of $\Delta\omega$, equations 4.13 and 4.14 can be equated to zero.

$$\frac{d^2 r_a}{d\omega^2} = 0 \quad (4.15)$$

$$\frac{d^2 r_d}{d\omega^2} = 0 \quad (4.16)$$

Substituting the expressions in equation 4.13 and 4.14 into equations 4.15 and 4.16 respectively and further simplification of above expressions yield:

$$e \cos^2 \omega - \cos \omega - 2e = 0 \quad (4.17)$$

$$e \cos^2 \omega + \cos \omega - 2e = 0 \quad (4.18)$$

Solving the simple quadratic equations 4.17 and 4.18 give two roots each, of which only one corresponds to the real case:

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[(1 - \sqrt{(1 + 8e^2)})/2e] \quad (4.19)$$

Equation 4.19 shows the real root which corresponds to specific values of ω leading

to maximum Δr_d . The extreme values for Δr_d in Orionids occur when $\omega \sim 171$ and 188.

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[(-1 + \sqrt{(1 + 8e^2)})/2e] \quad (4.20)$$

Equation 4.20 gives the real root for specific cases of ω which can produce extreme values of Δr_d . The maximum values for Δr_d in Leonids and Geminids appear when $\omega \sim 16$ and 343. The analytical treatment perfectly matches with the numerical solutions shown in figures 4.5, 4.6 and 4.7. Hence it is an independent and parallel verification of the whole analysis.

4.5 Summary and Discussion

It is found that changes in the nodal distances due to the small changes in argument of pericentre due to GR effects is substantial when we consider low q and low a showers. Of course there can be other effects during orbital evolutions which could modify these parameters in other ways. However it is important to note that precession due to GR is independent of the size of the particle unlike radiation pressure, Poynting-Robertson effect, Yarkovsky effect etc. Furthermore it would accumulate efficiently over time and would not get nullified or corrected directly by other secular effects.

It is evident that evolution of small meteoroid particles (with diameters ≤ 1 mm) would be dominated by various radiative forces (Burns, Lamy & Soter 1979). This would in turn mean that only the large particles accumulate the GR precession effectively over such long time scales. Such particles are definitely relevant in this study because large particles have more chances to produce bright meteors on Earth.

In short, in the well known case of Geminids, Δr from relativistic precession is about 1000 times that of the present day Leonids because of larger $\Delta\omega$ from relativistic precession and initial ω favouring the near maxima of Δr . It is found that the low q

shower Northern Daytime ω Cetids has the highest rate of GR precession in ω ($\Delta\omega \sim 5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees in 1 kyr) out of all the established meteoroid streams so far. For comparison (with GR), many Halley type orbits have classical precession of the order of few tens of degrees in kyr. The maximum Δr ($\sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ AU in 1 kyr) is seen in Daytime Arietids due to its low q and low a coupled with a slightly favourable value in ω . An interesting aspect of Daytime Arietids concerning its link with sungrazing comets is discussed in detail in chapter 5.

Changes in nodal distance r in this range can be crucial for meteor outburst/storm forecast models especially considering the dimensions of dust trails involved in Leonid meteor storms in the past. This proves that there could be interesting exceptions (regarding accuracy of the Newtonian model) for some particular combinations of q , e and ω of the meteoroid streams where GR effects have to be taken into account for accurate meteor shower forecasts.

Figure 4.1: Extreme values of $F(a, q)$ plotted for different values in a for Northern Daytime ω Cetids like ($q=0.108$ AU) orbit. The region to the left of $a = 0.108$ AU (separated by vertical dotted line) shows the unreal part. To the right of that region is the feasible and stable part of the function.

Figure 4.2: Extreme values of $F(a, q)$ plotted for different values in q for Northern Daytime ω Cetids like ($a=0.967$ AU) orbit. The region to the right of $q = 0.967$ AU (separated by vertical dotted line on the right) is the unreal part. The region to the left of that separation is real (except when q is smaller than the radius of the sun shown by the vertical dotted line on the left). The region between two dotted lines corresponds to feasible part in the solar system.

Figure 4.3: Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Daytime Arietids for different values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=4.0 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr

Figure 4.4: Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Northern Daytime ω Cetids for various values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr

Figure 4.5: Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Geminids for all values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=2.3 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees/kyr

Figure 4.6: Change in heliocentric distance of ascending node in Orionids for various values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=1.2 \times 10^{-4}$ degrees/kyr

Figure 4.7: Change in heliocentric distance of descending node in Leonids for all possible values of argument of pericentre for a constant $\Delta\omega=1.7 \times 10^{-4}$ degrees/kyr

Chapter 5

Sungrazers

5.1 Overview

Sungrazers constitute a category of comets which are significantly different (in terms of some orbital elements) from other types like Jupiter family and Halley-type comets. They have been a subject of great interest ever since comets were observed.

There have been recorded observations (Kreutz 1888; Marsden 1967, 1989; Hasegawa & Nakano 2001; Strom 2002; Sekanina & Chodas 2012) of extremely bright and spectacular sungrazing comets in historical times.

Kreutz (1888) was able to link some of the observed sungrazing comets in the past to the orbit of a common ancestor which would have fragmented in the past. Many later works were able to confirm this link. Hence this class of comets was named Kreutz family in his honour.

Marsden (1967) studied the main effects of planetary perturbations on the orbit of sungrazers both from a simplified analytical theory as well as numerical integrations of typical trajectories. New orbit determinations were done for some observed members of the Kreutz family. Overall the evolution of the Kreutz members was confirmed to an accurate degree.

Marsden (1989) improved on the earlier analysis by utilising orbits defined with respect to the barycentre of the solar system. This showed that there is a prevailing direction to the evolution of the orbits of Kreutz family members. It showed that except one member all the observed Kreutz sungrazers originated from a comet visible around the year 1100.

Hasegawa & Nakano (2001) estimates the time of perihelion passages for 24 candidates of the Kreutz family from Japanese, Korean and Chinese historical records. This work looked into many ancient cometary records to find evidence of unknown sungrazing candidates.

Strom (2002) discusses the previously unrecognised sungrazers in the ancient Chinese solar observations. Many of the objects recorded by Chinese observers were the bright nuclei of sungrazing comets. This data corresponds to seventeenth century which was not studied before.

Sekanina & Chodas (2012) engages in the accurate orbit determination of C/2011 W3 (Lovejoy) and its fragments which were produced after the perihelion passage. They cite the intense thermal stress as the likely reason for fragmentation. They conclude that this comet is the first member of a new, 21st century group of bright Kreutz family comets. It was found that the magnitude of thermal stress on the nucleus was around 10 kPa or more soon after perihelion eventually causing the nucleus to shatter into a cloud of debris.

In the context of meteor phenomena, intuitively one would expect some of these comets to produce spectacular meteor showers (like those from many Jupiter family and Halley type comets). In case of such a shower when sungrazers are involved, there are two factors in favour of producing intense meteor phenomena. Firstly these comets pass very close to the sun ($q \sim 0.004 - 0.06$ AU) which would enable more ices to sublimate according to conventional understanding (Whipple 1950) and thereby eject more dust particles into similar orbits.

Whipple (1950) was a classic work which led to the famed dirty snowball model for comets. It was proposed (and later confirmed from satellite observations) that meteoroids are dust particles ejected from the nuclei due to sublimation of ices. Being closer to the sun could lead to more intense sublimation which thereby leads to more amounts of dust being ejected per perihelion passage to form a meteoroid stream.

Secondly some sungrazers are dynamically new comets (Bailey, Chambers & Hahn 1992), coming from the Oort-Öpik cloud into the inner solar system for the first time, suggesting a strong possibility for more volatiles in their composition. This could enhance the chances for strong outgassing and thereby the comet being very efficient in ejecting meteoroids.

Bailey, Chambers & Hahn (1992) explores the nature of sungrazing orbits produced due to the Kozai mechanism (Kozai 1962). The secular effects in perihelion distance, eccentricity and inclination over long time scales are studied in detail. They find that the minimum perihelion distance is achieved mostly in the order of 1000 revolutions which is ten times shorter than the typical dynamical ejection timescale. It is understood that destruction by solar heating, break up or physical collision, rather than dynamical changes, must be the common end state. This work applies to Halley type comet orbits and not the long period cometary orbits.

Bailey & Emel'yanenko (1996) studies the dynamical evolution of 10 Halley type comets. Mean motion resonances, secular perturbations and close encounters with planets are studied in detail. The occurrence of Kozai libration and subsequent evolution to sungrazing states is seen in some cases. Overall it is concluded that secular effects become critically important in the context of dynamical evolution. Here the effects due to Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune are taken into account. Conversion from retrograde to prograde orbits is also seen during such long term cycles. The relationship between 96P/Machholz, (944) Hidalgo and (5335) Damocles is explored.

Kozai (1962) was a pioneering work in the field of celestial mechanics. This work showed by analytical derivation that eccentricity and inclinations are anti-correlated

with each other in order to keep the Z component of angular momentum a constant. The conservation of axial symmetry of the system leads to evolution from less eccentric highly inclined orbits to highly eccentric (which also means low perihelion distance) less inclined orbits and vice-versa. This involves the libration of the argument of pericentre of the orbiting body (in Kozai's classic paper it was first applied to asteroids).

This Kozai mechanism is the primary reason why many high inclination cometary orbits become sungrazing over long time scales. Rather than any sudden close encounter with giant planets, these comets are driven by the slow secular effects which in turn make them come dangerously close to the sun.

Coming back to the topic of meteor phenomena, nevertheless we hardly observe any spectacular meteor activity on Earth due to these frequently observed sungrazing comets despite the two favourable physical reasons mentioned above. The work of this chapter presents a mathematical formalism of demonstrating the absence of any strong meteor shower from comet C/2012 S1 (ISON). The perihelion passage of this comet on 2013 Nov 28 was a much awaited event. Unfortunately the comet fragmented and the nucleus was lost around its perihelion passage (CBET 3731). Hence it did not survive to become a spectacular event in history.

During this mathematical analysis some comparisons are done with the famous Newton's comet C/1680 V1 due to the surprisingly similar orbital elements with ISON. The same technique is then applied to all the known sungrazing families mentioned in Marsden & Williams (2008).

Marsden & Williams (2008) is a cometary catalogue which shows the classification of sungrazing families observed so far. They list the groups and their various members together with their orbital elements. Most of them were observed by SOHO or STEREO spacecraft. 50 out of the 1490 sungrazing orbits have not been linked to any particular family.

5.2 Effect of ejection velocity on meteoroids' nodal distances

The key aim is to understand how the ejection velocities of meteoroids affect their nodal distances and whether they could exist into Earth intersecting orbits during present times.

Please refer to appendix 1 to understand the notations used here.

5.2.1 Conditions to favour meteor phenomena on Earth

Among the most critical parameters determining the feasibility of meteor showers on Earth are the ascending and descending nodal distances of meteoroid particles:

$$r_a = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{(1 + e \cos \omega)} = \frac{q(1 + e)}{(1 + e \cos \omega)} \quad (5.1)$$

$$r_d = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{(1 - e \cos \omega)} = \frac{q(1 + e)}{(1 - e \cos \omega)} \quad (5.2)$$

The necessary condition (but not sufficient) for meteor activity on Earth is: $r_a \sim 1$ AU or $r_d \sim 1$ AU. Equations (5.1) and (5.2) become

$$(1 + e \cos \omega) = q(1 + e) \quad (5.3)$$

$$(1 - e \cos \omega) = q(1 + e) \quad (5.4)$$

implying

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[(q(1+e) - 1)/e] \quad (5.5)$$

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[(1 - q(1+e))/e] \quad (5.6)$$

From the compiled observations of sungrazers (Marsden & Williams 2008) one can constrain the range of e and q . The condition $e \sim 1$ simplifies equations (5.5) and (5.6) to

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[2q - 1] \quad (5.7)$$

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}[1 - 2q] \quad (5.8)$$

For the range $q \sim [0.004 \text{ AU}, 0.06 \text{ AU}]$ which comes from observations of various sungrazing families:

equation (5.7) shows $r_a \sim 1 \text{ AU}$ only if $\omega \in [152^\circ, 173^\circ]$, $[187^\circ, 208^\circ]$;

equation (5.8) shows $r_d \sim 1 \text{ AU}$ only if $\omega \in [7^\circ, 28^\circ]$, $[332^\circ, 353^\circ]$.

Each interval spans $\sim 21^\circ$, and ω in one of these four ranges is a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for high e belonging to sungrazers to undergo meteoroid intersection with Earth.

Although predicting the presence of a meteor shower on Earth would depend on other parameters like time of nodal crossing, Earth's precise position in its own orbit at that time and width of the dust trail, predicting the absence of significant meteor activity can be done using this necessary condition concerning the geometry of nodes. In other words, it is not necessary to check if additional prerequisites hold if this condition does not hold in the first place.

5.2.2 *Separating the effects due to three components of ejection velocity*

Even if parent bodies' nodal distances are quite far from Earth's orbit, meteoroid ejection in different directions can change the nodal distances into $r_a \pm dr_a$ and $r_d \pm dr_d$ depending on the ejection velocity components. Nodal dispersion primarily depends on the range of ejection speeds involved. Therefore analysing these parameters for realistic values of cometary ejection velocities can verify whether the meteoroid stream's nodal distances can approach 1 AU or not.

The mathematical technique underlying our analysis uses Lagrange's planetary equations (page 221, Roy 2005). The relevant equations concerning this analysis are given in section 1.4.

Using equation (5.1)

$$r_a = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos \omega} \quad (5.9)$$

taking the differential,

$$dr_a = \left[\frac{\partial r_a}{\partial a} \right] da + \left[\frac{\partial r_a}{\partial e} \right] de + \left[\frac{\partial r_a}{\partial \omega} \right] d\omega \quad (5.10)$$

and finding the expressions for the partial derivatives gives

$$dr_a = \left[\frac{(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos \omega} \right] da + \left[\frac{-2ae(1 + e \cos \omega) - a \cos \omega(1 - e^2)}{(1 + e \cos \omega)^2} \right] de + \left[\frac{ae(1 - e^2) \sin \omega}{(1 + e \cos \omega)^2} \right] d\omega \quad (5.11)$$

Similarly equation (5.2),

$$r_d = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 - e \cos \omega} \quad (5.12)$$

leads to

$$dr_d = \left[\frac{\partial r_d}{\partial a} \right] da + \left[\frac{\partial r_d}{\partial e} \right] de + \left[\frac{\partial r_d}{\partial \omega} \right] d\omega \quad (5.13)$$

$$dr_d = \left[\frac{(1 - e^2)}{1 - e \cos \omega} \right] da + \left[\frac{-2ae(1 - e \cos \omega) + a \cos \omega(1 - e^2)}{(1 - e \cos \omega)^2} \right] de + \left[\frac{-ae(1 - e^2) \sin \omega}{(1 - e \cos \omega)^2} \right] d\omega \quad (5.14)$$

Equations (5.11) and (5.14) require expressions for da , de and $d\omega$. These orbital can be related to the separate velocity components using equations shown in section 1.4:

$$da = \left[\frac{2}{n\sqrt{1 - e^2}} e \sin f \right] dv_r + \left[\frac{2a\sqrt{(1 - e^2)}}{nr} \right] dv_t + [0] dv_n \quad (5.15)$$

$$de = \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{na} \sin f \right] dv_r + \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{na} (\cos E + \cos f) \right] dv_t + [0] dv_n \quad (5.16)$$

$$d\omega = \left[-\cos f \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{nae} \right] dv_r + \left[\sin f \left(1 + \frac{r}{a(1 - e^2)} \right) \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{nae} \right] dv_t + \left[\left(2 \sin^2 \left(\frac{i}{2} \right) - 1 \right) \left(\frac{r \sin(\omega + f)}{na^2 \sqrt{1 - e^2} \sin i} \right) \right] dv_n \quad (5.17)$$

Equations (5.15), (5.16), (5.17) followed by (5.11) or (5.14) express the changes in ascending and descending nodal distances in terms of of the separate radial, transverse and normal ejection velocity components at any given point in the orbit. Numerical checks confirmed these differential approximations to be valid for the ranges in dv_r , dv_t , dv_n up to $\pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (limit enforced by the gas expansion velocity) where we apply them.

The whole set of transformation equations can be expressed in matrix form:

$$dr_a = P.R \quad (5.18)$$

$$dr_d = Q.R \quad (5.19)$$

and

$$R = A \times C \quad (5.20)$$

where

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(1-e^2)}{1+e \cos \omega} & \frac{-2ae(1+e \cos \omega) - a \cos \omega(1-e^2)}{(1+e \cos \omega)^2} & \frac{ae(1-e^2) \sin \omega}{(1+e \cos \omega)^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(1-e^2)}{1-e \cos \omega} & \frac{-2ae(1-e \cos \omega) + a \cos \omega(1-e^2)}{(1-e \cos \omega)^2} & \frac{-ae(1-e^2) \sin \omega}{(1-e \cos \omega)^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} da \\ de \\ d\omega \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2e \sin f}{n\sqrt{1-e^2}} & \frac{2a\sqrt{1-e^2}}{nr} & 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2} \sin f}{na} & \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2}}{na} (\cos E + \cos f) & 0 \\ \frac{-\sqrt{1-e^2} \cos f}{nae} & \sin f \left(1 + \frac{r}{a(1-e^2)}\right) \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2}}{nae} & (2 \sin^2(\frac{i}{2}) - 1) \left(\frac{r \sin(\omega+f)}{na^2 \sqrt{1-e^2} \sin i}\right) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} dv_r \\ dv_t \\ dv_n \end{pmatrix}$$

This notation makes the visualisation easier to understand where the contributions from the normal component (in some cases) are nil.

5.3 C/2012 S1 (ISON) and C/1680 V1 (Newton's comet)

Comet C/2012 S1 (ISON) was predicted to pass very close ($q \sim 0.012$ AU) to the sun on 2013 Nov 28 and expected to be an interesting naked eye object in 2013. Unfortunately it broke up around the perihelion passage and the nucleus was lost beyond recovery (CBET 3731).

Interestingly ISON's $\omega \sim 346^\circ \in [332^\circ, 353^\circ]$ lies in the favourable range (subsection 5.2.1) for which, the descending node can be close to Earth's orbit, i.e. the perihelion direction is favourably oriented for potential meteor showers.

Specifically, for an ISON like orbit ($q=0.012$ AU and $e \sim 1$), equations (5.7) and (5.8) imply $r_a \sim 1$ AU when $\omega \sim 168^\circ$ or 192° and $r_d \sim 1$ AU when $\omega \sim 12^\circ$ or 348° (Figure 5.1), and equation (5.2) shows comet ISON itself has $r_d \sim 0.76$ AU (see Table 5.1).

Calculations outlined in Section 5.2 were done to find the nodal dispersion of meteoroids ejected over the entire range of true anomaly from 0–360°. In reality, for water ice sublimation requires that $r \sim 0.012 - 3.4$ AU (cf. Fitzsimmons & Williams 1994) which corresponds to $f \in [-174, 174]$ in the case of ISON.

Fitzsimmons & Williams (1994) discusses the estimation of size and shape of cometary

Table 5.1: Orbital elements taken from JPL Horizons, IAU Minor Planet Center, and computed nodal distances, for a few well known sungrazers (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).

Comet	q (AU)	e	i (Degrees)	ω (Degrees)	r_a (AU)	r_d (AU)
C/2012 S1 (ISON)	0.012	1.000	61.8	345.536	0.012	0.755
C/2011 W3 (Lovejoy)	0.006	0.999	134.3	53.877	0.007	0.029
C/1965 S1-A (Ikeya-Seki)	0.008	0.999	141.9	69.049	0.012	0.025
C/1680 V1 (Newton's comet)	0.006	0.999	60.5	350.613	0.006	0.881

nuclei of P/Levy 1991XI (1991 L3) when it was 3.1 AU from the sun. Although most comets outgas at this distance, the nucleus of this comet was observed to be inactive at this distance.

Previous work on comet C/1995 O1 (Hale-Bopp) has shown that CO outgassing could occur as far as 7 AU (Biver et al. 1997; Flammer et al. 1998; Enzian 1999) which corresponds to $f \in [-176, 176]$ for ISON.

Biver et al. (1997) discusses the abundances of various volatiles in C/1995 O1 (Hale-Bopp) when it was observed at 7 AU pre-perihelion to 4 AU post-perihelion.

Flammer et al. (1998) finds that gas production switched from CO-driven to water ice driven around 4 AU in comet Hale-Bopp. It was observed to outgas CO even at distances at 7.2 AU. From the effective sublimation area, they estimate the size of nucleus of about 5 km.

Enzian (1999) studies the gas flux in order to understand the evolution of CO outgassing during apparitions from Hale-Bopp and comet 46P/Wirtanen. The model showed that sublimation of CO ice at large heliocentric distances of about 7 AU produces a gradual increase in comet's activity as it comes near the sun.

These works on Hale-Bopp demonstrated the possibility and relevance of outgassing at large heliocentric distances. Hence it is reasonable to apply such distance limits for dynamically new comets like ISON. But it has to be clarified that composition of comets are very different from each other and one cannot apply this as a general rule

to all comets.

Figure 5.2(a-c) shows the change to r_d at all f for a fixed value (1 km s^{-1}) of each velocity component. For small enough changes as considered here, dr_d is proportional to ejection velocity, and the nodal displacements simply alternate signs depending on whether the velocity is positive or negative. Table 5.2 shows the maximum absolute change in r_d (also in r_a) over all f when the magnitude of the ejection velocity component is $\pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Because r_a is very far away from Earth (see Table 5.1), it is not meaningful to analyse dr_a any further for practical purposes.

Figure 5.2 and Table 5.2 show that changes in nodal distance due to radial and normal ejection velocity components are much less effective than those due to the transverse part in bringing the node close to Earth's orbit. However, a value of $dv_t = 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, even at the most suitable f , still fails to bring the orbit to Earth intersection ($r_d + dr_d \sim 0.91 \text{ AU}$).

Table 5.2: Maximum nodal displacement of meteoroids due to individual components of ejection velocity (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).

Comet	dv_r (km s^{-1})	dv_t (km s^{-1})	dv_n (km s^{-1})	$ dr_a $ (AU)	$ dr_d $ (AU)
C/2012 S1 (ISON)	0	0	± 1	3.167×10^{-3}	6.769×10^{-2}
	0	± 1	0	4.274×10^{-3}	1.503×10^{-1}
	± 1	0	0	3.166×10^{-3}	6.682×10^{-2}
C/1680 V1 (Newton's comet)	0	0	± 1	1.022×10^{-3}	5.689×10^{-2}
	0	± 1	0	1.524×10^{-3}	1.589×10^{-1}
	± 1	0	0	1.137×10^{-3}	5.691×10^{-2}

From the plots and table mentioned above, it is evident that ejection velocities well above 1 km s^{-1} could bring the node close to Earth. But most well known meteor showers (from Jupiter family and Halley type comets) show prominent activity due to meteoroids with ejection velocities of the order of 10 m s^{-1} . This has been shown by numerous earlier works comparing the predictions and observations of meteor outbursts (Jenniskens et al. 1998; Asher, Bailey & Emel'yanenko 1999; McNaught & Asher 1999; Brown & Arlt 2000; Ma & Williams 2001; Asher & Emel'yanenko 2002; Ryabova 2003; Vaubaillon, Lamy & Jorda 2006; Jenniskens et al. 2007; Rendtel 2007; Sato &

Watanabe 2007; Christou, Vaubaillon & Withers 2008; Sekhar & Asher 2014b). But it is important to point out that because q is much less for sungrazers compared to other types of comet, meteoroid ejection with higher speeds than a few tens of m s^{-1} is feasible, e.g. ejection speeds approximately proportional to r^{-1} for small r (cf. Whipple 1951; Jones 1995; Ma et al. 2002).

Whipple (1951) is a classic work that discusses (among other things) about the physically plausible ejection velocities for dust particles ejected from comets' nuclei at small heliocentric distances. A hemispherical ejection model was considered for this purpose. It was shown that meteoroid ejection velocities would be higher and more particles would be ejected near perihelion.

Jones (1995) improves upon Whipple's model by including adiabatic expansion of gases and effects of cooling due to sublimation. They find that even a very small active region can lead to very high dust production rates. Outgassing from pits and depressions on the comet's surface was discussed as well.

Szego et al. (2001) studied the rotation of 1P/Halley by taking into account the external torques due to outgassing affecting the nucleus. Ice sublimation equations are solved at each point on the sunlit surface using the surface shape derived from 1986 flyby data. It is assumed that nuclear surface is homogeneous in composition. The derived model is consistent with 1986 nucleus observations with the estimated non-gravitational forces. This was done by assuming a nucleus density of 0.5 g/cm^3 .

Ma et al. (2002) found using a different model that ejection velocities drop more sharply at large distances compared to Whipple's model. This in turn leads to 33 percent higher ejection velocities at heliocentric distances around 1 AU. The key idea is that incident radiation makes the sublimation temperature constant and does not lead to heating of nuclei.

However according to various models, ejection velocities in the range of a few km s^{-1} are unrealistic even for very low q sungrazers. The physical limit on the gas expansion

velocity forces this severe constraint.

The evolution of particles of diameter significantly less than 1 mm (usually few microns to hundreds of microns) with such high ejection velocities will be dominated by other forces (Nesvorný et al. 2011) such as radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson drag. Hence studying the geometry of nodal dispersion due to ejection velocities would not work efficiently to verify such rare (and almost visually unobservable) processes.

Nesvorný et al. (2011) study the evolution of small debris ejected from Oort Cloud Comets (OCCs). It was found that OCC particles with diameters smaller than 10 microns will be ejected from the solar system due to radiation pressure (Burns, Lamy & Soter 1979) and diameters larger than 1 mm have very low Earth impact probability. About 1 percent of particles evolve to orbits with $a \sim 1$ AU due to Poynting-Robertson drag.

Surprisingly the orbital elements of this new comet ISON in 2013 and the famous Newton's comet of 1680 have similar orbital elements (Table 5.1) which has led to speculations that they might have a common ancestor. The value of $\omega \sim 351^\circ$ (for C/1680 V1) is also favourable (Section 5.2.1), and $r_d \sim 0.88$ AU.

Similar calculations were done (Section 5.2.2) to check the nodal dispersion of ejected meteoroids. As with ISON, radial and normal components are less effective (Table 5.2) in pushing the nodes towards Earth. In principle, the transverse component of ejection velocity can bring the descending node ($r_d + dr_d \sim 1$ AU) very close to Earth's orbit at very high ejection velocities ($dv_t \sim 800$ m s⁻¹).

The absence of any known predictions or observations by Newton or other scientists at that time or later about possibly related spectacular meteor phenomena prevents any further conclusions here. If there had been any such observations, it could be evidence for high ejection speeds ~ 1 km s⁻¹, provided other conditions were satisfied such as meteoroids and Earth reaching their mutual node at the same time. In reality, there is no point in looking into these aspects any further because the link between comets

and meteor showers was only made in the 19th century and it was not known during Newton's time.

But like in the case of any meteor showers, one can immediately rule out the possibility of any strong or spectacular meteor phenomena (if only meteoroids with ejection velocities in the range close to 1 km s^{-1} have nodes intersecting Earth's orbit). There are no known recorded predictions or observations by Newton or other scientists at that time or later about any such event which nullify the argument. Hence one could expect such a regime (especially because q of C/2012 S1 is almost twice that of C/1680 V1 i.e. which means even lesser ejection velocities for an ISON like orbit) in the case of ISON as well.

Although both these comets could have different evolution in terms of other parameters like timing of reaching the node and position of Earth during their arrival at the node, it is reasonable to compare them in terms of ejection velocities and nodal displacements. Since that is a necessary condition for intersection with Earth, it is still important to rule out any brilliant meteor phenomena.

For comparison, the well known sungrazers C/2011 W3 (Lovejoy) and C/1965 S1-A (Ikeya-Seki) do not have ω in the favourable range discussed in Section 5.2.1. As expected their nodes are far away (see Table 5.1) from Earth's orbit. A similar analysis in terms of the ejection velocity components showed the nodes of meteoroids remain significantly below 1 AU even at very high ejection velocities (dv_t, dv_r, dv_n to 1 km s^{-1}). Hence meteor activity on Earth from particles ejected from these comets in present times can also be completely ruled out.

5.4 Marsden family versus other sungrazing families

A search among 1440 compiled orbits of sungrazers belonging to various known sungrazing families (Marsden & Williams 2008) showed that only 27 of these orbits have ω in the favourable ranges mentioned in Section 5.2.1 (see Table 5.3; note that 50 of

1490 sungrazing comets listed have not been linked to any specific families).

Table 5.3: Distribution of sungrazing families from Catalogue of Cometary Orbits 2008 (taken from Sekhar & Asher 2014a).

Family	Number of comets	Bodies favouring the range in ω so that $r_a \sim 1$ AU or $r_d \sim 1$ AU
Kreutz	1277	0
Meyer	89	0
Marsden	32	27
Kracht 1	31	0
Kracht 2	4	0
Kracht 3	2	0
Anon 1	3	0
Anon 2	2	0

All of these 27 comets are Marsden family. This is a family of comets (like other families) which has been known to have originated from the same parent body in the past. A total of 32 Marsden members have been observed so far. The dynamical evolution of them was studied in detail by Brian Marsden and hence they were named in his honour.

It is reasonable to assume that out of this small number of favourable parent bodies, a few of them might have fallen into the sun or tidally fragmented (like the Kreutz family discussed in Biesecker et al. 2002) which thereby makes the number of possible candidates even smaller.

Biesecker et al. (2002) argues that LASCO comets which have nuclei in the range of a few to tens of metres experience their first and last apparition as unique fragments and none can be found across perihelion. The overall conclusion is that most Kreutz members end their life during their perihelion passage.

Another factor is that many of these sungrazers have very small sizes (Isele et al. 2002). Diameter is considered as an important parameter for the outgassing phenomenon in Whipple's model. According to Whipple's derivation:

$$V_{eject} = \left(\frac{1}{n_s r^{9/4}} - 0.052 R_c \right)^{1/2} R_c^{1/2} \times 328 \text{cm/s} \quad (5.21)$$

where V_{eject} is the ejection velocity, s is particle radius (in cm), R_c is cometary radius (in km) and r is the heliocentric distance in AU.

Iseli et al. (2002) derives upper size limits for sungrazers which are completely destroyed during perihelion passages. They argue that most disrupted sungrazers have sizes of just the order of tens of metres.

Our calculations (using equations 5.1 and 5.2) confirm that r_a and r_d are significantly less than 1 AU for all other sungrazing families. Thus only Marsden family comets have conditions favourable to produce meteoroids that can encounter Earth in present times (although comets from other families could have favourable conditions, in terms of the right combination of ω and q , to produce meteor phenomena during their distant past or future). Long term changes in these orbital elements are not analysed in this work.

Marsden family members have $r_d \in [0.16, 4.76]$ AU. The range for the 27 most favourable members (cf. Table 5.3) is $r_d \in [0.81, 4.63]$ AU. Figure 5.3 (a–c) shows the change to r_d at all f due to each ejection velocity component; these plots are virtually identical for all Marsden family members. Figure 5.3 (a) shows that the transverse component dv_t is most effective in changing the nodal distance so that it can come near 1 AU. For values of f where dv_t is ineffective, both dv_r and dv_n can be significant (Figure 5.3 (b–c)), although dv_n is most effective near aphelion where normal meteoroid ejection is not expected.

Earlier works (Ohtsuka et al. 2003; Sekanina & Chodas 2005; Jenniskens et al. 2012) have proposed that the Marsden family could be linked to the daytime Arietids (171 ARI, IAU-MDC).

Ohtsuka et al. (2003) finds that orbital elements of comet 96P/Machholz at epoch 2319 A.D. correspond to both the daytime Arietids (ARI) and the Marsden family. Furthermore they show that 96P/Machholz at epoch 2408 agrees with Kracht family. Time lags between that of the orbit of these groups are of the order of a few hundreds of years. The basic conclusion is that 96P/Machholz, Arietids, Marsden and Kracht

groups form a complex.

Jenniskens et al. (2012) studies the orbits of a short period Marsden sunskirter and shows that daytime Arietid meteors observed using their camera network can be linked to this comet. The theoretical orbital evolutions and predictions match the presently observed ARI shower and hence makes the case for this association stronger which was postulated before by other authors.

Our calculations show that Marsden family members typically need ejection velocities of at least a few hundred m s^{-1} so that $r_d \pm dr_d \sim 1 \text{ AU}$. The number of large meteoroids (diameters $> 1 \text{ mm}$) having high ejection velocities of a few to several hundred m s^{-1} (required to bring their nodes close to Earth's orbit in this case) will be quite small (cf. discussion in section 5.3).

Our analysis specifically shows that ejection speeds of some hundreds of m s^{-1} from most Marsden family sungrazers can produce meteoroids whose descending node is at 1 AU. This is in accord with the proposed association discussed before (by Ohtsuka et al. 2003; Sekanina & Chodas 2005; Jenniskens et al. 2012) with 171 ARI which has $\omega \sim 20\text{--}30^\circ$, similar to the Marsden family (cf. equation 5.8). Long term evolution to induce a substantial ω separation is not required for this to happen. Various members of the Marsden family in the dataset we used had perihelion passages during 1996–2008, and a range in ω that can easily arise in the short term (even a single revolution). In the short term, the nodal distances r_d remain in the range resulting from the ejection velocities discussed here. Hence such an analysis remains valid. However in long term, for multiple revolutions ω would be different and hence using the approach mentioned in this chapter would not be appropriate.

However it is important to note that changes in orbital elements, due e.g. to planetary perturbations, would be substantial during long term evolution, over which different points in the ω precession cycle may be reached. Previous works (Ohtsuka et al. 2003, Sekanina & Chodas 2005) have found that the Kracht group ($\omega \sim 50^\circ$) could be linked to the Marsden family and daytime Arietids during their long term evolution.

Furthermore Sekanina & Chodas (2005) identified a possible connection between the Southern δ Aquariids (005 SDA) which have $\omega \sim 150^\circ$ (meteor shower at ascending node; equation 5.7) and the Marsden and Kracht groups.

Sekanina & Chodas (2005) discusses the idea that the 96P/Machholz complex can also be linked to the Southern δ Aquariids. They find that the precursors of this shower of the 1950s passed through the Marsden family stage around 1700s and through the Kracht family stage in 1780s. It appears that the Daytime Arietids are related most directly to Marsden group. All fragments have similar orbital evolution but they reach the same stage (dependent on the value of ω) at different epochs. In theory, the present day Marsden family would in future go through a Kracht group stage and then through the Southern δ Aquariids stage. But in reality, the short physical lifetime (compared to dynamical life time $\sim 10^5$ yr) interrupts this evolution.

The nominal orbital periods of most Marsden sungrazers are very high ($\sim 10^3 - 10^6$ yr) because a is large. Hence the orbital evolution of meteoroids for subsequent revolutions was not checked. At the upper end of this period range, long term future predictions for meteor showers from this family would even require a completely independent analysis including other effects due to perturbations from galactic tides or passing stars. The same limitation applies for the long term evolution of meteoroids from ISON where original $1/a \sim 9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ AU}^{-1}$ (taken from IAU-MPC before ISON's disruption) and Newton's comet where $a \sim 444 \text{ AU}$ (JPL Horizons) as well. The accuracy of conventional long term predictions (usually applied to Jupiter family and Halley type comets) of meteor showers without considering these additional effects will be questionable when orbital periods are very high (which applies to most sungrazers observed so far).

Similar calculations (like in the case of ISON and Marsden family) were done on the orbits of other sungrazing families (as mentioned in Table 5.3). Our calculations clearly show that no realistic ejection velocities in any direction can bring the nodes of meteoroids close to Earth's orbit, $r_a \pm dr_a$ and $r_d \pm dr_d$ for all these cases (during

present times) remaining significantly small compared to 1 AU.

5.5 Nodal Dispersion in 1P/Halley and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle

For comparisons between sungrazing orbits and Halley-type cometary orbits in this context of nodal dispersion, a similar analysis was repeated on comets Halley and Tempel-Tuttle as well.

Figure 5.4 (a) and (b) shows the heliocentric distances of ascending and descending nodes respectively for different values of ω for a Halley like ($q \sim 0.58$ AU, $e \sim 0.968$) orbit. Halley's $\omega \sim 112^\circ$ during present times. For the past 3000 years, Halley's ω has precessed from 72° (in 1404 B.C.) to 112° (1986 A.D.). The plots clearly show that both Halley's nodes can be near Earth during present times. This is precisely the reason why we observe two meteor showers now, namely Orionids at the ascending node and Eta Aquariids at the descending node respectively. Previous works (Christou, Vaubaillon & Withers 2008) have shown interesting aspects of the Orionids and Eta Aquariids shower being possible at other planets like Venus and Mars during different cycles in ω .

Figure 5.5 (a) and (b) shows the heliocentric distances of ascending and descending nodes respectively for different values of ω for a Tempel-Tuttle like ($q \sim 0.98$ AU, $e \sim 0.906$) orbit. Tempel-Tuttle's $\omega \sim 173^\circ$ during present times. The plots clearly show that only the descending node can be near Earth during present times. The ascending node is very far away from Earth's orbit. In contrast the descending node is within 0.001 AU of Earth's orbit during recent epochs.

Table 5.4 lists the orbital elements and computed nodal distances during present times for Halley (JD 2449400.5) and Tempel-Tuttle (2451040.5). Orbital elements were retrieved from JPL Horizons (Giorgini et al. 1996).

Figures 5.6 (a–c) and 5.7 (a–c) show the effect of each component of ejection velocity

Table 5.4: Orbital elements (from JPL Horizons) and computed nodal distances during present times for Halley and Tempel-Tuttle

Comet	q (AU)	e	i (Degrees)	ω (Degrees)	r_a (AU)	r_d (AU)
1P/Halley	0.586	0.967	162.263	111.332	1.79	0.837
55P/Tempel-Tuttle	0.976	0.906	162.487	172.500	18.48	0.98

on ascending and descending nodal distances respectively, as a function of true anomaly in Halley. Both these set of plots and nodal distances presented in Table 5.4 show that meteoroids ejected from Halley during present times cannot reach near the Earth's orbit even at high ejection velocities. Our numerical simulations also show that only particles ejected from this comet at least a thousand years back can come into Earth intersection during present times (cf. chapter 2). Hence this analysis using Lagrange's planetary equations can be used as a quick test to check the feasibility of meteor showers from particles ejected from comets at different epochs.

Figures 5.8 (a-c) and 5.9 (a-c) show the effect of each component of ejection velocity on ascending and descending nodal distances respectively, as a function of true anomaly in Tempel-Tuttle. Looking at the value of $r_a \sim 18.48$ AU (shown in Table 5.4) and maximum change in nodal distance (as per figure 5.8), it is clear that ascending nodes of meteoroids cannot reach near Earth's orbit for feasible ejection velocities. On the other hand, it is clear that descending nodes can reach Earth intersecting orbit at small ejection speeds which leads to higher density of particles as found by other previous works (Vaubailon et al. 2003; Asher 2008, 2010). Results of this analysis is consistent with the real Leonid meteor shower (occurring at the descending node) which we observe during present times.

Asher (2008) describes a method to calculate trail cross section once an ejection model is selected. Such models if made for a range of ejection parameters of storms and outbursts can quantitatively constrain the process of the meteoroid ejection mechanism from the nucleus. This includes the mass distribution of particles as well.

Asher (2010) shows that the young trails in different meteoroid streams have different

shape cross sections. This would mean that there will be different activity profiles when Earth intersection occurs. The Leonid trails show elliptical cross sections whereas Perseid trails have unique structures. The comparison between theory and observations have reached a significant level (accuracy of about ten minutes) during present times.

5.6 Summary and Discussion

The necessary (but not sufficient) condition to create meteor showers on Earth as an immediate result of particles ejected from high e sungrazers is that their orbits lie in a favourable range in ω thereby enabling the ascending or descending nodes to closely approach Earth's orbit.

The sungrazing comet C/2012 S1 (ISON), had $\omega \sim 346^\circ$. Although this is unusually (for sungrazers) very close to the ideal condition of $r_d \sim 1$ AU, which would occur if $\omega \sim 348^\circ$, the descending node nevertheless does not extend to the Earth's orbit ($r_d \sim 0.76$ AU when $\omega \sim 346^\circ$). Moreover quite high ejection velocities do not bring meteoroids to intersect the Earth's orbit ($r_d + dr_d \sim 0.91$ AU for 1 km s^{-1} ejection). This is sufficient to prove the absence of strong meteor activity from this comet.

The compiled observational records of sungrazers (Marsden & Williams 2008) show that only the Marsden family have ω in this favourable range. We find that 27 out of 32 Marsden family comets lie in this range. The other sungrazing families have ω far from this small range during present epochs and their nodes cannot reach near Earth. This in turn explains why we hardly see any prominent meteor activity from the frequently observed sungrazers of many different groups.

Surprisingly out of all observed sungrazing family members (listed in Marsden & Williams 2008), none of them have orbits such that small meteoroid ejection velocities ($\sim 1 - 100 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) lead to meteor phenomena on Earth (even the Marsden family typically requiring some hundreds of m s^{-1}). It would be very interesting to repeat these calculations for the sungrazers which are going to visit us in future and check whether

any of them have a combination of orbital elements so as to become an exception from this general trend. The idea is to map out the regions of phase space of Keplerian elements favourable for inducing nodal dispersion so as to reach Earth intersecting orbits at low ejection speeds.

On a general note, calculations along these lines can help for forecasting potential meteor showers on Venus especially because Venus is closer to the sun compared to Earth (see small nodal distances in Table 5.1, particularly C/2012 S1 having r_d close to the Venusian semi-major axis of 0.72 AU). Hence much smaller ejection velocities (which are obviously more common in nature) could induce sufficient nodal dispersion in meteoroids to reach near the orbit of Venus. This idea gives scope for future work using similar techniques on sungrazers.

In order to have some comparisons between sungrazing orbits and Halley type orbits in this context, similar calculations were done on Halley and Tempel-Tuttle. It was seen that meteoroids ejected from Halley during present times cannot have either nodes near Earth intersection for feasible ejection velocities. But in Tempel-Tuttle, descending nodes can come very near Earth for practically allowed ejection speeds. All these comparisons agree with previous numerical simulations. Hence an independent test through numerical integrators affirm the credibility of this analysis.

Figure 5.1: Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for an ISON like ($q \sim 0.012$ AU, $e \sim 1$) orbit

Figure 5.2: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For C/2012 S1 ISON when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.3: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For Marsden family comets when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.4: Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for a Halley like ($q \sim 0.58$ AU, $e \sim 0.968$) orbit

Figure 5.5: Heliocentric distances of (a) ascending and (b) descending nodes versus argument of pericentre for a Tempel-Tuttle like ($q \sim 0.98$ AU, $e \sim 0.906$) orbit

Figure 5.6: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on ascending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 1P/Halley when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.7: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 1P/Halley when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.8: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on ascending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 55P/Tempel-Tuttle when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.9: Effect of each component of ejection velocity on descending nodal distance, as a function of true anomaly. For 55P/Tempel-Tuttle when (a) transverse; (b) radial; (c) normal component = 1 km s^{-1} .

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

The structure and contents of this thesis were the result of trying to answer various interesting questions (concerning meteoroid stream dynamics) which flowed from one to another in a more-or-less spontaneous and unforeseen way. Hence all four chapters are deeply interwoven in a fundamental way. But the specific goals and techniques employed in different chapters can also be considered distinct and self contained pieces of research.

The start of the project was focused on understanding the role of Jovian resonances in the Orionid and Leonid streams. Using many simulations, I was able to correlate numerical integrations and historical observations recorded by different civilisations. In parallel, the resonant motion of parent bodies 1P/Halley and 55P/Tempel-Tuttle itself was studied as well. Halley was trapped in 1:6 Jovian resonance from 1404 B.C. to 690 B.C. and in 2:13 Jovian resonance from 240 B.C. to 1700 A.D. Tempel-Tuttle was in the 5:14 Jovian resonance for about 2,000 years starting from 1366 A.D. Interestingly it is likely to be trapped in 4:11 Jovian resonance for about 1,000 years continuously, in the distant future (after few thousands of years). It was found that when a parent body

itself is in resonance with Jupiter, it would enhance the chances for ejected meteoroids to get trapped in the same resonance mechanism and thereby cause meteor outbursts or storms in subsequent years.

These calculations eventually led to the question whether similar resonant effects could be induced by Saturn's gravitational forces. The main challenge was to separate the Jovian and Saturnian periodic effects in meteoroid particles because of the 5:2 near commensurability between these two massive planets. This was done by using the well known D'Alembert rules in celestial mechanics. Typically the strength of resonance is higher when the order of resonant argument is lower. Here strength refers to the amount of time particles get trapped in resonances. Thus it was found that Saturnian resonances of lower order could very well become relevant when the nearby Jovian resonance is of much higher order (and hence much weaker). After many simulations, eventually it was found that strong and active Saturnian resonant sub-structures could be found in the Orionid and Leonid streams. The existence of 1:3 and 8:9 Saturnian resonances were demonstrated in Orionids and Leonids respectively. Analysis of key orbital parameters in different phase planes led to the finding that very dense dust trails due to Saturnian resonances are indeed real in the present day stream. The 1:3 and 8:9 resonant structures in Orionids and Leonids typically remain librating for about 4,000 and 700 years respectively. One was able to see the contrast between the resonant dust trails induced by Saturn's influence and the highly scattered non-resonant structures in both meteoroid streams.

The elaborate simulations pertaining to Jovian and Saturnian resonance mechanisms involved the study of long term orbital evolution of test particles in the Newtonian gravitational model. This raised the question as to whether any general relativistic effects are to be taken into account and whether it could affect the long term meteor shower forecasts. Because the general relativistic orbital precession is more significant in low perihelion distance orbits, a precession calculation was done on low perihelion distance meteoroid streams (out of all the established showers given in IAU-MDC)

for long time scales of the order of thousands of years. Using fundamental calculus, it was found that there can be some specific values in argument of pericentre when the errors in the calculations of nodal distances of meteoroid particles could become even more pronounced owing to the contribution from the precession in argument of pericentre due to general relativity. The maximum general relativistic precession in argument of pericentre ($\sim 5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ degrees per kyr) was noted in the Northern Daytime ω Cetid shower. The highest change in nodal distance ($\sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ AU per kyr) due to the general relativistic precession was found in the Daytime Arietid shower. Later it was understood that although a simple Newtonian model works well for most meteor showers at present epochs, there could be some interesting combinations (or epochs) in orbital elements when neglecting the relativistic precession can lead to wrong predictions for dust trail-Earth intersections.

The primary focus on low perihelion distance in that work led to another question as to why meteor showers are not usually common from frequently observed sungrazing comets. Using some simple algebra on the sungrazing orbits observed so far, it was found that only the comets with some specific ranges in argument of pericentre will be able to have the ascending or descending nodes near the Earth's orbit. The nodes of comets with argument of pericentre values lying outside this range are very far from Earth's orbit. The next step was to analyse whether any feasible meteoroid ejection velocities (maximum of 1 km/s) in nature could induce sufficient nodal dispersion to bring nodes very close to Earth's orbit so that meteors could be observed. These calculations were done by using Lagrange's planetary equations which essentially express the change in various Keplerian orbital elements as a function of ejection velocities in transverse, radial and normal directions separately. Applying these equations on the orbits of C/2012 S1 (ISON) and C/1680 V1 (Newton's comet) showed that even for very high ejection velocities, the nodes do not reach the Earth's orbit. In order for the node to reach Earth's orbit, the required ejection velocities for ISON and Newton's comet is more than about 1 km/s and 800 m/s respectively. However it was found that feasible ejection velocities (about some hundreds of m/s) in the Marsden family

of comets can bring their nodes to Earth intersecting orbits. This is in close agreement with previous works by other authors which link the Marsden family of comets with the Daytime Arietids and Southern delta Aquariids.

On a more general note, the key conclusion throughout all the calculations and analysis in this thesis points to the fundamental stochastic and chaotic nature of solar system orbits. In most cases, one could find that very small initial changes in orbital elements could lead to drastically different outcomes (which cannot be compared to anything better than the famous ‘Butterfly effect’ in chaos theory). The uncertain and counter intuitive nature of celestial mechanics makes the whole study void of any boredom and fills it with surprises and excitement !

Beyond a pure academic interest in meteor storms and outbursts on Earth, almost all of the calculations done in this thesis can be directly relevant for threat evaluation on spacecrafts and satellites. They are very critical for the health of space systems of various agencies. Some relevant and practical aspects of such calculations can be found in some interesting recent works (Vaubailon, Colas & Jorda 2006; Vaubailon, Lamy & Jorda 2006).

6.2 Future Work

6.2.1 Extension of Jovian Resonances Work

Calculations presented in Chapter 2 showed that 1:6 Jovian resonant particles could retain their compact structures for about 50,000 years. Out of all the Jovian resonances I have studied so far, this one is exceptionally stable and the survival times are 10 times that of other resonances. It is worthwhile to search for other similar exceptionally stable resonances like this and study all the different orbital parameter phase planes like (a, e) , (a, i) and (a, M) favourable for such long term librations. In turn such mapping of stable planes spaces could be compared to chaos studies done using MEGNO

techniques by Hinse et al. (2010). This can quantify the extent of phase spaces and survival times favouring the resonant mechanism concerning the long term evolution of different meteoroid streams.

6.2.2 Extension of Saturnian Resonances Work

Simulations in Chapter 3 showed the active role of Saturnian resonances in Orionids and Leonids. So far no observed enhanced meteor phenomena have been correlated with any Saturnian resonant dust trails. It would be an exciting direction to pursue this problem in more detail by looking at historical observational records of the most prominent showers and trying to correlate some of them with Saturnian resonances. This would mean looking for new Saturnian mean motion resonances in other streams as well. If one could find any correlation between theory and observations, it would be useful in matching the simulations and to extrapolate and predict future similar outbursts or storms.

6.2.3 Extension of General Relativistic Precession Work

The analysis shown in Chapter 4 showed the importance of taking general relativistic effects into account in specific cases of some showers and at certain epochs. Over time scales of thousands of years, it is expected that radiation pressure and Poynting-Robertson drag would become important for small (≤ 1 mm) meteoroid particles. Their orbital evolution would be significantly different from much bigger (≥ 1 mm and higher) meteoroid particles whose orbits would of course undergo continuous general relativistic precession every revolution. This can in turn lead to substantial shifts at their nodal distances. The different evolution of both sets of particles can lead to dust trails intersecting Earth at different times in future. If the theoretical simulations incorporating general relativity can reproduce real observations, it will act as a strong independent test of general theory so far.

6.2.4 Extension of Sungrazing Orbits Work

The mathematical techniques in Chapter 5 showed that only a small range in the argument of pericentre would allow nodes to come near the Earth in the case of already observed sungrazing comets. Outside these favourable ranges, it is even less likely for feasible ejection velocities to lead to sufficient nodal dispersion in meteoroids so as to intersect the Earth. This is consistent with the fact that visually spectacular meteor showers are extremely rare from sungrazing comets. As a next step it would be interesting to map out the entire phase space of Keplerian orbital elements and check what subset of the phase space can lead to Earth intersecting orbits for very small meteoroid ejection velocities (\sim few 10 m/s). In future, when any such example of meteor phenomena are observed on Earth, it would be strong evidence in favour of this prediction made by Lagrange's planetary equations.

6.2.5 Kozai Resonance and Meteoroid Stream Dynamics

It is a well known fact that certain Halley type comets undergo Kozai librations (Kozai 1962) during their dynamical lifetimes (Bailey, Chambers & Hahn 1992). From some of my previous simulations it has been found that high eccentricity and low inclination (both prograde and retrograde near ecliptic inclinations) are more suitable for strong resonant mechanisms. This would essentially mean that the initial eccentricity and inclination of meteoroid orbits (or cometary orbits) play a key role in their subsequent resonant dynamical evolution. It would be a fascinating test to check the difference in resonant dust trails' evolution from both extreme ends of the Kozai cycle of the same comet. The strength and stability of libration can play a significant role in the further evolution of the substructures.

6.2.6 Ancient Meteor Records

There are plenty of compiled ancient records concerning various meteor outbursts and storms in the Korean, Japanese and Chinese records (Imoto & Hasegawa 1958; Ahn 2003, 2004). Recently Mr Hutch Kinsman presented some very interesting results related to ancient Mayan meteor records at the Meteoroids 2013 conference in Poland. There is enough scope to try out various simulations in all these different streams and check whether any of these outbursts or storms were due to any Jovian or Saturnian resonance mechanism. If such historical observations can be matched directly and accurately, it would be a further confirmation of the orbit of the parent body beyond its real observations.

Bibliography

- Adams J.C., 1867, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 27, 247.
- Ahn S. H., 2003, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 343, 1095.
- Ahn S. H., 2004, *Earth, Moon & Planets*, 95, 63.
- Anolik M. V., Krasinsky G. A., Pius L. J., 1969, *Trudy Astronomicheskoy Observatorii Leningrad*, 14, 3.
- Arlt R., Molau S., Currie M., 1998, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 26, 153.
- Arlt R., Rendtel J. and Bader P. 2008, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 36, 55.
- Asher D. J., Clube S. V. M., 1993, *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 34, 481.
- Asher D. J. 1999, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 307, 919.
- Asher D. J., Bailey M. E. and Emel'yanenko V. V., 1999, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 304, L53.
- Asher D. J. and Emel'yanenko V. V., 2002, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 331, 126.
- Asher D. J. 2008, *Earth Moon & Planets*, 102, 27.
- Asher D. J. 2010, *Proceedings of the International Meteor Conference, Pore, Croatia, 24-27 September, 2009* Edited by Andreic, Z.; Kac, J. International Meteor Organization.
- Bailey M.E., Chambers J.E., Hahn G., 1992, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 257, 315.
- Bailey M. E. and Emel'yanenko V. V. 1996, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 278, 1087.
- Biesecker D.A., Lamy P., Cyr O.C., Llebaria A., Howard R.A. 2002, *Icarus* 157, 323.

- Biver, N., Bockelée-Morvan, D., Colom, P., et al. 1997, *Earth Moon & Planets*, 78, 5.
- Brouwer D., van Woerkom A. J. J., 1950, *Astron. Papers American Ephemeris and Nautical Almanac*, 13, 81.
- Brown P., Jones J. 1996, *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series; Proceedings of the 150th colloquium of the International Astronomical Union held in Gainesville; Florida; USA; 14-18 August 1995; San Francisco:Astronomical Society of the Pacific (ASP 104); edited by Bo A. S. Gustafson and Martha S. Hanner, p.113.*
- Brown P., 1999, *Icarus*, 138, 287.
- Brown P., Arlt R., 2000, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 319, 419.
- Brown P., 2001, PhD thesis, University of Western Ontario, Canada.
- Brown P., Campbell M., Suggs R., Cooke W., Theijsmeijer C., Hawkes R. L., Jones J., Ellis K. J., 2002, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 335, 473.
- Burns J. A., Lamy P. L., Soter S. 1979, *Icarus*, 40, 1.
- Central Bureau Electronic Telegram No. 944 dated 2007 Apr 25.
- Central Bureau Electronic Telegram No. 3731 dated 2013 Dec 1.
- Carusi, A., Kresak, L., Perozzi, E., Valsecchi, G. B. 1986, In *ESA Proceedings of the 20th ESLAB Symposium on the Exploration of Halley's Comet. Volume 2: Dust and Nucleus*, p.413.
- Chambers J. E. 1999, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 304, 793.
- Christou A. A., Vaubaillon J., and Withers P. 2008, *Earth, Moon, and Planets*, 102, 125.
- Christou A. A., 2010, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 402, 2759.
- Christou A. A., Asher D. J., 2011, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 414, 2965.
- Clemence G. M., 1943, *Astronomical Journal*, 50, 126.
- D'Alembert 1750, *Histoire de l'acadmie royale des sciences et belles lettres de Berlin*, 6, 355.
- Denning W. F. 1899, *The Observatory* 22, 90.
- Dubietis A. 2003, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)* 31, 43.
- Einstein A. 1915, *Preussische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Sitzungsberichte*, 831.
- Emel'yanenko V. V., Bailey M. E., 1996, in *Gustafson B. A. S., Hanner M. S., eds, ASP Conf. Ser. Vol. 104, Physics, Chemistry, and Dynamics of Interplanetary Dust. Astron. Soc. Pac., San Francisco, p. 121*
-

- Emel'yanenko V. V. 1988, *Soviet Astronomy Letters* 14, 278.
- Emel'yanenko V. V. 2001, Resonance structure of meteoroid streams. In *Proceedings of the Meteoroids 2001 Conference (ESA SP-495)*, Edited by Warmbein B. Noordwijk: ESA. pp. 43-45.
- Enzian, A. 1999, *Space Science Reviews*, 90, 131.
- Everhart E. 1985, An efficient integrator that uses Gauss-Radau spacings, In *Proceedings of IAU Colloq. 83*, Edited by Andrea Carusi and Giovanni B. Valsecchi, *Astrophysics and Space Science Library* 115, 185
- Fitzsimmons, A., Williams I. P. 1994, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 289, 304.
- Flammer, K. R., Mendis, D. A., Houppis, H. L. F. 1998, *Astrophysical Journal*, 494, 822.
- Flamsteed J., 1685, *Philosophical Transactions*, London, p244.
- Fox K., Williams I.P., Hughes D.W. 1982, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 199, 313.
- Giorgini J.D., Yeomans D.K., Chamberlin A.B., Chodas P.W., Jacobson R.A., Keesey M.S., Lieske J.H., Ostro S.J., Standish E.M., and Wimberly R.N. 1996, JPL's On-Line Solar System Data Service, *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 28(3), 1158
- Hajduk A. 1986, Meteoroids from Comet Halley and the comets mass production and age. In *ESA Proceedings of the 20th ESLAB Symposium on the Exploration of Halley's Comet*, 2, 239.
- Halley E. 1676, *Philosophical Transactions*, London, p683.
- Halley E. 1705, *Synopsis Astronomiae Cometicae*, London.
- Hasegawa I., Nakano S. 2001, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan*, 53, 931.
- Herschel A. S. 1866, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 26, 51.
- Hill G. W., 1890, *Astronomical Papers of American Ephemeris and Nautical Almanac*, vol. 4.
- Hinse T. C., Christou A. A., Alvarellos J. L., Goździewski K. 2010, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 404, 837.
- Hughes D. W. 1985, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 213, 103.
- Hughes D.W. and McBride N. 1989, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 240, 73.
- Imoto S. and Hasegawa I. 1958, *Smithsonian Contributions to Astrophysics* 2, 131.
- Iorio L. 2005, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 431, 385.
-

- Iseli M., Kuppers M., Benz W., Bochsler P. 2002, *Icarus* 155, 350.
- International Meteor Organisation Records (<http://www.imo.net/zhr>)
- Jenniskens P. 2006. *Meteor showers and their parent comets*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Jenniskens P., Lyytinen E., Nissinen M., Yrjola I., and Vaubaillon J. 2007, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 35, 125.
- Jenniskens, P., Betlem, H., de Lignie, M., Ter Kuile, C., van Vliet, M. C. A., van 't Leven, J., Koop, M., Morales, E., Rice, T. 1998, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 301, 941.
- Jenniskens P., Duckworth H., Grigsby B. 2012, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 40, 98.
- Jones, J. 1995, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 275, 773.
- Katasev L.A., Kulikova N. V. 1972, *The Motion, Evolution of Orbits, and Origin of Comets; Proceedings from IAU Symposium no. 45, held in Leningrad, U.S.S.R., August 4-11, 1970*. Edited by Gleb Aleksandrovich Chebotarev, E. I. Kazimirchak-Polonskaia, and B. G. Marsden. International Astronomical Union. Symposium no. 45, Dordrecht, Reidel, p.498
- Kepler J. 1609, *Astronomia Nova*, Heidelberg.
- Kepler J. 1619, *Harmonices Mundi Libri V*. Linz.
- Kepler J. 1672, *Keplerus et Berneggerus Epistolae mutuae*, p70.
- Kero J., Szasz C., Nakamura T., Meisel D.D., Ueda M., Fujiwara Y., Terasawa T., Miyamoto H. and Nishimura K., 2011, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 416, 2550.
- Kirkwood D. 1860, *Astronomical Journal*, 136, 126.
- Kondrat'eva E.D. and Reznikov E.A. 1985, *Solar System Research*, 19, 96.
- Kondrat'eva E. D., Murav'eva I. N. & Reznikov E. A. 1997, *Solar System Research*, 31, 489.
- Kozai Y. 1962, *Astronomical Journal*, 67, 591.
- Kozai Y. 1979, *Secular perturbations of asteroids and comets*. In *Dynamics of the solar system*. Proceedings IAU Symposium 81. Edited by Duncombe R.L. Dordrecht: Reidel Publishing Co., pp. 231.
- Kresak L. 1987, *The Evolution of the Small Bodies of the Solar System*, Proceedings of the International School of Physics "Enrico Fermi". Edited by M. Fulchignoni, and L. Kresak. Amsterdam, Elsevier, pp. 202.
- Kreutz H. 1888, *Astronomische Nachrichten*, 119, 381.
-

- Kronk G. W. 1988. Meteor Showers: a descriptive catalog. Hillside, NJ: Enslow Publishers.
- Lagrange J. L. 1811, *Mécanique Analytique*.
- Laplace P. S. 1785, *Mémoires de l' Académie des Sciences*, p33.
- LeVerrier M. 1872, *Comptes Rendus*, vol.21.
- Lieske, J. H., Null G. W., 1969, *Astronomical Journal*, 74, 297.
- Lindblad B. A. and Porubcan V. 1999. Orionid Meteor Stream. *Contributions of the Astronomical Observatory of Skalnaté Pleso* 29, 77.
- Lovell A. C. B. 1954, *Meteor Astronomy*, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Lovett E. O., 1895, *Astronomical Journal*, 15, 113.
- Lyytinen E., van Flandern T. 2004, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 32, 51.
- Ma, Y., Williams, I. P. 2001, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 325, 379.
- Ma, Y., Williams, I. P., Chen, W. 2002, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 337, 1081.
- Marsden, B. G. 1967, *Astronomical Journal*, 72, 1170.
- Marsden B.G., Sekanina Z. and Yeomans D.K. 1973, *The Astronomical Journal* 78, 211.
- Marsden, B. G. 1989, *Astronomical Journal*, 98, 2306.
- Marsden, B. G. 2005, *Annual Reviews in Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 43, 75.
- Marsden B. G. and Williams G. V. 2008. *Catalogue of Cometary Orbits*, 17th ed. Cambridge, MA: Minor Planet Center/Central Bureau for Astronomical Telegrams.
- Maslov M. 2007, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 35, 5.
- McIntosh B. A. and Hajduk A. 1983, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 205, 931.
- McIntosh B. A. and Jones J. 1988, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 235, 673.
- McNaught R. H., Asher D. J., 1999, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation)*, 27, 85.
- Milani A., Knežević Z., 1990, *Celestial Mechanics & Dynamical Astronomy*, 49, 347.
- Millman P. M. 1936, *Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society of Canada* 30, 416.
-

- Miskotte K. 1993, WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation) 21, 292.
- Morais H., Namouni F., 2013, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters, 436, L30.
- Murray C.D. and Dermott S.F. 1999. Solar System Dynamics, Cambridge, UK, Cambridge University Press.
- Musen P. 1971, Celestial Mechanics, 4, 378.
- Nesvorný, D., Vokrouhlický, D., Pokorný, P., Janches, D. 2011, Astrophysical Journal, 743, 37.
- Newton I. 1687, Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica, London.
- Olivier C.P. 1921, Publications of the Leander McCormick Observatory 2, 201.
- Ohtsuka K., Nakano S., Yoshikawa M., 2003, Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan, 55, 321.
- Peale S. J., 1976. Annual Reviews of Astronomy & Astrophysics, 14, 215.
- Rendtel J. 2007, WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation), 35, 41.
- Rendtel J. 2008, Earth, Moon, and Planets, 102, 103.
- Rendtel J. and Betlem H. 1993, WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organisation), 21, 264.
- Roy, A. E. 1978, Orbital Motion (Bristol: Adam Hilger).
- Rudawska R., Jopek T.J., Dybczynski P.A. 2005, Earth Moon & Planets, 97, 295.
- Ryabova G. 2003, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 341, 739.
- Ryabova G. O. 2006. Meteoroid streams: mathematical modelling and observations. In Asteroids, Comets, Meteors, Proceedings IAU Symposium 229, edited by Lazzaro D., Ferraz-Mello S., Fernández J. A. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. pp. 229.
- Saha P. and Tremaine S. 1993, Icarus 106, 549.
- Sato M. and Watanabe J. 2007, Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan, 59, L21.
- Seargent, D. A. J. 2002, Minor Planet Center Circular 2002-E25 dated 2002 Mar 9.
- Sekanina, Z. 1976, Icarus, 27, 265.
- Sekanina, Z., Chodas, P. W. 2005, Astrophysical Journal Supplement, 161, 551.
- Sekanina, Z., Chodas, P. W, 2012, Astrophysical Journal, 757, 127.
- Sekhar A., 2013, WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organization), 41, 179.
-

- Sekhar A., Asher D.J., 2013, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters*, 433, L84.
- Sekhar A., Asher D.J., 2014a, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters*, 437, L71.
- Sekhar A., Asher D. J., 2014b, *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*, 49, 52.
- Shahid-Saless B., Yeomans D.K. 1994, *Astronomical Journal*, 107, 1885S.
- Shapiro I. I, Ash M. E., Smith W. B. 1968, *Astronomical Journal*, 71, 870.
- Sharaf Sh. G., Budnikova N. A. 1977, *Trudy Astronomicheskoy Observatorii Leningrad*, 16, 88.
- Sitarski G. 1992, *Astronomical Journal*, 104, 1226S.
- Spurny P. and Shrbeny L. 2008, *Earth, Moon, and Planets* 102, 141.
- Soja R. H., Baggaley W. J., Brown P., and Hamilton D. P. 2011, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 414, 1059.
- Steel D. I. 1987, *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 187, 909.
- Stoney, G. J., Downing, A. M. W., 1898, *Proceedings of the Royal Society London*, 64, 403.
- Strom, R. 2002, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 387, L17.
- Svoren J., Kanuchova Z., Jakubik M., 2006, *Icarus*, 183, 115.
- Szego K., Crifo J. F., Foldy L., Lagerros J. S. V., Rodionov A. V. 2001, *Astronomy & Astrophysics Letters*, 370, L35.
- Trigo-Rodriguez J.M., Madiedo J.M., Llorca J., Gural P.S., Pujols P., Tezel T. 2007, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 380, 126.
- Vaubailon J., Lyytinen E., Nissinen M., Asher D. J., 2003, *WGN (Journal of the International Meteor Organization)*, 31, 131.
- Vaubailon J., Lamy, P., and Jorda, L. 2006, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 370, 1841.
- Vaubailon J., Colas, F., and Jorda, L. 2006, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 450, 819.
- Venturini J., Gallardo T. 2010, *Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union Symposium No. 263*, 106.
- Watanabe J., Sato M., Kasuga T. 2005, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan*, 57, L45
- Weinberg S. 1972, *Gravitation and Cosmology: Principles and Applications of the General Theory of Relativity*, Wiley, New York.
- Whipple, F. L. 1950, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 111, 375.
-

-
- Whipple F. L. 1951, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 113, 464.
- Whipple A. L. and Shelus P. J. 1993, *Icarus* 101, 265.
- Wiegert P., Brown P. 2005, *Icarus*, 179, 139.
- Wiegert P., Vaubaillon J., Campbell-Brown M. 2009, *Icarus*, 201, 295.
- Williams I. P., 1997, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society Letters*, 292, L37.
- Williams I. P. 2011, *Astronomy and Geophysics*, 52, 2.20.
- Wu Z., Williams I. P. 1996, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 280, 1210.
- Yeomans D. K., 1981, *Icarus*, 47, 492.
- Yeomans D. K. and Kiang T. 1981, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 197, 633.
- Yeomans D. K., Yau K. K., Weissman P. R. 1996, *Icarus*, 124, 407.
- Zhuang T. S. 1977, *Chinese Astronomy*, 1, 197.
-

Appendices

Appendix A

Useful Stuff

These are the common notations and acronyms used throughout the thesis.

A.1 Notations

Variables defined below correspond to:

a - semi-major axis

e - eccentricity

q - perihelion distance

Q - aphelion distance

i - inclination

ω - argument of pericentre

Ω - longitude of ascending node

ϖ - longitude of pericentre

E - eccentric anomaly

f - true anomaly

M - mean anomaly

S, dv_r - radial component of meteoroid ejection acceleration/velocity

T, dv_t - transverse (in-plane, orthogonal to radial) component

W, dv_n - normal component

n - mean motion

P - orbital period

t - time

r - heliocentric distance

r_a, r_d - heliocentric distance of ascending/descending node

τ - perihelion passage time

Γ - connection tensor

q - order of resonance

λ - mean longitude

σ - resonant argument

M_{\odot} - mass of central body/sun

R - disturbing function

α_j - represents different Keplerian elements in transformation equations

O - origin of the coordinate system

m_1, m_2 - masses of bodies

$\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2$ - position vectors to respective masses from the coordinate system

\mathbf{r} - relative position vector between two masses

g - acceleration due to gravity

F - Newtonian force

$F(a, q)$ - function in semi-major axis and perihelion distance

L - semi-latus rectum

β, γ - parameters in Einstein's general theory

T_J - Tisserand parameter with respect to Jupiter

k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4 - coefficients in D'Alembert rule

λ_{\odot} - solar longitude

V_{eject} - ejection velocity

s - particle radius

R_c - cometary radius

A.2 Acronyms

IAU: International Astronomical Union
MMR: Mean Motion Resonances
JPL: Jet Propulsion Laboratory
MPC: Minor Planet Center
MDC: Meteor Data Center
ZHR: Zenithal Hourly Rate
GR: General Relativity
LT: Lense-Thirring
PR: Poynting-Robertson
B.C.: Before Christ Era
A.D.: Anno Domini
J.D.: Julian Date
CBET: Central Bureau Electronic Telegram
MPEC: Minor Planet Electronic Circular
MNRAS: Monthly Notices of Royal Astronomical Society
ApJ: Astrophysical Journal
EMP: Earth, Moon and Planets
AJ: Astronomical Journal
ACM: Asteroids, Comets, Meteors Conference
EPSC: European Planetary Science Congress
NAM: National Astronomy Meeting
IMC: International Meteor Conference
IMO: International Meteor Organization

A.3 Physical Constants

These are some useful constants as per IAU definitions in units of the International System of Units.

Symbol	Numerical value	Units	Quantity
G	6.67259×10^{-11}	$\text{m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$	Newton's Gravitational Constant
AU	$1.49597870700 \times 10^{11}$	m	Astronomical Unit
M_{\odot}	1.9891×10^{30}	kg	Solar Mass
R_{\odot}	6.96×10^8	m	Solar Radius
c	2.99792458×10^8	m s^{-1}	Speed of Light in Vacuum
k	$1.720209895 \times 10^{-2}$		Gaussian constant of Gravitation
d	86400	s	1 day
yr	365.25	d	Julian year
ly	63241	AU	Light-year

IAU 2012 Resolution B2 redefined AU as this exact figure shown above. k was the fundamental definition previously.

